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Biochemical Effect of Helicobacter Pylori on Immuno-Stress Biomarkers

For the PhD Degree in
(Biochemistry & Clinical Biochemistry)

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

قالوا

لسببنا انك لا تعلم لنا
إلا ما علمتنا إنك أنت
العليم العظيم

صدقة الله العظيم

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***My Dear
Children***

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List of Abbreviations

AA	: Arachidonic acid
ACTH	: adrenocorticotrophic hormone
AP	: alternative pathway
APCs	: antigen-presenting cells
APE1	: apurinic/aprimidinic endonuclease 1
B cells	: B cells are lymphocytes that play a large role in the humoral immune response
BabA	: blood group antigen-binding adhesion
BMD	: bone mineral density
C 13	: Proton Pump Inhibitor
C 14	: Food and Drug Administration
CagA	: Cytotoxin-associated gene A
CAM	: Cell adhesion molecules (CAM)
CO₂	: Carbon dioxide
COX	: Cyclooxygenase
CP	: classic pathway
CYP450	: cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes
DAG	: Diacylglycerol lipase
DAMPs	: Damage-associated molecular pattern molecules
DCs	: Dendritic cells
DNA	: deoxyribonucleic acid
dupA	: duodenal ulcer promoting gene
EC	: endothelial cells
ELIZA	: enzyme immunoassay
ESL	: E-selectin ligand
FD	: Functional dyspepsia
FDA	: The ferric uptake regulator
FGIDs	: functional gastrointestinal disorders
Fur	: Hop-related proteins
GAC	: Gastric carcinoma
G-CSF	: granulocyte colony stimulating factor,
GGT	: glutamyl transpeptidase
GI	: gastrointestinal
GM-CSF	: granulocyte-macrophage colony stimulating factor
H1 receptor	: histamine receptor

H2RA	: Histamine 2 receptor antagonist
HCC	: hepatocellular carcinoma
HCT-AMPs	: helix–coil conformation transitionable antimicrobial poly
HMGB-1	: High Motility Group Box-1
Hom	: H. pylori outer membrane
Hop	: outer membrane proteins
Hor	: Hop-related proteins
HP	: Helicobacter pylori
HPA	: hypothalamic-pituitaryadrenal axis
HPU	: H pylori urease
Hsp60	: Heat shock protein 60
ICA	: immunochromatographic assay
ICAM	: intercellular adhesion molecule
IFN-γ	: Interferon gamma
IgG	: Immunoglobulin G
IgM	: Immunoglobulin M
IL-1	: interleukin 1
IL-8	: interleukin 8
INF-α	: Human interferon alpha
IR	: Induce insulin resistance
IRFs	: Interferon regulatory factors
IS	: Immunoreactive substance
JAM	: Junctional adhesion molecule
LabA	: lacdiNAc-binding adhesin
LDH	: lactate dehydrogenase
LFA-1	: lymphocyte function-associated antigen 1
LOX	: lipoxygenase
MALT	: Mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue
MC	: Mast cells
MIF	: Macrophage migration inhibitory factor
mRNA	: Messenger Ribonucleic Acid
MS	: Metabolic syndrome
NADH	: Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) + hydrogen (H)
NAFLD	: Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease
NAP	: Neutrophil-activating protein
NapA	: Periplasmic nitrate reductase.
NEP	: Neutral endopeptidase
NF-κB	: Nuclear factor kappa-B
O₂	: Oxygen

OipA	: Outer membrane inflammatory protein adhesin
OMPs	: Outer membrane proteins
OXPPOS	: Oxidative phosphorylation
PAF	: Platelet activating factor
PAI	: H. pylori pathogenicity island
PAMPs	: Pathogen-associated molecular patterns
PCR	: Polymerase chain reaction
PECAM	: Platelet endothelial cell adhesion molecule
PG	: Peptidoglycan
PH	: Power of hydrogen
PHLG-MHH	: Poly(γ -6-N-(methyldihexylammonium)hexyl-L-glutamat
PLA2	: Phospholipase A2
PLGE	: Protein-losing gastroenteropathy
PMNLs	: Polymorphonuclear leukocytes
PPI	: Proton pump inhibitors
PPRs	: Pattern recognition receptors LP
RA	: Rheumatoid arthritis
RBCs	: Red blood cells
RCTs	: Published randomized controlled trials
ROS	: Reactive oxygen species
rRNA	: Ribosomal ribonucleic acid
SP	: It is an undecapeptide member of the tachykinin neuropeptide family.
SabA	: Sialic acid-binding adhesin
SIRS	: Systemic inflammatory response syndrome
SLE	: Systemic lupus erythematosus
SMO	: Spermine oxidase
T cells	: T cells are a subset of lymphocytes that play a large role in the immune response
T4SS	: Protein forming a type 4 secretion system
TC	: Total Cholesterol
TCA	: The tricarboxylic acid cyc
TCA	: Tricarboxylic acid
TEM	: Transendothelial cell migration
TG	: Triglycerides
TGF-b	: Transforming Growth Factor-b
TGF-β	: Transforming growth factor- β
Th	: T-helper
Th1	: T helper cell type 1
Th17	: T helper 17 cells

Th2	: T-helper type 2
TIBC	: Total iron binding capacity
TLR	: Toll-like receptors
TMB	: Tetramethylbenzidine
TNF	: Tumor necrosis factor
TNF-α	: Tumor necrosis factor-alpha
Tregs	: Regulatory T cells
UBTs	: Urea breath test
Vac-A	: Vacuolating toxin A
VLA4	: Very Late Antigen-4
VLDL	: Very low density lipoprotein
WBCs	: White blood cells.

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Introduction

Introduction

Helicobacter pylori (H pylori) is one of the most frequent chronic infections worldwide, with an overall prevalence of 32.6% in children. H pylori infection is associated with chronic gastritis, peptic ulcers, gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, and gastric cancer. For children, extra gastric complications, such as iron-deficiency anemia, Henoch-Schönlein purpura, and chronic idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, may be induced by H pylori infection. The eradication of H pylori infection has also been found to reduce the recurrence of peptic ulcers and lower the risk of gastric cancer. H pylori infection has been an important public health problem in both developing and developed countries (*Zhou et al., 2020*).

Helicobacter pylori is a gram-negative, microaerophilic bacterium that infects the stomach and can lead to, among other disorders, the development of gastric cancer. The inability of the host to clear the infection results in a chronic inflammatory state with continued oxidative stress within the tissue. Reactive oxygen species and reactive nitrogen species produced by the immune and epithelial cells damage the host cells and can result in DNA damage. H pylori has evolved to evoke this damaging response while blunting the host's efforts to kill the bacteria. This long-lasting state with inflammation and oxidative stress can result in gastric carcinogenesis (*Butcher et al, 2017*).

H pylori strains contain multiple virulence factors that may contribute to the host's production of oxidative stress. The presence of *cagA* in a strain results in an increased risk of gastric carcinogenesis compared with individuals infected with CagA-negative strains. (*Tsugawa et al, 2012*)

Figure (1): Oxidative Stress Resulting From *Helicobacter pylori*. (*Butcher et al,2017*).

H. pylori infection leads to oxidative stress. *H. pylori* infection results in ROS production by the immune and epithelial cells in an attempt to kill the bacteria. Virulence factors from *H. pylori* such as CagA are injected into the epithelial cell while VacA is secreted from the bacteria and trapped in an intracellular vesicle. The virulence factors trigger multiple cellular responses including the production of intrinsic ROS. The ROS result in DNA damage in the epithelial cells, activating APE1, which then translocates to the nucleus to regulate gene transcription and to attempt to repair the DNA. Spermine oxidase (SMO) also is activated and results in DNA damage, as well as acting on the mitochondria membrane. Immune cells recruited to the area by virulence factors including NapA release extrinsic ROS in

an attempt to clear the infection, resulting in more damage to the area (*Butcher et al, 2017*).

H. pylori, a Gram-negative, spiral-shaped bacterium that dwells on the gastric epithelium, has an influence on approximately 50% of the human population, with a high rate in those living in developing countries. The prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is approximately 30% in developed countries and up to 80% in developing countries. *H. pylori* infection induces chronic inflammation and immune responses in the stomach. *H. pylori* infection increases inflammatory factors, such as interleukin 1 (IL-1), interleukin 8 (IL-8), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α). These inflammatory factors may result in metabolic changes and systemic immune responses. Moreover, *H. pylori* is the most prevalent pathogenic bacteria in the stomach and can lead to a wide array of gastric disorders, including chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer, gastric cancer, and gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma (MALT) . It is also considered a class I carcinogen. In recent years, accumulating evidence has demonstrated the role of *H. pylori* infection in extragastrointestinal diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, neurological disorders, metabolic diseases, and kidney disease. IL-1 and TNF- α trigger bone. In addition, osteoporosis is a condition with progressively decreasing BMD and increased bone fragility, with increased risk of bone fractures (*Lu et al., 2018*).

Gastric carcinoma (GAC) is the fifth most common cancer in the world with 9% of total cancer mortality. Most of the noncardia GACs are caused by *H. pylori* infection. After *H. pylori* colonization in the stomach, which is often asymptomatic, polymorphonuclear leukocytes, macrophages, and lymphocytes infiltrate the mucosa. This inflammation together with some bacterial toxins and constituents could cause gastroduodenal ulceration, GAC, and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma. The molecular mechanisms of local immune response initiated

by H pylori are complex, but it is believed that cytokines produced by both immune and non-immune cells amplify the ongoing inflammation. To date, the pathogenesis of H pylori-related chronic gastritis and the mechanism responsible for the change into neoplasm are still debated. The carcinogenicity of H pylori through the local and systemic immune response and the roles of cytokines and chemokines have been investigated in many researches (*Salim et al., 2016*).

Although limited to the gastric mucosa, HP can trigger a local and systemic inflammatory response and consequently play a part in the development of various extragastrointestinal disorders. The bacterial peptides of HP are considered to be effective in the pathogenesis of those diseases by chronically stimulating the immune system in various mechanisms. Gastric mucosa infected by HP stimulates the release of proinflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), interferon γ (IFN- γ), interleukin-1 (IL-1), IL-6, IL-8, IL-10 and IL-12. It also triggers the cellular and humoral immune system and causes specific immune cell activation. Also it increases cytokines derived from mononuclear macrophages, stimulates neutrophil chemotaxis and its activation, and increases the expression and degranulation of adhesion molecules and the production of reactive oxygen metabolites. Therefore, it also stimulates specific immunity. This local proinflammatory effect that HP has on gastric mucosa was thought to have a potential systemic effect and activate the immune response. Following the discovery of HP, its relation to pathologies such as thrombocytopenic purpura, coronary artery disease, respiratory disorders, iron deficiency, anemia and urticaria was studied (*Dede et al., 2015*).

Currently, Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori, Hp) infection is considered the major cause of the chronic gastric inflammation of FD patients. Gastric inflammation has been shown to affect motor function and visceral sensitivity in experimental models. H. pylori strains that express CagA may be responsible for

the FD (Functional dyspepsia) associated with the more severe forms of gastritis. It was reported that CagA-positive *H. pylori* strains induced more dyspeptic symptoms than CagA negative or *H. pylori*-negative strains in patients with FD . Some of these functional symptoms can be explained by a gut-driven brain disorder, and in vivo hormonal changes have also been implicated. However, no definite clinical manifestation is linked to CagA-positive *H. pylori* strains infection or fluctuating levels of hormones in FD patients (*Meng et al., 2016*).

Fig (2):The brain-gut-microbiota axis. Postulated signaling pathways between the gut microbiota, the intestinal barrier and the brain. A dysfunctional intestinal barrier or “leaky gut” could permit a microbiota-driven proinflammatory state with implications for neuroinflammation.

Infection with *H. pylori* causes an increased concentration of IL-8, IL-1, IL-6 and TNF- α . IL-8 in tissue, which activates neutrophils, results in the epithelial cells, as well as in other cells in the wall of the stomach. Expression is dependent

on the adherence and the genotype of the *cagA*. The immune response Th1 is triggered in case of infection by intracellular pathogens and cancer, immune responses Th2 is characterized in infection by extracellular pathogens. In contrast to the expected reaction in the host with *H. pylori* infection, Th1 immune response is particular. Bacteria should choose an immune response by stimulating IL-12, which leads to a Th1 response. Thus stimulated immune system cannot overcome the infection. The cellular immune response and the formation of IgG antibodies which can activate complement cause intense inflammation and further damage to the mucosa. Neutrophils which are attracted and activated by IL-8 are an important component in the development of chronic active gastritis. The result of infection with the same strain of *H. pylori* could be different in the immune response of the different entities (*Stubljär and Skvarc.,2015*).

Although *H. pylori* is typically considered to be noninvasive because most of the bacteria reside in the mucous layer of the stomach in contact with the epithelium, studies have demonstrated that the bacterium and its products can be in direct contact with lamina propria immune cells. Consequently, infection with *H. pylori* results in a large influx of immune cells that include neutrophils, macrophages, dendritic cells, and lymphocytes, and an associated innate and adaptive immune response. Although this has been shown to include both Th1 and Th17 components, one hallmark of the response is that there is also a downregulation of effective immunity that appears to involve recruitment of regulatory T cells (Tregs) and B cells. Vaccination studies, adoptive transfer of Th1-selected lymphocytes, and efforts to suppress Treg responses have been successful at reducing or clearing the infection in mice (*Lewis et al.,2011*).

H. pylori is a microaerophilic bacterium so that anaerobic as well as aerobic metabolic pathways are possible. *H. pylori* might be able to switch between these two pathways. depending on its environment. The metabolic routes of substrate

catabolism by intact cells of *H. pylori* have been investigated by several groups. *H. pylori* is able to metabolize glucose and pyruvate under aerobic and anaerobic conditions and the metabolism of pyruvate and glucose under anaerobic conditions leads to a rapid metabolism of pyruvate to lactate by lactate dehydrogenase. On the other hand under aerobic conditions acetate is the main product generated from glucose and pyruvate by aldolase activity (**Nilius and Malfertheiner, 1996**)

Aim of the work

AIM OF THE WORK

The aim of the present study is to shed some light on the effect of H.pylori infection on immune-stress biomarker and the changes in serum albumin, Total Protein, lactate, pyruvate, Interleukin-2, Interleukin-6, CRP, and Cortisol. And illustrate how helicobacter pylori infection affects the immune system by changing the concentration of Immunoglobulins (IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE), Complement system (C3 and C4), and Autoantibodies (Anti-DNA double-strand and anti-nuclear antibody pattern).

Review

Helicobacter pylori

1-Morphology:

H. pylori (Figure 3) is a small, Gram-negative, asporogenous, S-shaped or slightly spirally curved, microaerophilic bacterium. Thirty-seven degrees Celsius and pH 4.0-6.0 are the most favorable conditions for the life, growth, and reproduction of *H. pylori*; although, the species also survives at pH 2.5. *H. pylori in vivo* and under optimum *in vitro* conditions exists as an S-shaped bacterium with 1 to 3 turns, 0.5 μm \times 5 μm in length, and a tuft of 5 to 7 polar sheathed flagella. The bacterial cell is covered with a smooth sheath. The flagellum of *H. pylori* is 30 nm in diameter, consisting of an internal filament approximately 12 nm in diameter surrounded by a sheath, the outer membrane of which is continuous with the outer membrane of the cell (*Reshetnyak et al., 2017*).

Unipolar flagella are essential for the unique motility of *H. pylori*. *Qin et al 2017* employed cryo-electron tomography to visualize intact *H. pylori* cells, with a particular focus on the flagella. Remarkably, the unipolar flagella of *H. pylori* are driven by one of the largest flagellar motors found in bacteria. The flagellar motor provides higher torque needed by the bacterium to navigate the viscous environment of the human stomach. Thin sections of *H. pylori* reveal the typical cell wall detail of a Gram-negative bacterium that consists of outer and inner, or plasma, membranes separated by the periplasm of approximately 30 nm thickness. *H. pylori* has inherent corkscrew motility. The presence of flagella, a smooth cell sheath, a spiral shape, and corkscrew motility allows this microorganism to move in the mucus thickness along the pH gradient and serves as its virulence factor. In addition, the flagella contribute to the aggregation of *H. pylori* to colonize the latter on the epithelial surface of gastric mucosal (*Reshetnyak et al., 2017*).

Fig (3): Morphology of *Helicobacter pylori*. S-shaped *H. pylori* with five to seven sheathed polar flagella. Field emission SEM, bar = 0.5 μm (*Reshetnyak et al.,2017*).

2) Epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* infection

The study of *Helicobacter pylori* genetic variability Based on multilocus sequence typing and more recently on whole genome sequencing, paleomicrobiology still attracts the attention of global researchers in relation to its ancestor roots .A number of studies confirm that *H. pylori* prevalence is falling worldwide especially in the developed world and in children but that the level of infection is higher in certain ethnic minorities and in Migrants. There is little new in identifying the mode of *H. pylori* transmission though intrafamilial spread appears to be important. There have, however, been some interesting papers on the presence of the organism in food, water, and the oral cavity (*Burucoa and Axon., 2017*).

The trend of declining prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is continuing, with major evidence available from studies in Europe. However, in some parts of the world, for example, in some countries in the Middle East, the prevalence has remained relatively stable. A number of systematic reviews and meta analysis have been published during the past year indicating the lowest prevalence rates of the infection in Oceania (24.4%), the highest in Africa (79.1%), and the global annual recurrence rate of *H. pylori* (4.3%). The recurrence rates were found to be directly related to the human development index and prevalence of infection. Several studies have addressed the correlation between *H. pylori* infection and sociodemographic conditions, source of drinking water and dietary factors. A hypothesis on the role of insects and yeasts in transmitting *H. pylori* has been suggested and addressed. *Helicobacter* sp. has been found in flow flies in Brazil. So far there is no evidence available that *H. pylori* may survive and persist on the outer body of the fly (*Sjomina et al., 2018*).

3) Helicobacter pylori transmission:

H. pylori infection prevalence was significantly associated with increasing age, sharing of a bed with siblings during childhood and the mode of sanitation used. Clinicians and the public have to be aware of the important role of H pylori in upper gastrointestinal disease. Use of better sanitation methods, appropriate hygiene, avoidance of over-crowding amongst other measures should be encouraged as a means to reduce the acquisition and transmission of H pylori(*Mungazi, wt al.,2018*).

Transmission of the bacterium can occur thru two different modes: vertical or horizontal. In vertical transmission, H. pylori infection transmits from parents to children, while in horizontal transmission, people are infected with the bacterium via environmental contamination

or social interactions. Oral-oral transmission is possible across individuals by infected saliva containing *pylori*. Oral-oral transmission is supported by evidence obtained from transmission of bacteria by African mothers who chew nutrients before they feed their babies and by gnotobiotic beagle puppies infected by *Helicobacter felis* that transmit bacteria by licking uninfected animals. One of the most common transmission routes of the bacterium is the fecal-oral route. *H. pylori* was successfully cultured by using stool samples of children from different regions of the world such as Gambia, England and United States of America. However, successful culture of bacteria is not always achieved due to rich bacterial flora in stool and this situation aggravates the toxic effects of stool over *H. pylori*. Fecal-oral transmission has been verified indirectly from the results of South American studies. These studies showed consumption of raw vegetables contaminated by human feces are significant risk factors for *H.pylori* infection. The role of flies as a vector of enteric illnesses has also been known for years. *H.pylori* has been isolated in houseflies, suggesting the possible role of houseflies in the fecal-oral transmission of bacteria. Although very rare, human-to-human transmission by an iatrogenic route such as inadequately sterilized endoscopes is possible. Transmission by kissing or sexual relationship has been previously suggested; however, this has failed to be proven by studies. *H. pylori* infection is observed in domestic animals, but the frequency of infection is not increased in the owners of these pets. Hence, *H. pylori* infection is not accepted as a zoonotic infection. Vomiting is a common condition in early childhood. In this situation, the transmission will be via gastric juice. Inhalation of gastric juice results in transmission of *H. pylori* and the bacteria may survive out of the stomach, which is not its typical environment. The gastro-oral route is an important transmission mode particularly in unhygienic environments. Moreover, in

recent studies, *H. pylori* was detected at the tongue dorsum and the periodontal pockets with a nested PCR method. There was a significant relationship between tongue and fingernail positivity. According to these results, some researchers propose that *H. pylori* may be carried by hands and finger-mouth contact could be an important method of *H. pylori* transmission (*Bagirova, et al., 2017*).

4) Helicobacter pylori -zoonopathogen

Helicobacter pylori is the etiological agent of chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, gastric cancer and MALT lymphoma, in humans. The route of transmission of this bacterium has not been clearly proved. One of the theories is transmission via raw uncooked milk from animals to humans. *Turutoglu et al. 2002* have investigated the presence of *H. pylori* in sheep milk. Some helicobacters naturally colonise the intestinal tract of animals, many of which also colonise humans and are often associated with diarrhea. Immunocompromised hosts are particularly susceptible to these microaerobic organisms. Some of these enterohepatic helicobacters (*H. pullorum*, *Helicobacter fennelliae*, *H. canis*, *H. cinaedi*, *H. canadensis* and *H. rappini*) have been isolated from diarrhoeic and bacteraemic humans, and may also have zoonotic potential. The detection of *Helicobacter pylori* in animals and their probable transmission in humans as reported in several studies is indicative of its zoonotic credential; however, long-term cohort studies are necessary to link and prove this underlying connection (*Mladenova and Patel., 2017*).

5) H.pylori colonizes multiples sites within the body

H. pylori primarily colonizes the stomach, but evidence suggests occasional or persistent colonization of other sites (Figure 4). Growth properties of *H. pylori* hamper detection of low-density colonization.

Relatively slow growth and complex growth requirements have been barriers to identifying *H. pylori* colonization. *H. pylori* will not grow in many commonly-used solid or liquid media. *H. pylori* grows best with 1%-5% serum, but higher serum concentrations can be inhibitory. *H. pylori* is also microaerophilic and is killed by atmospheric oxygen. Exposure of samples to ambient oxygen, as well as complement and phagocytic cells from blood will kill some of the bacteria before they can be cultured. Even under ideal conditions, *H. pylori* require about 5 day to form visible colonies on solid media. By that time, any other bacteria or fungi present in the sample can overtake the culture (Testerman and Morris et al., 2014).

Helicobacter pylori have been found in the middle-ear effusions of some adult patients. However, despite its presence in the middle ear, there is limited evidence supporting the role of *H. pylori* in the pathogenesis of Otitis media with effusion (Mills & Hathorn., 2016).

Figure (4): Detection of *Helicobacter pylori*. Evidence of *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) has been found in numerous sites throughout the body. Colored dots indicate the method of detection used. In cases where *H. pylori* has been directly (Testerman and Morris et al., 2014).

6) Pathogenesis of helicobacter pylori:

Helicobacter pylori pathogenesis and disease outcomes are mediated by a complex interplay between bacterial virulence factors, host, and environmental factors. After *H. pylori* enters the host stomach, four steps are critical for bacteria to establish successful colonization, persistent infection, and disease pathogenesis:

- (1) Survival in the acidic stomach.
- (2) Movement toward epithelium cells by flagella-mediated motility.
- (3) Attachment to host cells by adhesins/receptors interaction.
- (4) Causing tissue damage by toxin release.

Over the past 20 years, the understanding of *H. pylori* pathogenesis has been improved by studies focusing on the host and bacterial factors through epidemiology researches and molecular mechanism investigations. These include studies identifying the roles of novel virulence factors and their association with different disease outcomes, especially the bacterial adhesions, *cag* pathogenicity island, and vacuolating cytotoxin. Recently, the development of large-scale screening methods, including proteomic, and transcriptomic tools, has been used to determine the complex gene regulatory networks in *H. pylori*. In addition, a more available complete genomic database of *H. pylori* strains isolated from patients with different gastrointestinal diseases worldwide is helpful to characterize this bacterium (*Kao et al., 2016*).

Three decades have passed since Warren and Marshall described the successful isolation and culture of Helicobacter pylori, the Gram-negative bacterium that colonizes the stomach of half the human population worldwide. Although it is documented that *H. pylori* infection is implicated in a range of disorders of the upper gastrointestinal tract, as well as associated organs, many aspects relating to host colonization,

successful persistence and the pathophysiological mechanisms of this bacteria still remain controversial and are constantly being explored. Unceasing efforts to decipher the pathophysiology of *H. pylori* infection have illuminated the crucially important contribution of multifarious bacterial factors for *H. pylori* pathogenesis, in particular the *cag* pathogenicity island (PAI), the effector protein CagA and the vacuolating cytotoxin VacA. In addition, recent studies have provided insight into the importance of the gastrointestinal microbiota on the cumulative pathophysiology associated with *H. pylori* infections (*Sgouras, et al., 2015*).

6.1. Bacterial virulence factor

Helicobacter pylori may express the virulence factors associated with inflammation as well as inflammatory symptoms in infected patients. The main pathogenicity factors of *Helicobacter pylori* include gamma glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT), cytotoxin-associated gene A (*cagA*) product, and virulence components vacuolating toxin (*vacA*), in addition to pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) such as flagella and lipopolysaccharide (LPS). The cytotoxin associated gene (*cag*) pathogenicity island (PAI) is one of these factors which has been extensively studied in regard to inflammation. Colonization with the strains that possess *cagA* is more frequently associated with peptic ulceration gastric adenocarcinoma or other gastric mucosal complications than the *cagA* strains. It has been shown that *cagA* may play a role in production of IL-8 as well as activation of nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B).

Furthermore, expression of *cagA* induces production of IL-8 and translocation of NF- κ B nuclear in gastric epithelial cells . The *vacA* from *H. pylori* is capable of inducing intracellular vacuolation in gastric

epithelial cells. Hence, it has been hypothesized that it may contribute in damage of gastric and duodenal mucosa which ultimately leads to ulcer formation, *in vivo*. Moreover, the bacterial virulence factors vacA and cagA have important roles in pathogenesis of *H. pylori* infection. Others like blood group antigen-binding adhesion (BabA), outer inflammatory protein (oipA), sialic acid-binding adhesion (sabA), iceA (induced by contact with epithelium), and duodenal ulcer promoting gene (dupA) may promote colonization of the mucosa, too. In regard to virulence factors cagA and vacA, these bacteria are very heterogeneous. A lot of evidences have revealed that these genetic variations may have an important role in the outcome of infection (*Razavi et al.,2015*).

6.2. Cag Pathogenicity Island (PAI)

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a Gram-negative microaerophilic bacterium and a causative agent in various gastroduodenal diseases in humans. The association between *H. pylori* infection and gastric cancer led to its classification as a class I carcinogen. Infection with this bacterium has been found to stimulate of various pro-inflammatory cytokines from gastric cells such as interleukin-1 (IL-1), IL-6 and IL-8, that is play important roles in gastric inflammation . The most important *H. pylori* virulence factor is the cag pathogenicity island (cagPAI) which encodes a type 4 secretory system (T4SS) and immunodominant antigen of CagA. Strains expressing the cagPAI have been associated with a more severe inflammatory response than that induced by cagPAI-negative strains. *H. pylori* have been reported to depend upon both T4SS- and CagA-dependent mechanisms to induce IL-8 production in gastric cells, resulting in increased inflammation. It has also been shown that studies of gastric biopsies from patients infected with *H. pylori* cag-positive strains induce significantly more IL-1 α and IL-1 β than do cag-negative strains.

Therefore, several studies have suggested that the *H. pylori* cagPAI is a putative marker for virulent strains of *H. pylori* that are associated with severe gastroduodenal diseases, especially gastric adenocarcinoma (*Boonyanugomol et al., 2018*).

6.3. Vacuolating cytotoxin VacA

The vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA) is a bacterial virulence factor that promotes more severe disease and gastric colonization. VacA generates a unique reservoir for *H. pylori* within gastric cells conferring bacterial survival advantage. Normally the lysosome and autophagy pathways target and eliminate intracellular pathogens. VacA disrupts the endolysosomal pathway to form large intracellular vacuoles and impairs host-cell autophagy to generate the intracellular niche. However, the mechanism by which VacA alters the endolysosomal pathway is unknown (*Capurro et al., 2018*).

6.4. Conserved *H.pylori* virulence factors:

6.4.1. Urease

One of the main factors responsible for a successful infection is the *H. pylori* urease (HPU), whose ureolytic activity results in the production of ammonia, which in turn leads to the neutralization of the gastric acidic medium, allowing the bacteria survival in the stomach. Accordingly, several pieces of evidence have demonstrated that urease-deficient *H. pylori* are unable to colonize gastric epithelium (*de Jesus et al., 2019*).

Helicobacter pylori urease (HPU) is a key virulence factor that enables bacteria to colonize and survive in the stomach. We early demonstrated that HPU, independent of its catalytic activity, induced inflammatory and angiogenic responses in vivo and directly activated human neutrophils to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS). We have

investigated the effects of HPU on endothelial cells, focusing on the signaling mechanism involved. Urease has a positive role in microbial physiology, representing a key factor for the infectivity or persistence of microorganisms. HPU enzymatic activity is essential for these bacteria to overcome the lethal effect of the gastric acidic pH and to establish a distinct site of persistent infection. *de Jesus et al., 2019* have previously reported that non-catalytic HPU has pro-inflammatory activity in mice and activates host cells, inducing blood platelet aggregation, chemotaxis, and ROS production by human neutrophils. More recently, it was demonstrated that HPU was internalized by epithelial gastric cells, triggering the expression of pro-angiogenic mediators, and induced angiogenesis in vivo in the chicken chorioallantoic membrane model. *de Jesus et al.*, showing that HPU directly activates human microvasculature endothelial cells, modulating the molecular mechanisms that lead to their differentiation toward a pro-inflammatory profile. The severe local inflammation that occurs during *H. pylori* infection is associated with peptic ulcers and gastric cancers, and its outcome is mostly determined by the expression of specific virulence factors. In this context, HPU emerges as an important pro-inflammatory factor, able to induce significant changes in the oxidative profile of endothelial cells, leading to increased paracellular permeability and neutrophils adhesiveness to endothelium, two main features of inflammatory response (*de Jesus et al., 2019*).

6-4-2-Cecropins

Cecropins are antimicrobial peptides in *H. pylori* that may be important to exclude other bacterial species from the gastric niche. They are derived from the ribosomal protein LI. They showed antibacterial activity against gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria. Autolysis of *H. pylori* may allow release of these peptides into the gastric milieu to

prevent colonization by other non *Helicobacter* species (*Abd El-Maksoud, et al .,2016*)

6-4-3-LPS (lipopolysaccharide)

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) is a large and variable complex glycolipid, and is an integral structural component of the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria. Localized in the outer leaflet of the outer membrane, LPS molecules maintain the barrier function of the outer membrane and mediate several interactions between the bacterium and its surrounding environment. To date, the proposed structure of *Helicobacter pylori* LPS (Fig. 5) follows the same basic structure of other Gram-negative LPS molecules. It is composed of three domains: a hydrophobic domain termed lipid A (or endotoxin), which is embedded in the outer membrane; a relatively conserved non-repeating core oligosaccharide; and a variable outermost polysaccharide (or O-antigen). The three LPS domains differ in structure, and therefore confer different biological properties: The lipid A domain interacts with immune receptors and confers the LPS molecule with a range of immunological and potential endotoxic properties; the core oligosaccharide influences permeation properties of the outer membrane; and the O-antigen contributes to the antigenicity and serospecificity of the molecule (*Li et al.,2016*).

Fig (5): Lipopolysaccharide Structure in *Helicobacter pylori* (*Li et al., 2016*).

6-4-4-Adhesins and outer membrane proteins (OMPs)

The outer membrane is the outer barrier of Gram-negative bacteria, which consists of two highly asymmetric layers the inner monolayer contains only phospholipids and the outer monolayer consists mainly of outer membrane proteins (OMPs) that are resistant to the external environment. OMPs have a variety of biological functions, not only in maintaining the outer membrane structure and guaranteeing the material transportation but also in playing an essential role in the process of contact with the host. The study of *H. pylori* OMPs will contribute to the development of vaccine and drug targets. OMPs in *H. pylori* mainly include lipoproteins, porins, iron-regulated proteins, efflux pump proteins, and adhesins . The expression of OMPs in different strains is related to the virulence of *H. pylori*. The pathogenicity of the OMPs may be achieved through the following mechanisms:

- (1) Adhesion.
- (2) Penetration of the bacteria through the defense barrier
- (3) Evasion of the immune system.

Several strains of *H. pylori* have been subjected to whole-genome sequencing, and approximately 4% of their genes were found to encode OMPs. *Xu et al ., 2020* further divided them into five paralogous gene families according to their functions . Hop (outer membrane porins) and Hor (Hop-related proteins) proteins are the best-known family. The second and third are Hof (*H. pylori* OMP) and Hom (*H. pylori* outer membrane) proteins, respectively. Iron-regulated OMPs are the fourth family, and efflux pump OMPs are the fifth family. The other types of OMPs that do not belong to any of these families have different alleles, regional distribution characteristics, and distinct correlations with other virulence factors. Allelic variation and phase variation are the most common methods used to regulate the expression of OMPs. Usually,

there are multiple alleles for each OMP, and the functions of proteins encoded by each allele are somewhat different. Additionally, due to geographical differences among strains, the expression of OMPs is also variable (*Xu et al., 2020*).

6-4-5-Catalase and superoxidase dismutase

Helicobacter pylori has undergone considerable adaptation to allow chronic persistence within the gastric environment. While *H. pylori*-associated diseases are driven by an excessive inflammation, severe gastritis is detrimental to colonization by this pathogen. Hence, *H. pylori* has developed strategies to minimize the severity of gastritis it triggers in its host. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is well known for its role in protecting against oxidative attack; less recognized is its ability to inhibit immunity, shown for SOD from mammalian sources and those of some bacterial species. Stent et al., examined whether *H. pylori* SOD (HpSOD) has the ability to inhibit the host immune response to these bacteria (*Stent et al., 2018*).

6-4-6-Heat Shock Proteins

When bacterial cells experience a sudden temperature increase, they promptly induce the expression of a group of genes known as heat-shock genes. They encode a class of proteins, referred to as heat-shock proteins (HSP), which are highly conserved throughout all kingdoms of life. This mechanism of cellular protection, crucial for survival and adaptation to adverse environmental growth conditions, is known as heat-shock response. In addition to temperature up shift, heat-shock proteins typically accumulate following different kinds of stress insults and are involved in several cellular processes, including promoting the correct folding of newly-synthesized polypeptides, preventing aggregation of

cellular proteins under stress conditions, and recovering proteins that have been partially or completely unfolded by stresses (*Roncarati and Scarlato.,2018*).

7-factor affecting colonization efficiency

7-1-motility

Helicobacter pylori is a highly motile bacterial pathogen that colonizes approximately 50% of the world's population. *H. pylori* can move readily within the viscous mucosal layer of the stomach. It has become increasingly clear that its unique flagella-driven motility is essential for successful gastric colonization and pathogenesis. *H. pylori* possess multiple unipolar flagella, which are driven by one of the largest flagellar motors found in bacteria. These large motors presumably provide the higher torque needed by the bacterial pathogens to navigate in the viscous environment of the human stomach (*Qin et al., 2017*).

Flagellar motility of *Helicobacter pylori* has been shown to be important for the bacteria to establish initial colonization. The ferric uptake regulator (Fur) is a global regulator that has been identified in *H. pylori* which is involved in the processes of iron uptake and establishing colonization. However, the role of Fur in *H. pylori* motility is still unclear (*Lee et al., 2017*).

7-2- Chemotaxis

Bacterial chemotaxis is an essential element for successful colonization and establishment of infection, particularly for *H. pylori* populations that penetrate and grow as cell-associated micro colonies deep within the gastric glands. Chemotaxis allows a bacterium to control its swimming behavior in response to extracellular chemical signals. In a recent study, *Sigal et al.* utilized advanced quantitative confocal microscopy to analyze gastric stem cell responses in infected humans and

mice. The demonstrated that mutant bacteria with defects in chemotaxis that were able to colonize the stomach surface did not succeed in colonizing the antral glands in mice and also failed to activate stem cells (*Sigal et al.,2015*).

Bacterial membrane or in the cytoplasm are molecules that act as chemoreceptors of extracellular chemical signals and following interaction with their respective ligands, initiate a molecular signal transduction cascade, which causes a change in the direction of rotation of the flagellar motors (*Liu.,2015*).

7-3-Adherence

When *H. pylori* colonizes on the mucosal layer lining the gastric epithelium, the interaction of bacterial adhesins with cellular receptors protects the bacteria from displacement from the stomach by forces such as those generated by peristalsis and gastric emptying, and then bacteria get metabolic substrates and nutrients to improve growth through releasing toxins to damage the host cells. Although blood-antigen binding protein A (BabA) and sialic acid-binding adhesin (SabA) are the well-characterized adhesins studied so far, not all *H. pylori* strains express these adhesins. There are several other known adhesins in *H. pylori* for adapting to different hosts/tissues, including neutrophil-activating protein (NAP), heat shock protein 60 (Hsp60), adherence-associated proteins (AlpA and AlpB), *H. pylori* outer membrane protein (HopZ), and lacdiNAc-binding adhesin (LabA) (*Kao,et al.,2016*).

8-Metabolism in Helicobacter pylori's Helical Shape

Helical cell shape is important for Helicobacter pylori's ability to colonize the human stomach. Cell shape in this Gram-negative pathogen is determined by the cell wall, which is composed of peptidoglycan (PG),

a polymer of disaccharides with an attached pentapeptide stem that can join glycan strands by cross linking with an adjacent peptide stem. Maintaining helical shape requires the activity of two endopeptidases, two carboxypeptidases, and several non-enzymatic proteins (*Taylor, et al., 2018*).

9- Biochemical characteristics of *H. pylori*

H. pylori infection is usually life long as it has the capacity to adjust to natural habitat like mucus layer over the gastric epithelial cell. *H. pylori* lack several pathways which are commonly present in less specialized bacteria like enteric bacteria. The organism can be cultured only in specific chemically defined medium containing amino acids arginine, histidine, iso leucine, methionine, phenylalanine and valine . *H. pylori* are urease, catalase, oxidase positive and is microaerophilic utilizing O₂ as terminal electron acceptor. Ammonia plays very important role in both nitrogen metabolism and acid resistance. Ammonia production is mainly through high urease activity, which acts as key component in nitrogen metabolism, acid resistance and virulence factor (*Ashwini et al.,2015*).

10-Classic *H.pylori*-Associated Disease

10-1-Dyspepsia

Functional dyspepsia (FD) is characterized by bothersome epigastric pain or burning, postprandial fullness, or early satiation without evidence of structural disease. Functional dyspepsia is a very common disease with a prevalence of about 10% of general population and the socioeconomic burden of disease is substantial due to the frequent visits to healthcare facilities and repeated medications and investigations. The pathogenesis of FD includes diverse mechanisms such as diet factor,

psychological distress, a disturbance of gastric physiology, duodenal inflammation, and infectious causes represented by *Helicobacter pylori*. This infection was estimated to be about 2.3 fold in patients with dyspepsia compared with normal controls and *H. pylori* was found in about half of the patients with dyspepsia. Therefore, there have been many studies on whether *H. pylori* eradication therapy is effective in relieving the symptoms of dyspepsia. However, the effect of eradication therapy in FD patients was inconsistent in previously published randomized controlled trials (RCTs) (*Kang et al., 2019*).

10-2-Gastritis

Chronic stimulation of gastric epithelium by *H pylori* antigenic determinants as well as toxin and other secretions in association with the recruitment of the immune system cells to the gastric mucosa, all together, provide a highly activated microenvironment in favor of the initiation of premalignant lesions. Understanding the immunological response to *H pylori*-induced gastritis, and consequently carcinogenesis, provides a clear path toward new strategies against this abundant infection. *H pylori* is able to escape the host's immune response and induce persistent inflammation by triggering an imbalance in T helper 1 (Th1)/Th2 cells in gastric mucosal. T-cell immunity is known to play an important role during inflammatory response and may even affect the prognosis of the disease. T helper cells differentiate into a variety of Th subsets, including Th1, Th2, Th17, Th9, Th22, and Tfh, after exposure to antigen, or different signals induced by cytokines or even the type of antigen-presenting cells (*Shamsdin et al., 2020*).

Fig (6): Typical *Helicobacter pylori*-associated pathology. Gastritis may be antral-predominant, corpus-predominant, or diffuse. The risk of developing adenocarcinoma or MALT lymphoma varies depending on the type of pathology present (*Testerman and Morris2014*)

10-3-Gastric cancer

Helicobacter pylori infection is also a critical risk factor for gastric cancer, contributing to approximately 75% of all gastric cancer cases, as well as to low-grade mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, a subcategory of primary gastric lymphoma, which accounts for approximately 30–40% of extranodal lymphomas in total. Gastric cancer has remained a significant commonly diagnosed form of gastrointestinal malignancy. Although morbidity and mortality from gastric cancer have decreased in the past few decades, gastric cancer remains the third leading cause of cancer for both men and women worldwide, constituting a global health problem. Thus, considerable efforts are focused on *H. pylori* eradication in vulnerable patients, with the goal of eliminating gastric symptoms and preventing the development of gastric cancer. This strategy has shown signs of success: for instance, the decrease in *H. pylori* infections in Japan is believed to have contributed to a decline in gastric cancer cases. However, the cause of an increase in gastric cancer in young population in the USA (notably,

young Hispanic men), where overall the incidence of H. pylori infection is also waning, is unexplained. Thus, unknown factors likely unrelated to H. pylori infection may be contributing to a rise in gastric cancer in specific populations, further complicating the perplexing etiology of the disease (*Mentis, et al., 2019*).

11-Treatment

11-1- The first-line treatment

The first line, Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved drug regimens for the treatment of H. pylori are listed in table 2.

(Table 1): FDA approved first line oral therapy for H. pylori treatment

Therapy	Duration (days)	Eradication Rates	Comments
PPI twice a day, clarithromycin 500 mg twice a day, amoxicillin 1g twice a day	10-14	70-85%	Not allergic to penicillin and have not received a macrolide
PPI twice a day, clarithromycin 500 mg twice a day, metronidazole 500 mg twice a day	10-14	70-85%	Allergic to penicillin and have not received a macrolide.
Bismuth subsalicylate 525 mg four times a day, metronidazole 250 mg four times a day, tetracycline 500 mg four times a day, PPI twice a day for 2 weeks, or H2RA for 4 weeks	10-14	75-90%	Those allergic to penicillin or failed triple therapy or prevalence of macrolide-resistance is > 20%.

PPI: Proton Pump Inhibitor, Lansoprazole 30 mg twice a day, Omeprazole 20 mg twice a day, H2RA: Histamine 2 receptor antagonist (*Thaker et al.,2016*).

These therapies include proton pump inhibitor (PPI) and two antibiotics or bismuth subsalicylate, acid suppressor, and two antibiotics. However, eradication rates using these regimens are a disappointing 75% in the United States due to increased H. pylori resistance to standard

antibiotics .Clarithromycin and metronidazole show the highest rates of resistance and the factors associated with resistance include geographic region, sex, ethnicity, age, and active versus inactive ulcer disease. As a result of the declining eradication rates, other more promising therapies have been proposed. In a recent metaanalysis comprised mostly of trials from Italy, five days of a PPI with amoxicillin followed by five days of a PPI with clarithromycin and tinidazole had an eradication rate of 93.4%. This regimen has not yet been validated in the United States and it is not clear if it is superior to quadruple therapy. Sequential therapy (e.g. five days of PPI + amoxicillin followed by 5 days of PPI + clarithromycin and metronidazole) may increase medication adherence compared to quadruple therapy since it requires fewer medications. Another promising therapy that requires validation in the United States is PPI with levofloxacin and amoxicillin, with a reported 87% eradication rate in a recent meta-analysis (*Thaker et al.,2016*).

11-2-Second-line treatment

After the failure of an empirical first line treatment, physicians should use a levofloxacin triple therapy (PPI + levofloxacin + amoxicillin) or a bismuth quadruple therapy. In particular, levofloxacin triple therapy should be the treatment of choice after the failure of bismuth quadruple therapy. Two recent meta analyses showed that these two regimens have similar performances as secondline treatment for H. pylori infection. A meta analysis of 25 randomized control trials (RCTs) assessed the outcome of levofloxacin triple therapy in second line reporting a pooled eradication rate of 74.5%. Similarly, a pooled analysis of 38 RCTs, assessing the efficacy of bismuth quadruple therapy as second line treatment, reported an eradication rate of 78% (*Zagari et al.,2018*).

11-3-Third-line treatment

Antibiotic resistance is growing worldwide, and patients who have failed consecutive 1st- and 2nd-line H. pylori eradication regimens are increasing. Therefore, the role of the bacterial culture with antibiotic susceptibility testing and molecular susceptibility testing is important for avoiding the use of ineffective antibiotics. However, antibiotic susceptibility testing-guided treatment does not necessarily guarantee successful eradication, and there have been mixed results for the effectiveness of a 3rd-line rescue therapy. Therefore, providing patients with pretreatment medication instructions and education is important. It is also crucial to determine the reason of the eradication failure, including host-related factors (poor compliance to eradication regimen, smoking, and cytochrome P450 2C19 genetic polymorphism) or treatment-related factors (inadequate dosage or duration of therapy and gastric acidity), as such factors can be modified for a tailored therapy. Although the indications for H.pylori eradication have widened, patients at a high risk of gastric cancer can gain definitive benefits with a 3rd-line or even 4th-line therapy (*Choi et al.,2018*).

After the failure of second line treatment, the third line regimen should be based on culture with susceptibility testing or molecular determination of genotype resistance. However, susceptibility testing is not widely available. International guidelines finally recognized that this is a real issue in clinical practice and provided recommendations for an empirical third line treatment. It is recommended to use in third line the eradication regimen that was not used in first and second line among clarithromycin containing therapies, levofloxacin triple therapy and bismuth quadruple therapy. A bismuth based levofloxacin quadruple therapy and a rifabutin containing triple therapy (PPI + rifabutin + amoxicillin) may be a valid alternative for third or fourth line treatments(*Zagari et al.,2018*).

11-4- Probiotics

Treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infection is important for the management of gastrointestinal disorders such as peptic ulcer and gastric cancer. Due to the increase in the prevalence of *H. pylori* resistance to antibiotics, triple therapy with clarithromycin is no longer the best treatment for *H. pylori*, especially in some areas where the local resistance to this antibiotic is higher than 20%. Alternative treatments have been proposed for the eradication of *H. pylori*. Some of them including novel antibiotics or classical ones in different combinations; these treatments are being used in the regular clinical practice as novel and more effective treatments. Others therapies are using probiotics associated to antibiotics to treat this infection (*Goderska et al., 2018*).

11-5-Selective killing of *Helicobacter pylori* with pH-responsive HCT-AMPs

Current clinical treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, the main etiological factor in the development of gastritis, gastric ulcers, and gastric carcinoma, requires a combination of at least two antibiotics and one proton pump inhibitor. However, such triple therapy suffers from progressively decreased therapeutic efficacy due to the drug resistance and undesired killing of the commensal bacteria due to poor selectivity. Here, we report the development of antimicrobial polypeptide-based monotherapy, which can specifically kill *H. pylori* under acidic pH in the stomach while inducing minimal toxicity to commensal bacteria under physiological pH. Specifically, we designed a class of pH-sensitive, helix-coil conformation transitionable antimicrobial polypeptides (HCT-AMPs) $(\text{PGA})_m\text{-}r\text{-(PHLG-MHH)}_n$, bearing randomly distributed

negatively charged glutamic acid and positively charged poly(γ -6-N-(methylhexylammonium)hexyl-L-glutamate) (PHLG-MHH) residues. The HCT-AMPs showed unappreciable toxicity at physiological pH when they adopted random coiled conformation. Under acidic condition in the stomach, they transformed to the helical structure and exhibited potent antibacterial activity against *H. pylori*, including clinically isolated drug-resistant strains. After oral gavage, the HCT-AMPs afforded comparable *H. pylori* killing efficacy to the triple-therapy approach while inducing minimal toxicity against normal tissues and commensal bacteria, in comparison with the remarkable killing of commensal bacteria by 65% and 86% in the ileal contents and feces, respectively, following triple therapy. This strategy renders an effective approach to specifically target and kill *H. pylori* in the stomach while not harming the commensal bacteria/normal tissues (*Xiong et al.,2017*).

12-Vaccine

Vaccines have been developed against a large number of infectious and non-infectious diseases. Early attempts focused on the recombinant urease showed some promising outcomes in animals, nevertheless, some subsequent clinical trials were hampered by a number of certain side effects of mucosal adjuvants. More recently, an intramuscularly administered trivalent vaccine (recombinant CagA, VacA, and neutrophil-activating protein) was developed, while unfortunately the antigens were recognized by the host's cellular and humoral immune systems, causing no immunity in a challenged model . *Chen et al 2012* synthesized an *H. pylori* oipA DNA construct, as a therapeutic vaccine, that was delivered by attenuated *Salmonella typhimurium* in the C57BL/6 mouse model with *H. pylori* strain SS1 infection . To increase the expression level, the oipA gene was codon-optimized for the

mammalian cell systems, resulting in a 2-log reduction of *H. pylori* colonization with sterilizing immunity achieved in three out of 10 mice. The LPS of *H. pylori* is relatively nontoxic but may promote autoimmune responses. Considering the potential of polysaccharide-based conjugate vaccines, *Altman et al 2012* chemically modulated the LPS of *H. pylori* by delipidation and conjugation processes to enhance the immunogenicity (*Kakelar et al.,2018*).

13-Diagnostic test of helicobacter pylori

13-1-Urea breath test

Here are two UBTs available and gained Food and Drug Administration approval: ^{13}C and ^{14}C tests. Both tests are affordable and can provide real-time results. Some physicians may prefer the ^{13}C test as it is non-radioactive compared to ^{14}C which uses a radioactive isotope, especially in young children and pregnant women, though dose of radianis very minimal (about 1 microCi) the dose of radiation is the dose of ^{14}C -UBT with the mini dose equals to 1 microCi (37 kbq) which has a high diagnostic accuracy. UBT is indicated to confirm *H. pylori* colonization and to monitor its eradication. Positive UBT indicates an active *H. pylori* infection which require treatment or further confirmation with invasive procedures (*Ferwana et al.,2015*).

13-2-Stool antigen test (SAT)

Stool antigen test (SAT) is a non-invasive test used to detect *H. pylori* antigen in the stool sample of the patient. The SAT is used as an enzyme immunoassay (EIA) or immunochromatographic assay (ICA). In SAT tests, monoclonal or polyclonal antibodies are used. In the study of *Gisbert et al 2004* monoclonal antibodybased tests showed sensitivity and

specificity of 94% and 97%, respectively . Monoclonal antibodybased tests are more accurate than polyclonal antibody tests (*Tonkic et al., 2018*)

13-3-Antibody-Based Tests

Numerous serological tests based on the detection of anti-*H. pylori* IgG antibody are widely available for *H. pylori* diagnosis and EIA test is the most common and accurate technique among them. Serological tests have also frequently been used in screening for epidemiological studies because of their inexpensive, rapid and acceptability to patients. Moreover, Several immunogenic proteins, like CagA, VacA, UreA, Omp and GroEL, have been used as candidates to detect infection. The *H. pylori*FliD protein, an essential element in the assembly of the functional flagella, is also recognized as a novel marker for serological diagnosis of *H. pylori*infection, with sensitivity and specificity of 99% and 97% respectively. A novel line immunoassay, recomLine *H. pylori* IgG, which using six highly immunogenic virulence factors (CagA, VacA, GroEL, gGT, HcpC, and UreA) was introduced recently for serological diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection. The recomLine, in contrast to EIA and immunoblot, allows the identification of specific antibody response against distinct *H. pylori* antigens and increased discriminatory power. As compared to histology, the recomLine showed sensitivity and specificity of 97.6% and 96.2% respectively. The recomLine is also a useful tool to identify specific virulence factors of *H. pylori* (*wang et al.,2015*)

13-4-Molecular methods

Molecular methods, most often amplification of nucleic acid by conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or real-time PCR are being increasingly more used to detect *H. pylori* DNA in biopsy samples

or other types of specimens, like saliva or feces. So, PCR can be categorized as invasive or non-invasive method regarding the type of specimen tested (*Tonkic, et al.,2018*)

14-Survival of helicobacter pylori

14-1-in acidic medium

Helicobacter pylori is uniquely adapted to colonize the gastric mucosa. The key components for gastric colonization include motility, adhesion, and acid acclimation. The flagellar system allows the bacteria to move within the gastric mucus layer to the sites where conditions are optimal for survival. Adhesion to the gastric mucosa, via interaction between bacterial and host proteins, allows the bacteria to withstand bulk flow of gastric fluid. Acid acclimation is the system that allows for periplasmic and cytoplasmic pH regulation in the setting of an acidic environment. The bacteria are bioenergetically neutralophiles, meaning they are able to survive between pH 4 and 8 and grow between pH 6 and 8. The pH at the gastric surface in the presence of *H. pylori*, as shown by microelectrode, fluorescent dye, and in vivo transcriptome studies, is below the range for growth and near to below the limits for survival. The bacteria are able to sense acidic medium pH and stimulate trafficking of cytoplasmic urease and its accessory proteins to the proton-gated urea channel, UreI, in the inner membrane. The breakdown of urea into carbon dioxide and ammonia buffers the periplasm and cytoplasm to within the pH range optimal for a neutralophile. Understanding gastric colonization is clinically relevant because these systems that facilitate colonization can be targeted or interfered with to improve efficacy of eradication regimens (*Marcus et al., 2016*).

14-1-1-Acid-responsive activity of the *Helicobacter pylori* metalloregulator NikR

Helicobacter pylori is a human pathogen that infects the stomach, where it experiences variable pH. To survive the acidic gastric conditions, *H. pylori* produces large quantities of urease, a nickel enzyme that hydrolyzes urea to ammonia, which neutralizes the local environment. One of the regulators of urease expression in *H. pylori* is HpNikR, a nickel-responsive transcription factor. Here we show that HpNikR also regulates urease expression in response to changes in pH, linking acid adaptation and nickel homeostasis. Upon measuring the cytosolic pH of *H. pylori* exposed to an external pH of 2, similar to the acidic shock conditions that occur in the human stomach, a significant drop in internal pH was observed. This decrease in internal pH resulted in HpNikR-dependent activation of *ureA* transcription. Furthermore, analysis of a slate of *H. pylori* genes encoding other acid adaptation or nickel homeostasis components revealed HpNikR-dependent regulation in response to acid shock. This regulation was consistent with pH-dependent DNA binding to the corresponding promoter sequences observed in vitro with purified HpNikR. These results demonstrate that HpNikR can directly respond to changes in cytosolic pH during acid acclimation and illustrate the exquisitely coordinated regulatory networks that support *H. pylori* infections in the harsh environment of the human stomach (Jones et al., 2018).

14-2 Survival of *Helicobacter pylori* through inhibition of autophagy pathway

Autophagy is present in mammalian cells at a low basal level. As an evolutionarily conserved cellular activity, it delivers organelles and cellular materials to the lysosome for degradation within double-

membraned vacuoles, called autophagosomes. Autophagy is considered one of the innate immune effectors against intracellular bacterial infection (e.g., *Streptococcus pyogenes*). Autophagic proteins act as cytosolic sensors to rapidly launch the autophagic pathway when the innate defense system recognizes invasive bacterial pathogens. However, some intracellular pathogens use highly evolved machinery to deceive autophagic recognition, manipulate the autophagic pathway, and reconstruct the autophagosomal compartment for their own survival. Over the last decade, many studies have reported that *H. pylori* infection can induce macroautophagy and that *H. pylori* may evade the autophagic machinery through downregulating the expression of autophagic proteins (*Yang et al., 2016*).

The Immunity

Immunity is one of physiological functions in humans, which can be divided into innate and adaptive immunity. The human body relies on immunity to recognize ‘self’ and ‘non-self’ components, then the immunity protects human against invasion of pathogens. Two major processes of the innate immunity are usage of a large set of different pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) and a system for random and nonselective generation of antigen specific receptors. The adaptive immunity has been viewed as a complement to the innate immunity and a definitive solution to pathogen recognition. However, there are some differences between the innate and adaptive immunity (*Huang, et al.,2016*).

1-Innate immunity

Innate Immunity The innate immune response provides a barrier function, to prevent organisms from invading the body as well as effector mechanisms designed to eliminate microbes that breach the epithelial barriers through recognition, ingestion and killing by phagocytes. Innate immunity also alerts the adaptive immune response to microbial invasion, stimulates adaptive effector cells and influences the nature of the adaptive immune response generated, based on the nature of the pathogen (*Wilson and Schooley.,2017*).

1-1-Barrier Function Of The Innate Immune Response Epithelial.

Barriers form the first line of defense against the microbial world surrounding all multicellular organisms. The skin and mucosal surfaces lining the gastrointestinal, respiratory and genitourinary tracts provide both a physical barrier to invasion and also play a critical role in serving

as the first geographic location at which interactions between pathogens and host occur. Additional physical protection is provided on mucosal surfaces by the secretion of mucus and immunoglobulins in which bacteria and other pathogens are aggregated for clearance by cilia, coughing and/or peristalsis (*Wilson and Schooley et al.,2017*)

1-2- frontline cells of innate immunity

Macrophages and dendritic cells (DCs) are the frontline cells of innate immunity. They sense and immediately respond to invading pathogens, thus providing an early defense against external attack. Pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) on the surfaces of these cells recognize pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) present in the invaders and, as a result, activate intracellular signaling cascades, leading to the induction of a general pro-inflammatory response. This includes the release of antimicrobial mediators, which target the invading pathogen, chemokines, which recruit more immune cells to the site of infection, and pro-inflammatory cytokines, which drive further inflammation, and induce the adaptive immune response, which is mediated by T and B lymphocytes and is more specific for the particular invading pathogen (*Kelly and O'neill .,2015*).

2-Adaptive immunity

Unlike innate immunity, adaptive immunity holds the capability to create a “memory”in which it studies and learns the antigen presented and remember it for future references. As a result, when a host is presented with the same type of antigen for a second time, it allows the immune system to respond to the antigen and destroy the pathogen much faster (Estepa .,2019)

In contrast to the innate immunity, adaptive immunity possesses specificities and immune memory abilities. Adaptive immunity and innate immune supplement each other and mutually resist invasion of pathogenic microorganisms. The original T cells amplify and are differentiated into different subsets such as Th1, Th2, Th17 and Treg cells after stimulation of antigens. Th1 cells eliminate pathogens inside cells; Th2 cells protect human body from harmful parasites and adjust allergic reactions; Th17 cells remove extracellular bacteria and fungi; Treg cells promote tissue repairs. However, disorders of T cell responses and imbalance of T cell subsets induce excessive releases of cytokines and chemokines, which lead to inflammation (Huang, et al.,2016)

Adaptive immunity is defined by the presence of lymphocytes, either T or B cells, and includes both CD8⁺ cytotoxic T cells that are the effector cells that directly destroy tumor cells, CD4⁺ helper T cells that regulate CD8⁺ T-cell and B-cell function, and B cells that present antigen and produce antibodies (*Stanton et al.,2018*)

3-Innate Immune Response (Inflammation)

Inflammation results from activation of the immune system in response to a broad range of different stimuli. The immune system is a highly complex and evolutionary optimized defense system with cellular and humoral components. The course of an inflammatory response is influenced by the immune condition of the host, the virulence e. g. of an infectious agent, and the fine tuning of the local tissue reaction, which may be influenced by individual genetic factors. Immunity is a compromise between insufficient (immunodeficiency) or exaggerated (autoimmunity) immune reactions (*Sahlmann and Ströbel,2016*)

At the tissue level, inflammation is characterized by redness, swelling, heat, pain, and loss of tissue function, which result from local immune,

vascular and inflammatory cell responses to infection or injury. Important microcirculatory events that occur during the inflammatory process include vascular permeability changes, leukocyte recruitment and accumulation, and inflammatory mediator release. Various pathogenic factors, such as infection, tissue injury, or cardiac infarction, can induce inflammation by causing tissue damage. The etiologies of inflammation can be infectious or non-infectious (Table 1). In response to tissue injury, the body initiates a chemical signaling cascade that stimulates responses aimed at healing affected tissues. These signals activate leukocyte chemotaxis from the general circulation to sites of damage. These activated leukocytes produce cytokines that induce inflammatory responses (*Chen et al., 2018*).

Etiology of inflammation

Non-infectious factors	Infectious factors
Physical: burn, frostbite, physical injury, foreign bodies, trauma, ionizing radiation Chemical: glucose, fatty acids, toxins, alcohol, chemical irritants (including fluoride, nickel and other trace elements) Biological: damaged cells Psychological: excitement	Bacteria viruses other microorganisms

Table (2): Etiology of inflammation (*Chen et al., 2018*).

4- H.Pylori Causes of inflammation

Chronic inflammation induced by *Helicobacter pylori* infection is a critical factor in the development of peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer. Central to this inflammation is the initiation of pro-inflammatory signaling cascades within epithelial cells, in particular those mediated by two sensors of bacterial cell wall components, nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing protein 1 (NOD1) and alpha-protein kinase 1 (ALPK1). *H pylori* is, however, also highly adept at mitigating inflammation in the host, thereby restricting tissue damage and favoring

bacterial persistence. *H pylori* modulates host immune responses by altering cytokine signaling in epithelial and myeloid cells, which results in increased proliferation of regulatory T cells and downregulation of effector T-cell responses (*Robinson and Lehours., 2020*).

5-Types of inflammation

5-1-Acute Inflammation

Tissue damage due to trauma, microbial invasion, or noxious compounds can induce acute inflammation. It starts rapidly, becomes severe in a short time and symptoms may last for a few days for example cellulitis or acute pneumonia. Subacute inflammation is the period between acute and chronic inflammation and may last 2 to 6 weeks (*Pahwa et al., 2019*).

5-2-Chronic Inflammation

Chronic inflammation is also referred to as slow, long-term inflammation lasting for prolonged periods of several months to years. Generally, the extent and effects of chronic inflammation vary with the cause of the injury and the ability of the body to repair and overcome the damage. (*Pahwa et al., 2019*)

6- H.Pylori Inflammatory injury

The bacterial pathogen *Helicobacter pylori* commonly colonizes the human gastric mucosa during early childhood and persists throughout life. The organism has evolved multiple mechanisms for evading clearance by the immune system and, despite inducing inflammation in the stomach, the majority of infections are asymptomatic. *H. pylori* is the leading cause of peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer. However, disease outcomes are related to the pattern and severity of chronic inflammation in the gastric mucosa, which in turn is influenced by both bacterial and host factor (*White et al., 2015*).

Fig (7): The effect of gastritis pattern on gastric acid production and associations with duodenal and gastric disease (White et al., 2015).

7- Inflammatory response

The inflammatory response is the coordinate activation of signaling pathways that regulate inflammatory mediator levels in resident tissue cells and inflammatory cells recruited from the blood. Inflammation is a common pathogenesis of many chronic diseases, including cardiovascular and bowel diseases, diabetes, arthritis, and cancer. Although inflammatory response processes depend on the precise nature of the initial stimulus and its location in the body, they all share a common mechanism, which can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Cell surface pattern receptors recognize detrimental stimuli.
- 2) Inflammatory pathways are activated.
- 3) Inflammatory markers are released.
- 4) Inflammatory cells are recruited (*Chen et al., 2018*).

A successful inflammatory response tends to resolve in a coordinated series of molecular and cellular events, including the resolving phase of inflammation. Exciting new discoveries have revealed

a post-resolution phase of inflammation, composed of a third wave of leukocyte influx that seemingly links innate and adaptive immune systems. Recent discoveries have suggested that failed or impaired resolution of inflammation may underpin the pathogenesis of certain chronic inflammatory diseases, such as inflammatory bowel disease and rheumatoid arthritis. The identification of failed resolution as an underlying cause or contributing factor to certain human inflammatory diseases has brought new exciting therapeutic opportunities for treating inflammation, based on promoting events associated with resolution, rather than simply blocking proinflammatory pathways. Recently, the potential of human translation is reflected by the identification/quantification of proresolving molecules and pathways in humans, and by the pioneering use of human models of inflammation to test the efficacy of proresolving agonists. In order to effectively translate the knowledge of resolution biology into potential new therapeutics for a variety of inflammation-associated diseases, precise definitions of the cellular players, molecular mediators, receptors, and signaling pathways engaged during inflammation resolution are necessary (*Sugimoto et al., 2019*).

8-Inflammatory markers

Markers are used in clinical applications to indicate normal versus pathogenic biological processes, and assess responses to therapeutic interventions. Inflammatory markers may be predictive of inflammatory diseases, and correlate with the causes and consequences of various inflammatory diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, endothelial dysfunctions, and infection. Stimuli activate inflammatory cells, such as macrophages and adipocytes, and induce production of inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , and inflammatory proteins and

enzymes. These molecules can potentially serve as biomarkers for diseases diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutic decision making (*Chen et al., 2018*)

9-Inflammatory cytokines

Cytokines (Table 2) are predominantly released from immune cells, including monocytes, macrophages, and lymphocytes. Pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines facilitate and inhibit inflammation, respectively. Inflammatory cytokines are classified as ILs, colony stimulating factors (CSF), IFNs, TNFs, TGFs, and chemokines, and are produced by cells primarily to recruit leukocytes to the site of infection or injury . Cytokines modulate the immune response to infection or inflammation and regulate inflammation itself via a complex network of interactions. However, excessive inflammatory cytokine production can lead to tissue damage, hemodynamic changes, organ failure, and ultimately death. A better understanding of how to regulate cytokine pathways would allow for more accurate identification of agent-mediated inflammation and the treatment of inflammatory diseases (*Chen et al., 2018*).

Summary of cytokines and their functions

Cytokine	Family	Main sources	Function
IL-1 β	IL-1	Macrophages, monocytes	Pro-inflammation, proliferation, apoptosis, differentiation
IL-4	IL-4	Th-cells	Anti-inflammation, T-cell and B-cell proliferation, B-cell differentiation
IL-6	IL-6	Macrophages, T-cells, adipocyte	Pro-inflammation, differentiation, cytokine production
IL-8	CXC	Macrophages, epithelial cells, endothelial cells	Pro-inflammation, chemotaxis, angiogenesis
IL-10	IL-10	Monocytes, T-cells, B-cells	Anti-inflammation, inhibition of the pro-inflammatory cytokines
IL-12	IL-12	Dendritic cells, macrophages, neutrophils	Pro-inflammation, cell differentiation, activates NK cell
IL-11	IL-6	Fibroblasts, neurons, epithelial cells	Anti-inflammation, differentiation, induces acute phase protein
TNF- α	TNF	Macrophages, NK cells, CD4 ⁺ lymphocytes, adipocyte	Pro-inflammation, cytokine production, cell proliferation, apoptosis, anti-infection
IFN- γ	INF	T-cells, NK cells, NKT cells	Pro-inflammation, innate, adaptive immunity anti-viral
GM-CSF	IL-4	T-cells, macrophages, fibroblasts	Pro-inflammation, macrophage activation, increase neutrophil and monocyte function
TGF- β	TGF	Macrophages, T cells	Anti-inflammation, inhibition of pro-inflammatory cytokine production

Table (4): Cytokines and their functions (*Chen et al., 2018*).

10-The Inflammatory Pathway

The inflammatory process has been best studied in response to infectious stimuli, particularly bacterial infections. It is not clear whether most of the principles studied in infection-induced inflammation apply to other causes. However, a generic inflammatory pathway has been proposed. This pathway consists of inducers, sensors, mediators, and effectors. The inducers can be either infectious organisms or non infectious stimuli, such as toxins, foreign bodies, signals from necrotic cells, and damaged tissues. Sensors are specialized molecules that are activated by the inducers, which trigger the production of mediators. The mediators are endogenous chemicals that can induce the feeling of pain, can either promote or inhibit inflammation and tissue repair, and can activate the effectors—tissues and cells. The conjugation of these multiple players gives rise to many alternative routes in the inflammatory

pathway and which path is taken depends on the inciting stimuli. For a sterile stimulus, one of the goals is to prevent infection on the injured tissue. However, this cannot always be done successfully. Inducers can be classified as pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), which are molecular patterns from infectious organisms, and as damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), molecules released from damaged cells of the host. Each of these patterns is recognized by different receptors in macrophages and dendritic cells; pain receptors also sense tissue damage. Inflammatory cytokines are released after stimulation of those receptors. They include TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6, among others, which induce changes on the endothelium, allowing the passage of immune cells through the junctions between endothelial cells (*Varela et al., 2018*).

Figure (8): Inflammatory Pathway Components (*Abdulsalam., 2016*).

The inflammatory pathway consists of inducers, sensors, mediators, and target tissues. Inducers initiate the inflammatory response and are detected by sensors. Sensors, such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs), are expressed on specialized sentinel cells, such as tissue-resident macrophages, dendritic cells, and mast cells. They induce the production of mediators, including cytokines, chemokines, bioactive amines, eicosanoids, and products of proteolytic cascades, such as bradykinin. These inflammatory mediators act on various target tissues to elicit changes in their functional states that optimize adaptation to the noxious

condition (e.g., infection or tissue injury) associated with the particular inducers that elicited the inflammatory response. The specific components shown represent only a small sample of the myriad different sensors, mediators, and target tissues involved in the inflammatory response (*Abdulsalam.,2016*).

11-1- Activation of inflammatory pathways

Inflammatory pathways impact the pathogenesis of a number of chronic diseases, and involve common inflammatory mediators and regulatory pathways. Inflammatory stimuli activate intracellular signaling pathways that then activate production of inflammatory mediators. Primary inflammatory stimuli, including microbial products and cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), mediate inflammation through interaction with the TLRs, IL-1 receptor (IL-1R), IL-6 receptor (IL-6R), and the TNF receptor (TNFR). Receptor activation triggers important intracellular signaling pathways, including the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B), and Janus kinase (JAK)-signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) pathways (*Chen et al.,2018*).

12-Defence cells in the tissue

312-1-Mast cells

Mast cells, while best known for their role in allergic inflammation, have diverse physiologic roles including innate defense against infection, modulation of adaptive immunity, angiogenesis, and tissue homeostasis. Mast cells and neurons are closely aligned, anatomically and functionally, throughout the body. Mast cell activity is modulated by neurotransmitters, allowing them to act as conduits for

peripheral and central nervous system control of inflammation, immunity, hemodynamics, and tissue remodeling. Mast cells act as components of the somatosensory system, responding to environmental cues and relaying signals to the nervous system resulting in changes in neural activity, sensitivity, and phenotype. Mast cells localize to a specific brain region and play a role in normative behavior. There is also growing evidence that aberrant brain mast cell function may contribute to neurodegenerative, neurodevelopmental, and mood disorders (*Forsythe., 2019*).

It is well demonstrated that *H. pylori* infection leads to chronic inflammation and is involved in the etiopathogenesis of atrophic gastritis, intestinal metaplasia and peptic ulcers. Patients with Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) have been found to have increased lamina propria immune cells in the colonic mucosa and significantly reduced levels of oleoylethanolamide (a fatty acid amide with anti-inflammatory properties) when compared to healthy controls. These are suggestive of chronic, subclinical inflammation at the microscopic level. Increased infiltration of mucosal mast cells have also been reported in the GI tract of patients with (IBS) when compared to healthy controls. In considering the possible pathogenic mechanisms of *H. pylori* in relation to (IBS), *H. pylori* infection has been associated with elevated inflammatory markers, increased mast cell activation and gastric mucosal and neural remodeling. Vacuolating cytotoxin A and the neutrophil-activating protein of *H. pylori* are both potent mast cell stimulators. Although a definite and consistent pattern of immune dysregulation has yet to be established in patients with (IBS), increased mast cell activation and immune activity in the gut may correlate with symptoms of visceral hypersensitivity (*Ng et al., 2019*).

Fig.(9): The mast cell, the “jack of all trades” immune cell (Walker et al.,2012)

The multitude of activators and the many modes of mast cell response account for their ability to impact a variety of physiological and pathogenic processes. Receptor-binding agonists, physical activators and cell–cell contact can all activate mast cells. Responses to activation are heterogeneous and include the release of preformed mediators stored within granules and the synthesis and release of new products. Activated mast cells can also respond by increasing the expression of ligands that mediate cell interactions with T and B cells (Walker et al.,2012).

12-2- Dendritic cell

Dendritic cells (DCs) are professional antigen-presenting cells (APCs) that induce T cell response against a presented antigen. Their migration from the site of an antigen uptake to the regional lymph nodes and their subsequent maturation profile decide about the type of the subsequent adaptive immune response profiles against infection (protective or nonprotective responses (Sesti-Costa et al., 2020)

Dendritic cells are considered proatherogenic especially in experimental immune models. Dendritic cells are likely to be involved in the initiation of the intimal inflammatory process. Resident vascular dendritic cells are present just beneath the endothelium, especially in mice strains. Blood monocytes differentiate to dendritic cells (*Xu et al., 2016*).

12-3-Macrophage

Macrophages belong to the mononuclear phagocytes; in other words, macrophages are differentiated monocytes and have larger cells and more intracellular organelles. Monocytes circulate in the bloodstream, and macrophages remain in different tissues. In different tissues, macrophages have special names, such as intestinal macrophages in the gut, Kupffer cells in the liver, microglial cells in the brain, and osteoclasts in bone. Macrophages are also very similar to neutrophils. Both have various types of PRRs, both have the powerful mechanism of phagocytosis, both can alarm other immune cells to the infection, and both use oxidative molecules to defend against invaders (*Tao et al., 2016*).

Macrophages are among the first cell types that *H. pylori* encounters if it invades the gastric epithelial barrier. Macrophages are the primary producers of TNF, and increased levels of TNF have been associated with an increased risk of gastric cancer. Kaparakis and coworkers showed that short-term depletion of macrophages from mice significantly reduced *H. pylori*-induced gastritis, demonstrating the contributory role macrophages play in the severity of gastric inflammation. Depending on environmental stimuli, macrophages polarize to M1 (classically activated macrophages) or M2 (alternatively activated macrophages) phenotypes. M1 macrophages (mostly present during *H. pylori* infection) play an essential role in initiating the host

response and eliminating pathogens through the production of proinflammatory mediators and antimicrobial molecules, such as nitric oxide (NO). In contrast, M2 macrophages resolve inflammation and are involved in wound healing and tissue homeostasis. Although macrophages are efficient at killing *H. pylori*, the pathogen has evolved several strategies to manipulate these effector cells and escape macrophage-mediated killing. For instance, *H. pylori* strains that carry the cag pathogenicity island (Cag-PAI) are able to block phagocytosis. *H. pylori* can also survive inside phagosomes when internalized. Furthermore, *H. pylori* prevents NO production and induces apoptosis in macrophages. The inability of macrophages to clear *H. pylori* produces a vicious cycle of the inflammatory response that eventually leads to peptic ulceration and favors gastric cancer development (*Gebremariam et al.,2019*).

13-Inflammatory mediator

The inflammatory response is a crucial aspect of the tissues' responses to deleterious inflammogens. This complex response involves leukocytes cells such as macrophages, neutrophils, and lymphocytes, also known as inflammatory cells. In response to the inflammatory process, these cells release specialized substances which include vasoactive amines and peptides, eicosanoids, proinflammatory cytokines, and acute-phase proteins, which mediate the inflammatory process by preventing further tissue damage and ultimately resulting in healing and restoration of tissue function. Whatever, the inflammatory response is triggered through two phases: (a) acute and (b) chronic, and each is apparently mediated by a different mechanism. These immune responses which involved in acute inflammation can be divided into vascular and cellular (*Abdulkhaleq et al.,2018*).

13-1-Vsoactive amine (histamine & serotonin)

Generally speaking, mast cells play an important role in acute inflammatory processes, allergic hypersensitivity type I reaction, tissue remodeling, wound healing and angiogenesis. Mast cells occupy strategic positions throughout the body, being present in areas exposed to the external cells occupy strategic positions throughout the body, being present in areas exposed to the external environment, such as skin, mucosa of the gastrointestinal, respiratory, and genitourinary tracts, where they interact with invading pathogens . Moreover, mast cells are located near vessels in the connective tissue where they may easily recruit circulating leukocytes. Secretory granules of human mast cells store biogenic amines (histamine and serotonin), preformed cytokines (tumor necrosis factor- α), serglycin proteoglycans, various lysosomal enzymes and some specific proteases, such as chymase, tryptase and carboxypeptidase A . The release of histamine from mast cells induces vasodilatation and edema, whereas the release of tumor necrosis factor- α , prostaglandin D2 and interleukin-8 stimulates neutrophil chemotaxis . Therefore, mast cell mediators play an important role in initiating the acute inflammatory reaction (*Petal., 2019*).

Bacteria are the most studied, particularly *Helicobacter pylori*. Protein components of *H. pylori* of molecular weight 21 and 35 Kd, can activate mast-cells in vitro, causing the release of histamine, TNF- α , IL-3, IFN- γ and LTB4 .(*Caffarelli et al.,2019*)

13-2-Arachidonic Acid and Its Metabolites

As a major component of cell membrane lipids, Arachidonic acid (AA), being a major component of the cell membrane lipid content, is mainly metabolized by three kinds of enzymes: cyclooxygenase (COX), lipoxygenase (LOX), and cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes. Based

on these three metabolic pathways, AA could be converted into various metabolites that trigger different inflammatory responses (*Wang et al., 2019*).

Helicobacter pylori could also act via immune-mediated mechanisms. Particularly, Doulberis et al., have suggested mechanistically, the release of proinflammatory and vasoactive factors, such as cytokines IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-12, TNF- α , interferon- γ , eicosanoids (leukotrienes, prostaglandins catalyzed by cyclooxygenase enzymes) and acute phase proteins (fibrinogen, CRP). Doulberis et al further postulated a possible stimulation of mononuclear cells to produce a tissue factor-like procoagulant, which converts fibrinogen to fibrin. Current evidence of abnormalities of both humoral and cellular immunity that play important roles in the *Helicobacter pylori* -associated gastric pathologies and other degenerative disorders including AD neuropathy have been recently reviewed (*Doulberis et al., 2020*).

13-4-Cyclooxygenase Enzyme 1 and 2 (COX-1,-2)

Cyclooxygenase 1, and 2 (COX-1,-2) are enzymes that catalyze the conversion of prostanoid to prostaglandins. Prostanoid synthesis is thought to be cytoprotective to the stomach and increases production of the pro-aggregatory prostanoid, thromboxane, by platelets (see Figure 1). Alternatively, COX-2 induction by TNF- α , INF- γ , and IL-1 is associated with colorectal cancer , and HP activates PLA2 and TNF- α expression . Also, COX-2 is present in the atrophic area and malignant gastric lesions . Overexpression of COX-2 prevents apoptosis . In this way, COX-2 might support the tumorigenic potential of HP. (*Alfarouk et al., 2019*).

Fig.(10): Phospholipase A2 is an enzyme (Alfarouk et al.,2019)

Phospholipase A2 is an enzyme that catalyzes the production of arachidonic acid from fatty acids. Arachidonic acid is further converted to prostaglandins and Leukotriene by cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenases enzymes, respectively. HP activates the Phospholipase A₂ enzyme (PLA₂) (Figure 10) (Alfarouk et al.,2019).

13-5-Leukotriene

Leukotriene is produced from arachidonic acid by the activity of the 5-Lipoxygenase enzyme, and this is accompanied by the release of histamine (see Figure 1). Leukotriene is associated with gastritis, and its receptors have been found to be overexpressed in gastric cancer. Leukotriene receptors are persistent in the epithelium of the stomach even after eradication of HP .In summary, HP is related to eicosanoids at multiple levels to create a sustainable chronic inflammatory environment that leads to initiation, development, and progression of gastric cancer. HP induced inflammation might, under certain circumstances, stimulate Prostaglandin E2 (PGE-2) which restores the mucous membrane of the stomach to normal homeostasis Lead to increase histamine so increase IgE (Alfarouk et al.,2019).

13-6-plasma protein

Serum protein markers, most notably albumin, have demonstrated significant value in assessing nutritional status and predicting outcomes in the setting of patients considered for elective surgery. Unfortunately the value of serum protein levels as indicators of nutritional status is extremely limited during the acute-phase response to injury, inflammation, infection, and surgical stress. The physiologic stress response upregulates expression of acute-phase reactive proteins, with unpredictable effects on “marker” protein levels. In the setting of acute burn care, presenting albumin levels or short-term changes therein should not be interpreted as being indicative of nutritional progress (*Carson et al., 2017*).

13-7-cytokines

Persistent infection with *H. pylori* is one of the triggers of chronic inflammation. Inflammation is a key component of the tumour’s microenvironment, and it is considered to represent the seventh hallmark of cancer. Chronic inflammation is associated with the generation and release of various mediators, including proinflammatory and oncogenic ones. During in-flammation, the released mediators that may predispose to tumourigenesis are reactive nitrogen oxygen species, inflammatory cytokines [i.e. interleukins (ILs), tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interferon (IFN), etc.], growth factors, and chemokines (*Negovan et al ., 2019*)

An important role in inflammatory response regulation is attributed to the cytokines. Cytokines are classified into two groups: Proinflammatory (IL-1 β , IL-1 α , IL-6, IL-8, IL-12, IL-17, IL-18, TNF- α , IFN- γ , etc) and anti-inflammatory (IL-4, IL-10, IL-13, etc). Some of the cytokines have a dual role (e.g., IL-10, IL-22, and TGF- β 1). Anti- and proinflammatory cytokines are involved in various cellular events, such

as the induction of expression of other cytokines, proliferation and differentiation of cells, adhesion, angiogenesis, necrosis, and apoptosis, all these processes being influenced by the presence of *H. pylori* infection. The inflammation induced by *H. pylori* infection leads to an increased gastric endothelial cell turnover and the deregulation of this inflammation, especially when it is associated with more virulent strains of *H. pylori* (*Negovan et al .,2019*).

cytokines play a central role in inflammatory diseases of infectious or noninfectious origin. PAMPs and DAMPs trigger a cytokine cascade that initially is composed of the proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-12, IFN- γ , IL-18, and TNF itself). These cytokines serve to contain and resolve the inflammatory foci through activation of local and systemic inflammatory responses. TNF also triggers a cytokine cascade of the antiinflammatory cytokines that block proinflammatory cytokine synthesis, as well as cytokine inhibitors that block proinflammatory cytokine actions. In most cases the inflammatory response is successfully resolved. Overzealous production of cytokines or the inability to shut down proinflammatory cytokine production, however, can lead to increasing concentrations of cytokines in the systemic circulation (“cytokine storm”). This continued cytokine production can have a deleterious effect on the host, with the development of hypotension, intravascular thrombosis, pulmonary edema, and hemorrhage; if this process is left unchecked, it can lead to multiple organ failure and death. This condition often is referred to as the *systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS)*. This term describes the clinical manifestations of widespread endothelial inflammation that leads to increased vascular permeability. This condition is the initiating pathologic process in a group of diverse disorders, such as bacterial

sepsis, ischemia, burn injury, trauma and tissue injury, and hemorrhagic shock (*Srinivasan et al., 2017*).

13-8-Cytokines

Cytokines are peptides that have a fundamental role in communication within the immune system and in allowing the immune system and host tissue cells to exchange information. Cytokines act via binding to a receptor that in turn sends a signal to the recipient cell, leading to a change in function or phenotype. Such signal cascades are complex and integrate a variety of environmental factors. Cytokines exist in broad families that are structurally related but exhibit diverse function (e.g., the TNF/TNF receptor superfamily, interleukin [IL]-1 superfamily, and IL-6 superfamily) (*Firesteine et al., 2016*).

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the *systemic inflammatory response syndrome* (SIRS). This term describes the clinical manifestations of widespread endothelial inflammation that leads to increased vascular permeability. This condition is the initiating pathologic process in a group of diverse disorders, such as bacterial sepsis, ischemia, burn injury, trauma and tissue injury, and hemorrhagic shock (*Srinivasan et al., 2017*).

13-9- Interferon

Dendritic cells (DC) act as a pivotal link in the specific immune response, and function in promoting pro-inflammatory T cells in response to *H. pylori* infection as demonstrated by increased interferon- γ (IFN- γ) and interleukin-12 (IL-12) production. This results in the stimulation of different subgroups of T lymphocytes (T cells), including T helper (Th) 1 and Th 2 cells, involved in mucosal protection and helping distinguish *H. pylori* from commensals. Furthermore, the most commonly observed Th1 phenotype, secreting IL-12 and IFN- γ , promotes gastritis, whereas Th2 cytokines are protective against gastric inflammation. *Morey et al., 2018* found that this mechanism allows *H. pylori* to persist in proximity to infected cells while inducing inflammation only in the neighboring, non-infected epithelium (*Wanqun et al., 2017*).

13-10-oxygen derived free radical

Inflammation caused by *H. pylori* is involved in the development of gut cancer which is due to its role in increasing chronic inflammation and cell proliferation. *H. pylori* induces alteration in various host signaling circuits enhancing pathogenicity. PRR signaling induced by *H. pylori* leads to the activation of AP1 and NF- κ B, resulting in the production of cytokines and chemokines. In addition, various mediators associated with inflammation, including free radicals (ROS and NOS), prostaglandins and growth factors, lead to chronic inflammation and oxidative damage of DNA in the gastric mucosa. Continuous

enhancement of proinflammatory mediators contribute to gastric mucosa and duodenal carcinoma. These factors induce DNA damage and oncogenic mutations and various epigenetic changes, including DNA methylation and histone changes provoking cancer development and progression including leukocytes, neo-angiogenesis, proliferation, survival, invasion and eventually, cancer metastasis. Related epigenetic changes in cancer suppressor genes promoters and regulatory impairments of some of the onco-miRNAs expression subsequently altered in cellular pathways are very relevant factors in the underlying formation of gastric carcinomas. It is noteworthy that gene expression regulation through epigenetic mechanisms, including DNA methylation and micro-RNAs are substantial to modulate cellular pathways. These epigenetic alterations represent prominent candidates for describing environmental factors roles in the genomic and cellular function enhancing the gastrointestinal carcinoma (Al-Alo et al., 2020)

13-11- Bradykinin

Bradykinin, a pro-inflammatory molecule, and its related peptides have been studied for their effects on acute reactions in upper and lower airways, where they can be synthesised and metabolized after exposure to different stimuli including allergens and viral infection. Bradykinin B1 and B2 receptors are constitutively expressed in the airways on several residential and/or immune cells. Their expression can also be induced by inflammatory mediators, usually associated with eosinophil and neutrophil recruitment, such as IL-4, IL-13, TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-8, via intracellular MAPK and NF- κ B signalling. In turn, the latter up-regulate both bradykinin receptors. Bradykinin activates epithelial/endothelial and immune cells, neurons and mesenchymal cells (such as fibroblasts, myofibroblasts and smooth muscle cells), which are implicated in the development of airway chronic inflammation,

responsiveness and remodelling (a major feature of severe asthma) (*Ricciardolo et al., 2018*).

H.pylori is a bacterium that lives in the intestinal lining of the stomach and releases a protein called Bradykinin. Increased plasma level of Bradykinin and H.pylori induced ROS was found to be associated with vasodilatation and inflammation (*Aloke et al., 2019*).

Bradykinin causes acute and chronic pain and thermal hyperalgesia in the presence of inflammation through second messenger cascades mediated via B2 and B1 receptors, respectively. Therapeutic targets should focus on the B1 pathways as well as the B2 receptor in order to have meaningful analgesic effects (*Milner and Doherty., 2015*).

14-Recognition of stimuli

14-1-Toll like receptor

Toll-like receptors (TLRs) play critical roles in host defense by recognizing specific molecular patterns from a wide variety of pathogens. Using a small set of adaptor proteins TLR engagement leads to the activation of nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) and interferon regulatory factors (IRFs). This results in the upregulation of downstream target genes including an array of pro-inflammatory cytokines, chemokines, and interferon-responsive genes. In macrophages TLR signaling also induces autophagy. Autophagy is a cellular response to starvation that helps remove damaged organelles and long-lived proteins from the cytosol. It also has a cytoprotective function helping to limit the replication of intracellular pathogens. Many pathogens target the autophagy pathway to thwart its effectiveness (*Vural et al .,2015*).

H. pylori infection disrupts gastric homeostasis within the local mucosa and promotes the production of multiple inflammatory cytokines. After microorganism infection, TLRs are the first line of host defense. They are important components of innate immunity and are involved in

the activation of the adaptive immune response. Thus, during *H. pylori* infection, TLRs on gastric epithelial and immune cells recognize many PAMPs. Toll-like receptors 2 and 4 recognize lipopolysaccharides, Toll-like receptor 5 recognizes flagellin, and Toll-like receptor 9 (TLR9) recognizes unmethylated CpG oligonucleotides, which are abundant in bacterial DNA. Based on the recognition and activation of these receptor signaling pathways, the inflammatory process and the presence of genetic polymorphisms may modulate the risk of developing precancerous gastric lesions and GC (Nemati et al.,2017).

Figure (11):Toll like receptor (Nemati et al.,2017)

14-2-Inflammasome

Infection with the Gram-negative pathogen *Helicobacter pylori* is the most prevalent chronic bacterial infection affecting about 50 % of the human world population and is the main risk factor for gastric cancer development. The pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β plays a crucial role

in the development of gastric tumors, and polymorphisms in the IL-1 gene cluster resulting in increased IL-1 β production have been associated with increased risk for gastric cancer. Recently, *Helicobacter pylori* was postulated to activate the inflammasome in human and mouse immune cells, and the molecular mechanisms and the bacterial virulence factors activating the inflammasome were elucidated in cell culture as well as animal models. It appears that *H. pylori*-induced IL-1 β secretion is mediated by activation of toll-like receptor 2 (TLR-2), Nod-like receptor family member NLRP3 and caspase-1. The *cag* pathogenicity island-encoded type IV secretion system, lipopolysaccharide, vacuolating cytotoxin, and urease B subunit appear to play a role in inflammasome activation. In addition, recent results indicate that the TLR-2 \rightarrow NLRP3 \rightarrow caspase-1 \rightarrow IL-18 axis is critical to *H. pylori*-specific immune regulation conferring protection against allergen-induced asthma and inflammatory bowel disease in murine models (*Pachathundikandi .,2016*).

Fig. (12): Signaling pathways of inflammasome activation by *Helicobacter pylori*. (*Pachathundikandi .,2016*).

H. pylori stimulate inflammasome formation in human and mouse DCs, macrophages, or monocytes. Host cell receptors including TLR-2, NOD2, and Muc1, which are targeted by various indicated or yet unknown bacterial factors, appear to play a role in upstream signaling events leading to transcription factor NF- κ B activation and production of NLRP3 and 1L-1b and 1L-18 pro-forms. Engagement of NLRP3 and ASC induces the cleavage of autoproteolytic pro-caspase-1 and the subsequent processing and release of mature interleukin-1b (1L-1b) and 1L-18 cytokines. In addition, *H. pylori* flagellin-A was shown to activate the phosphorylation of NLCR4 by a yet unknown mechanism, but this signaling does not lead to caspase-1 activation and must have other yet unknown consequences for the host cells. For more details please see text (*Pachathundikandi .,2016*).

15-Types of Inflammatory response

The inflammatory response is the coordinate activation of signaling pathways that regulate inflammatory mediator levels in resident tissue cells and inflammatory cells recruited from the blood. Inflammation is a common pathogenesis of many chronic diseases, including cardiovascular and bowel diseases, diabetes, arthritis, and cancer. Although inflammatory response processes depend on the precise nature of the initial stimulus and its location in the body, they all share a common mechanism, which can be summarized as follows: 1) cell surface pattern receptors recognize detrimental stimuli; 2) inflammatory pathways are activated; 3) inflammatory markers are released; and 4) inflammatory cells are recruited (*Chen et al., 2018*).

The inflammatory response is a complex biological reaction of the body which appears when healthy tissues are wounded by physical/chemical stimuli or are invaded by bacteria, viruses, or toxins.

The protective response of the injured tissue includes immune cells, blood vessels, and molecular mediators (*Nistor, and Rusu .,2019*).

The inflammatory response manifests primarily as acute (minutes-to-days) and chronic (weeks-to-months) responses based on the duration and intensity of inflammatory stimuli and its mitigation *in situ*. Generally, the acute inflammatory response to biomaterials resolves quickly, usually within a week, depending on the extent of injury (*Rao et al ., 2015*).

15-1-The acute inflammatory response

The Acute-Phase Response Released pro-inflammatory cytokines create a proinflammatory loop that can break away from the injured tissue and enter the bloodstream, leading to what has been called the Cytokine storm. TNF- α is one of the many cytokines involved in this process. Organ-specific receptors are activated by these cytokines and a systemic reaction ensues. This systemic reaction is called the acute-phase response, and here, the liver is the major player. The liver begins increasing the production of certain proteins—C-reactive protein, serum amyloid A, haptoglobin, fibrinogen, α -globulins with antiprotease-activity, lipopolysaccharide binding protein, ceruloplasmin, complement factor and decreasing the synthesis of others, which leads to the decrease in certain substances in serum—zinc, iron, albumin, transferrin, cortisol-binding globulin, transthyretin, and retinol-binding protein. The purpose of each of these changes in protein quantity has not yet been fully clarified, but scavenging pathogens and modulation of the inflammatory response and its consequences may be an important goal. C-reactive protein is the best clinical indicator of the acute-phase response , although it does not distinguish between the different causes of inflammation, while albumin has the disadvantage of also being decreased in case of malnutrition and elevated in dehydration. Another site where the circulating cytokines act is in the brain endothelium, leading to the

release of prostaglandins, which are responsible for the symptoms of lethargy, anorexia, and fever, a positive adaptive response to infection. Further changes occur during inflammation, namely an elevated metabolic rate, with muscle catabolism to retrieve amino acids, essential for tissue repair and synthesis of proteins for the immune response to the lesion; the outcome of this is muscle wasting (*Varela et al.,2018*).

15-1-1-vascular response

Epidemiologically, vascular inflammation is detected by enhanced circulating IL-6, a glycoprotein cytokine produced by the activated inflammatory cells within the vessel wall. IL-6 production, in turn, induces the expression of hepatic acute-phase reactants, including C-reactive protein, γ -fibrinogen, angiotensinogen, and others, some of which are measured clinically to assess atherosclerotic risk. Although useful clinically as a cardiovascular risk indicator, the role of IL-6 in the vasculature is only beginning to be understood (*Brasier.,2010*).

Vasodilation due to cytokines leads to hypotension, with a decrease of systemic vascular resistance, and, together with the shift of fluid to the interstitial space, less blood is returned to the heart, potentiating tachycardia and temporarily inducing an increase in myocardial contractility to increase systolic volume. Myocardial depression then ensues and an increase in central venous pressure follows the failing heart (*Varela et al.,2018*).

Several studies have reported that cardiovascular disease (CVD) may be associated with certain microorganisms such as *Chlamydia pneumonia*, cytomegalovirus, or *Helicobacter pylori*. Those reports have suggested that the pathogens might directly invade the vessel wall, leading to localized vascular inflammation. Additionally, not only localized but also systemic inflammation by such pathogens might

indirectly induce endothelial dysfunction and dyslipidemia, resulting in CVD (Lee et., 2018)

Fig.(13): Tissue and vascular changes during a local inflammatory event. the five cardinal signs of inflammation are in bold; DAMPs damage-associated molecular patterns; PAMPs pathogen-associated molecular patterns; ROS reactive oxygen species (Varela et al.,2018)

15-1-2- cellular response

At the tissue level, inflammation is characterized by redness, swelling, heat, pain, and loss of tissue function, which result from local immune, vascular and inflammatory cell responses to infection or injury. Important microcirculatory events that occur during the inflammatory process include vascular permeability changes, leukocyte recruitment and accumulation, and inflammatory mediator release. Various pathogenic factors, such as infection, tissue injury, or cardiac infarction, can induce inflammation by causing tissue damage. The etiologies of inflammation can be infectious or non-infectious. In response to tissue injury, the body initiates a chemical signaling cascade that stimulates responses aimed at healing affected tissues. These signals activate leukocyte chemotaxis from the general circulation to sites of damage. These activated

leukocytes produce cytokines that induce inflammatory responses (*Chen et al., 2018*).

15-1-2-1- Margination

Margination can be described as the ability of leukocytes and platelets to migrate from bulk flow to vessel walls in blood microcirculation, an essential phenomenon to ensure efficient immune systems inflammatory response. The richness of chemical and biological environment of cells in blood involves many long- and short-range interactions between cells in flow making intricate the physical understanding of margination (*Chachanidze., et al., 2019*).

Leukocytes or white blood cells (WBCs) are part of our immune system, performing various organism defense functions. In order to reach the sites of action (e.g., inflammation), WBCs have to migrate to the vessel walls through a process called margination , adhere efficiently to vascular endothelium (mediated by adhesion proteins), and further transmigrate into the surrounding tissues . The efficiency of WBC adhesion in blood flow is correlated with the contact frequency of WBCs with the vessel walls, and thus with margination. The mechanism for WBC margination in microvessels is related to the presence of red blood cells (RBCs) in blood. RBCs in microvessels migrate to the vessel center . This process is governed by cell-wall hydrodynamic interactions (often called lift force), which drive the cells away from the wall, and by cell-cell interactions, which tend to disperse RBCs. WBC margination is believed to be a consequence of the competition between lift forces on RBCs and WBCs, where the lift force on a RBC is larger than that on a WBC due to the nonspherical discocyte shape and high deformability of RBCs. These interactions result in WBC margination (i.e., segregation), such that their concentration becomes higher near a vessel wall (*Fedosov et al., 2012*)

Fig. (14): Inflammatory cellular events.

15-1-2-2- The Multistep Model Extravasation Cascade

Recruitment of circulating cells from blood to inflamed tissue involves a sequential and coordinated series of molecular actions mediated by adhesive interactions between circulating sentinels and endothelial cells in post-capillary venules. Here, we review the molecular effectors that regulate the initial phagocyte–endothelial binding interactions, which are essential for transendothelial migration of blood monocytes to sites of injury (*Silva et al.,2018*)

Figure (15):Mechanisms of adhesion and penetration of immune cells in the subendothelial space (*Tousoulis .,2017*).

Multistep model of circulating blood cell adhesion and migration along the vascular endothelium. Cells make adhesive contacts onto the inflamed endothelial surface through engagement of their sialofucosylated glycan determinants to vascular E-selectin (Step 1—tethering and rolling). Subsequent engagement of chemokine receptors leads to integrin activation (Step 2) and firm adhesion of leukocytes to endothelium (Step 3), allowing their transmigration (Step 4) (*Tousoulis* *.,2017*).

➤ **Step one (rolling)**

To initiate the extravasation process, circulating phagocytes establish low-affinity and reversible interactions (tethering) on target endothelial cells, achieving low velocity “rolling” adhesive interactions (Step 1, Figure 15) (*Silva et al.,2018*)

Leukocyte rolling describes the low affinity adhesive interaction between leukocytes and the vascular endothelium whereby the force of blood flow induces a rotational motion (i.e., rolling) of the leukocyte along the vascular wall. Rolling behavior is most often quantified as the number (or flux) of rolling leukocytes, which is assessed by counting the number of leukocytes flowing past a fixed point (line drawn perpendicular to the long vessel axis on TV monitor) in the vessel of interest that are moving slower than the stream of erythrocytes (*Zuidema and Korthuis., 2015*).

E-selectin extends from the plasma membrane of inflamed endothelium and serves to capture leukocytes from flowing blood via long-lived catch-bonds that support slow leukocyte rolling under shear stress. Its ligands are glycosylated with the tetrasaccharide sialyl Lewis^x (sLe^x), which contributes to bond affinity and specificity. E-selectin-mediated rolling transmits signals into neutrophils that trigger

activation of high-affinity β_2 -integrins necessary for transition to shear-resistant adhesion and transendothelial migration (*Morikis et al., 2017*).

The initial stage of an inflammatory response involves leukocyte marginalization. It takes place in small-diameter vessels, in which inflammatory cells do not migrate to the center but are pushed towards the vascular walls, where the process of their endothelial rolling begins. TNF- α , histamine and other mediators of inflammation stimulate translocation of P-selectin from Weibel–Palade corpuscles, which is later incorporated in the endothelial cell membrane. Selectin interacts with sialylated or fucosylated carbohydrate residues of the Lewis group antigens, which act as their ligands. PSGL-1 is best known among them. However, any adequately modified glycoprotein can be a potential selectin receptor, like CD34, which having been transformed on the endothelial surface becomes L-selectin receptor on leukocytes. Ligand binding to selectin is a dynamic process and the bonds being formed undergo rapid dissociation. Many times the binding of leukocytes to endothelium slows down their vascular flow from 1000 to 30 $\mu\text{m/s}$. A few hours after activation, E-selectin appears on the endothelial surface. P-selectin mediates binding at high shear stress, whereas E-selectin takes part in slow leukocyte rolling (low shear stress). This is associated with partial leukocyte integrin activation. The rolling leukocytes may have a direct contact with endothelium, due to which they may be activated by inflammatory factors (chemokines) present on the endothelial surface (*Korniluk et al., 2017*).

The issue of the role of infectious agents in recruiting platelets into thrombus has been widely examined.²⁷ Platelets derive from megakaryocyte cytoplasm, and on activation change from the normal disc shape to a compact sphere with dendritic extension facilitating adhesion. Platelets are the first blood cells to arrive at the site of endothelial

activation. By its glycoproteins (GPs) Ib and IIb/IIIa these cells engage surface molecules on the endothelium, which contributes to endothelial cell activation. Once activated, these cells express several types of leukocyte adhesion molecules, which can cause blood cell rolling along the vascular surface to adhere to the site of activation.²⁸ This step might play an important role in platelet aggregation leading to plaque vulnerability and eliciting acute ischemic events. Hence, the speculation that *H. pylori* infection could induce platelets and immune activation mediated by cytokines, such as interleukin (IL)-1, IL-6 and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α (discussion) (*Ribaldone., et al.,2016*).

➤ **Step 2: integrin activation**

Rolling exposes these cells to chemokines that are immobilized by glycosaminoglycans on the endothelial surface, and, in turn, facilitates engagement of G-protein-coupled chemokine receptors (GPCRs) expressed on the mononuclear phagocyte cell surface (Step 2, Figure 15), with resultant G-protein-driven integrin activation (*(Silva et al.,2018)*)

Figure (16) :rolling and vascular changes during a local inflammatory event.

➤ **Step 3: Leukocyte-adhesion cascade**

Activated integrins on phagocytes, principally very late activation protein 4 and LFA-1, bind to their respective endothelial receptors vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 and intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), leading to firm adhesion of MPS cells on the endothelium (Step 3, Figure 15) (*Silva et al.,2018*)

The leukocyte adhesion cascade is of critical importance for both the maintenance of immune homeostasis and the ability of immune cells to perform effector functions. All immune cells, including T cells, need to be able to traffic between the lumen of the vasculature and tissues to maintain immune homeostasis or to perform effector functions at the sites of infection and inflammation . In order to perform these duties, immune cells need to adhere to the endothelium near sites of activation while avoiding sites where no response is needed. In response to these challenges, nature has evolved the leukocyte adhesion cascade, which is typically separated into four distinct, sequential steps: tethering, rolling, firm arrest, and transmigration. During tethering, cells interact with P- or E-selectin molecules expressed on the activated endothelial surface. These initial interactions slow the cell while also allowing more intimate contact between the cell and the apical surface of endothelium. As the cell velocity slows, additional selectins and other adhesive molecules are engaged, leading to sustained or slow rolling. During rolling, the T lymphocyte can be activated by chemokines, either on the endothelium or in solution, which initiates intracellular signalling cascades whose end result is the activation of integrins such as LFA-1 on the T cell surface. Once fully activated, the integrin-based adhesions become mechanically stronger and lead to firm arrest on the endothelial surface (*Anderson et al., 2019*)

Cell adhesion molecules including receptors of the immunoglobulin superfamily and integrins are of crucial importance in mediating these processes. Particularly integrins play a vital role in regulating all aspects of immune cell function including immune cell trafficking into tissues, effector cell activation and proliferation and the formation of the immunological synapse between immune cells or between immune cell and the target cell both during homeostasis and during inflammation and cancer. Adhesion molecules are generally divided into five groups: integrins (discussed in greater detail below), selectins, cadherins, members of the immunoglobulin superfamily (IgSF) including nectins and others such as mucins. In addition to the conventional adhesion molecules, certain enzymes such as vascular adhesion protein 1 (VAP-1) also play a role in cell adhesion. Apart from structural differences, cell adhesion molecules also bind to different ligands. Integrins typically bind to the extracellular matrix, while selectins, cadherins, and IgSF members are associated with cell-cell adhesion. However, immune cell integrins also bind to soluble ligands and ligands on other cells. The cell-cell adhesion mediating molecules can further be divided by their ligands as selectins bind carbohydrates in a calcium dependent manner, cadherins mediate preferably homophilic bonds in a calcium-dependent manner and the IgSF subfamily nectins mediate homophilic and heterophilic bonds . Selectins are further divided into P-, E- and L-selectins originally based on which cell types they were found in: **p**latelets, endothelial cells and **l**eukocytes (however, P-selectin is also expressed on endothelial cells) . Selectins differ in kinetics of expression, as P-selectins are expressed within minutes and E-selectins within hours . Selectins are especially important for leukocyte trafficking, migration of lymphocytes to peripheral lymph nodes and to the skin. Their most prominent function is associated with the initial stage of the

rolling cell adhesion cascade in which selectin binding enables rolling . Selectin binding also initiates the subsequent integrin dependent step of slow rolling and cell arrest as selectin binding together with chemokine receptor activation initiates inside out signaling leading to integrin activation (see later sections) . L-selectins in particular display a force dependent binding e.g., L-selectin forms catch bonds with its ligands (bonds that strengthen under force). Catch bonds dominate until the applied force reaches a force threshold upon which slip bonds are formed (bonds that weaken under force). In other selectins this occurs to a lesser extent (*Harjunpää et al., 2019*)

15-1-2-3- Crawling

This crawling process has been proposed to be a mechanism that scans for optimal extravasation sites and allows leucocytes to efficiently migrate through the endothelial wall to the sites of primary inflammation. Additionally, neutrophils crawling over the endothelium during inflammation are able to specifically interact with other cellular blood components, such as platelets and red blood cells, through a process regulated by E-selectin and mediated by Mac-1. These interactions have been shown to be key in the development of thrombotic injury in models of acute inflammation, such as in transfusion-related acute lung injury (TRALI) or during vaso-occlusive crisis in sickle cell disease (SCD). The molecular mechanisms controlling intravascular neutrophil polarization, crawling and migration remain only partially understood. Similarly, other aspects of the behaviour of neutrophils inside vessels prior to their extravasation remain partially obscure, in part due to the lack of high-resolution imaging techniques that allow discrimination between intravascular and perivascular or extravascular spaces (*Gómez-Moreno et l., 2018*)

The process of “crawling” is mediated by proteins belonging to the leukocyte and endothelial integrins, i.e., Mac-1 (CD11b/ CD18) that bind ICAM-1. In the case of monocytes, the transmigration is mediated also by LFA-1 (CD11a/CD18) and ICAM-2. During diapedesis leukocytes assume the amoeboid shape as a result of cytoskeletal alterations and push their way between endothelial cells. The stages of rolling, activation, adhesion and “crawling” are reversible and require heterophilic bonds. On the contrary, diapedesis is a no-return path, during which leukocytes interact due to homophilic bonds (*Korniluk et al.,2017*).

Figure (17): The leukocyte extravasation cascade (*Filippi., 2016*)

The leukocyte extravasation cascade is controlled by sequential adhesive interactions between leukocytes and endothelial cells. This schema depicts various steps and the adhesive molecules that are involved at each step. The neutrophil extravasation cascade involves a sequence of tethering and rolling along the endothelium, followed by firm adhesion and arrest onto the endothelium. Subsequently, neutrophils undergo lateral migration or crawling on endothelial cells to find a permissive site for transmigration. It should be noted that subsequent to moving across the endothelial barrier, leukocytes undergo abluminal crawling between endothelial cells and pericytes before crossing the basement membrane and migrating within interstitial tissues (*Filippi., 2016*)

➤ Intavascular Crawling (Locomotion)

Getting leukocytes out of the vessel and into to the tissue is a major goal of acute inflammation. Leukocytes roll on and adhere to the vessel wall, locomote along the vessel to endothelial cell borders; transmigrate across the endothelium and across the subendothelial basement membrane into the tissue (Fig.18)

Figure (18): leukocyte-endothelial interactions that regulate leukocyte extravasation.

Leukocyte extravasation is regulated by a series of wellorchestrated interactive steps between leukocytes and activated endothelium. The capture and rolling of free-flowing leukocytes is mediated by selectins and integrins. The transition from fast rolling to slow rolling enables leukocyte activation mediated by chemokine receptor recognition of chemokines presented on the surface of endothelial cells (lightning bolt). Leukocyte tightly adhere and crawl along the vessel wall (integrin mediated) until they undergo diapedesis. Diapedesis or TEM is mediated by sequential protein-protein interactions between adhesion receptors expressed by the migrating leukocyte and the endothelium. Leukocytes then traverse the basement membrane and move through the interstitial tissue. It has since been updated to include slow rolling, locomotion, and newly identified proteins that regulate each step

transendothelial migration. Leukocyte locomotion is predominantly mediated by the $\beta 1$ integrin Mac-1. Locomotion is imperative for the leukocyte's transition from firm adhesion to moving along the vessel to find a suitable site for transendothelial migration. Monocyte expression of Mac-1 promotes locomotion along the vessel wall via ICAM-1 expressed by the inflamed endothelium. Selective inhibition of either Mac-1 or ICAM-1 in vitro prevents monocytes from crawling along the vessel wall despite still being adherent to the endothelium. In mice, leukocyte locomotion is mediated by IL-8 activation of Mac-1. Under flow conditions, mouse neutrophil crawling is increased via Mac-1 and junctional adhesion molecule C (JAM-C) binding (*Rutledge and Muller.,2020*).

Monocytes, like all leukocytes, undergo a series of sequential steps during extravasation from blood into tissues: tethering, rolling, adhesion and diapedesis. (*Schenkel and Muller.,2004*) have discovered an essential step, which we call locomotion, in which the monocyte moves from a site of firm adhesion to the nearest junction to begin diapedesis. Blocking CD11a-CD18 and CD11b-CD18 on human monocytes or adhesion molecules ICAM-1 and ICAM-2 on endothelial cells prevented the monocytes from reaching junctions. The blocked monocytes spun in circles as if they were unable to direct their movement despite being able to adhere and polarize normally. This step fills a gap in the paradigm of extravasation as a multistep process (*Schenkel., 2004*)

15-1-2-4- Diapedesis

The neutrophil transmigration across the blood endothelial cell barrier represents the prerequisite step of innate inflammation. Neutrophil recruitment to inflamed tissues occurs in a well-defined stepwise manner, which includes elements of neutrophil rolling, firm adhesion, and

crawling onto the endothelial cell surface before transmigrating across the endothelial barrier. This latter step known as diapedesis can occur at the endothelial cell junction (paracellular) or directly through the endothelial cell body (transcellular). The extravasation cascade is controlled by series of engagement of various adhesive modules, which result in activation of bidirectional signals to neutrophils and endothelial cells for adequate cellular response (*Filippi.,2016*)

When leukocytes leave the circulation, they cross the vessel wall by penetrating the endothelial monolayer, a specialized step called diapedesis. They can do that in a paracellular manner, that is, through the cell–cell junctions, or in a transcellular manner, that is, through the endothelial cell body. At this point in the transendothelial migration process, the endothelium actively participates by inducing actin-rich structures that surround the transmigrating leukocyte that in some cases extend dorsally. Morphologically, these structures resemble the interaction of an antigen-presenting-cell and a T-cell, also known as the immunological synapse. In this mini-review, we highlight the similarities between these two seemingly different cell–cell interactions processes and propose the term ‘*diapedesis synapse*’ to reflect the active participation of the endothelium with the leukocyte in order to finalize diapedesis and the importance of this interaction for immune cell function that surpasses the simple act of passing through a vessel wall (*Schoppmeyer and van., 2020*)

15-1-2-5- Leukocyte Transmigration

Transport into and out of the blood vessels (extravasation) is regulated by endothelial cells (ECs), pericytes, perivascular extracellular matrix (ECM), resident innate immune cells, and a variety of cytokine signals, all working to maintain or restore vascular barrier homeostasis. The study of leukocyte egress through the vascular wall is the most

widely studied transmigration event. Pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) trigger a response in the innate immune cells primarily residing in the peripheral tissues. These immune cells, such as macrophages, release a variety of cytokine and proinflammatory molecules that stimulate the ECs lining the blood vessels within proximity to the pathogenic invasion. The resulting cytokine gradient, coupled with the expression of pro-transmigration molecules on the EC surface, attracts circulating leukocytes to the site of infection (*Salminen et al., 2019*).

It should be noted that while leukocyte rolling and firm adhesion have been extensively examined including in in vivo studies, little is known about signaling mechanisms of leukocyte locomotion leading to transmigration in vivo. This is due to the technical complexity of examining these steps in vivo or in in vitro model systems of cells migrating through endothelial cells under shear flow. Further, the same signaling molecules are involved at each step of the extravasation cascade, although in different network organization, so that their specific roles during locomotion and diapedesis are difficult to appreciate in vivo using genetic models. Hence, most of our knowledge of leukocyte polarity and locomotion derive from in vitro studies of cells plated on various substrates and in transwell assays, which have yet to be validated by in vivo intravital microscopy studies (*Filippi, 2016*)

15-1-2-6- Chemotaxis

Neutrophils are the primary cells recruited to inflamed sites during an innate immune response to tissue damage and/or infection. They are finely sensitive to inciting stimuli to reach in great numbers and within minutes areas of inflammation and tissue insult. For this effective response, they can detect extracellular chemical gradients and move towards higher concentrations, the so-called chemotaxis process or

guided cell migration. This directed neutrophil recruitment is orchestrated by chemoattractants, a chemically diverse group of molecular guidance cues (e.g., lipids, N-formylated peptides, complement, anaphylotoxins and chemokines). Neutrophils respond to these guidance signals in a hierarchical manner and, based on this concept, they can be further subdivided into two groups: "end target" and "intermediary" chemoattractants, the signals of the former dominant over the latter. Neutrophil chemoattractants exert their effects through interaction with heptahelical G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) expressed on cell surfaces and the chemotactic response is mainly regulated by the Rho family of GTPases. Additionally, neutrophil behavior might differ and be affected in different complex scenarios such as disease conditions and type of vascular bed in specific organs. Finally, there are different mechanisms to disrupt neutrophil chemotaxis either associated to the resolution of inflammation or to bacterial escape and systemic infection (*Petri and Sanz ., 2018*).

Neutrophils are key players of the innate immune system, that are involved in coordinating the initiation, propagation and resolution of inflammation. Accurate neutrophil migration (chemotaxis) to sites of inflammation in response to gradients of chemoattractants is pivotal to these roles. Binding of chemoattractants to dedicated G-protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) initiates downstream signalling events that promote neutrophil polarisation, a prerequisite for directional migration (*Michael and Vermeren., 2019*)

15-1-2-7- phagocytosis

Phagocytosis is an important component of the microbicidal function of neutrophils; however, phagocytosis is also utilized by a variety of cell types in several physiological contexts. Elie Metchnikoff, commonly referred to as the father of innate immunity, explored

phagocytosis in polymorphonuclear neutrophils, and macrophages .Since then, many more metazoan cells have been described to display phagocytic capacity. The main objective of this review is to provide an overview of the multiplicity of functions served by phagocytes. Phagocytic cells can be organized into two categories: the professional and non-professional phagocytes. Professional or dedicated phagocytes consist primarily of polymorphonuclear neutrophils, monocytes, monocyte-derived macrophages, and tissue-resident macrophages cells whose raison d'être is phagocytosis. Non-professional phagocytes include all other cell types that can perform phagocytosis, such as epithelial cells, fibroblasts, and dendritic cells (DCs). Such cells have a more restricted set of targets and engulf them more slowly. Thus, the phagocytic capacity of non-professional phagocytes differs significantly in scope and efficiency from that of professional phagocytes. Both professional and non-professional phagocytes play important roles in innate immunity due to their ability to engulf pathogens. However, they are also vital in the maintenance of the healthy physiological state, in recovery from injury and in the development of the host organism. Thus, the consequences of phagocytosis extend well beyond the context of innate immunity (*Lim et al.,2017*).

The acute inflammatory response is normally terminated once the triggering insult is eliminated, the infection is cleared, and damaged tissue is repaired. Termination of the inflammatory response and transition to the homeostatic state is an active and highly regulated process known as the resolution of inflammation. Several key regulatory mechanisms of resolution have been identified including the switch from proinflammatory prostaglandins to anti-inflammatory, resolution-inducing lipoxins. This switch, in turn, orchestrates a transition from neutrophil to monocyte recruitment that results in clearance of the dead

cells and other debris and initiation of tissue repair at the affected site. If the inflammatory trigger is not eliminated by the acute inflammatory response or persists for any other reason, the resolution phase may not be appropriately induced and a chronic inflammatory state may ensue. This state can be caused by chronic infections, unrepaired tissue damage, persistent allergens, undigestible foreign particles, or endogenous crystals, such as monosodium urate. The chronic inflammatory response in these cases is typically localized to the site where the inflammatory inducer is present and often results in different types of local tissue remodeling (*Medzhitov.,2010*).

15-1-Chronic inflammatory response

Most of the features of acute inflammation continue as the inflammation becomes chronic, including expansion of blood vessels (vasodilation), increase in blood flow, capillary permeability and migration of neutrophils into the infected tissue through the capillary wall (diapedesis). However, the composition of the white blood cells changes soon and the macrophages and lymphocytes begin to replace short-lived neutrophils. Thus the hallmarks of chronic inflammation are the infiltration of the primary inflammatory cells such as macrophages, lymphocytes, and plasma cells in the tissue site, producing inflammatory cytokines, growth factors, enzymes and hence contributing to the progression of tissue damage and secondary repair including fibrosis and granuloma formation, etc (*Pahwa et al.,2020*)

Atherosclerosis is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by the formation of subintimal plaques comprised of lipid-laden macrophages (foam cells), vascular smooth muscle cells, chronic inflammatory cells, and extracellular matrix—predominantly collagen—in elastic and muscular arteries. Circulating low density lipoprotein (LDL) seeps into the arterial walls and over time becomes oxidized and

aggregated. These altered forms of LDL resemble pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and damage associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) that are recognized by scavenger receptors and Toll-like receptors on endothelial cells and macrophages. Endothelial cells activated by the underlying pro-inflammatory molecules express elevated levels the selectins and Ig superfamily molecules described earlier. The recruitment and adhesion of circulating monocytes by selectins, ICAM-1, and VCAM-1 is important for the progression of the disease . Monocyte interaction with activated endothelium during TEM is crucial for the development of foam cells from human monocyte-derived macrophages in vitro . Initially, induction of transcription factors in the macrophages attempts to break down the lipid and restore homeostasis. However, as the lesion grows in size, the macrophages become overwhelmed and can no longer keep up with the accumulation of lipid. They retain neutral lipid droplets giving their cytoplasm a foamy appearance (hence the name). Eventually, rather than undergoing anti-inflammatory apoptosis, these cells die by secondary necrosis, spilling pro-inflammatory mediators into the lesion and creating a vicious cycle of inflammation that fails to resolve. The growth of atherosclerotic plaques is promoted by the continued influx and activation of monocytes and lymphocytes . Previously, treatment for atherosclerosis has been focused on lowering cholesterol; however, more recent studies have demonstrated that inflammation per se is a significant promoter of inflammation and anti-inflammatory agents could be promising therapeutics treatment of atherosclerosis (The CANTOS trial) (*Rutledge and Muller., 2020*)

15-1-1-Types of Chronic Inflammation

Nonspecific proliferative:

Characterized by the presence of non-specific granulation tissue formed by infiltration of mononuclear cells (lymphocytes, macrophages,

plasma cells) and proliferation of fibroblasts, connective tissue, vessels and epithelial cells, for example, an inflammatory polyp-like nasal or cervical polyp and lung abscess (*Pahwa et al.,2020*).

The mononuclear cell infiltration which characterizes the chronic inflammatory reaction results from the migration of lymphocytes and monocytes through the endothelium of the postcapillary venule. The initial step in the emigration of these cells is their binding to the vascular endothelium (*Ziff,1989*).

B-Granulomatous inflammation:

A specific type of chronic inflammation characterized by the presence of distinct nodular lesions or granulomas formed with an aggregation of activated macrophages or its derived cell called epithelioid cells usually surrounded by lymphocytes. The macrophages or epithelioid cells inside the granulomas often coalesce to form Langhans or giant cells such as foreign body, Aschoff, Reed-Sternberg and Tumor giant cells (*Pahwa et al.,2020*).

15-1-2-Infiltration of mononuclear cells in chronic inflammation

Macrophage

Macrophages belong to the mononuclear phagocyte system (MPS), a family of professional phagocytes that includes monocyte and dendritic cells (DCs). Over the past few decades, classification of the cells within the MPS system has generated considerable controversy given the different, often confusing, nomenclature to identify macrophages in different physio/pathological conditions as a consequence of their plasticity, resulting in very different phenotype/functions. The first open debate arises already in the definition of macrophage cell of origin. The classic scenario of the MPS stated that monocytes recruited from the

periphery, under the influence of specific tissue-local growth factors, developed into macrophages. According to this scenario, macrophages derive from hematopoietic progenitors of bone marrow that differentiate under the influence of specific growth factors within the hosting tissues . These cells primarily enter the blood as monocytes and further infiltrate tissues as macrophages, where they adapt to the local microenvironment to play out specific functions, such Kupffer cells in the liver, microglial cells in the brain, and mesangial cells in the kidney (*Parisi, et al.,2018*).

The macrophage-derived cytokine production in the gastric mucosa is strongly upregulated during *H. pylori* infection. These adaptive responses are also characterized by increased lymphocyte and macrophage infiltration of infected gastric tissues. Thus, macrophages and DCs within the gastric mucosa may play an important role in *H. pylori*-induced acquired immunity. However, the mechanisms underlying *H. pylori* recognition and its interaction with the gastric mucosa remain unclear (*Kita .,et al 2018*).

The macrophage is probably the most important cell in chronic inflammation because of the great number of biologically active products it can produce. Important classes of products produced and secreted by macrophages include neutral proteases, chemotactic factors, arachidonic acid metabolites, reactive oxygen metabolites, complement components, coagulation factors, growth-promoting factors, cytokines, and acid. Phagolysosomes in macrophages can have acidity as low as pH of 4 and direct microelectrode studies of this acid environment have determined pH levels as low as 3.5. Moreover, only several hours are necessary to achieve these acid levels following adhesion of macrophages (*Anderson and Jiang, 2017*)

Plasma cells

Plasma cells are terminally differentiated B lymphocytes that constitutively secrete antibodies. These antibodies can provide protection against pathogens, and their quantity and quality are the best clinical correlates of vaccine efficacy. As such, plasma cell lifespan is the primary determinant of the duration of humoral immunity. Yet dysregulation of plasma cell function can cause autoimmunity or multiple myeloma. The longevity of plasma cells is primarily dictated by nutrient uptake and non-transcriptionally regulated metabolic pathways (*D'Souza and Bhattacharya et al., 2019*).

The gastrointestinal mucosa contains numerous plasma cells (PCs) under normal condition. Immunocytochemical studies have shown that most of these PCs contain (and presumably produce) immunoglobulin A (IgA). Immunoglobulin G and M (IgG and IgM, respectively) can be detected in a few of these PCs. Tolerance in the intestinal immune system is required to inhibit immunity against commensal bacteria, as well as an array of dietary antigens. The microenvironment regulates PC survival in the small intestine . Additionally, bacterial Toll-like receptor (TLR) ligands induce survival factors of PCs, such as a proliferation-inducing ligand from intestinal epithelial cells , lamina propria dendritic cells (LP-DCs), and mucosal neutrophils . Bacterial exposure induces not only LP-PC survival but also the generation of specific IgA-secreting (IgA+) LP-PCs. Differentiation of B cells into PCs is affected by external and internal factors. Activated B cells can express IL-6 receptors, which can induce the differentiation to PCs. However, IL-6 alone cannot promote the differentiation to PCs. IL-10 also functions to increase PCs. IL-10, originally identified as a TH2 helper T-cell product, can inhibit cytokine production by TH1 cells, but it induces PCs to secrete large amounts of IgG, IgA, and IgM (*Wang., et al ., 2019*).

16-Cellular homeostasis and inflammatory responses

There are 2 groups of immune response, TH1 and TH2, and they can be distinguished from one another by cytokine profiles. TH1 proinflammatory cytokines are interleukin (IL)-2, IL-12, interferon (IFN)- γ , and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α ; TH2 anti-inflammatory cytokines are IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, and transforming growth factor (TGF)- β .⁴ TH1 immunity is important in antitumor activity and TH2 immunity is dominant in advanced carcinomas because the TH1/TH2 ratio is important for an antitumor effect. TH1 immunity is more favorable in anti-tumor immunity than TH2 immunity. In this study, we investigated the cytokines representing TH1 and TH2 immunity, which interact with each other (*Salim et al.2016*).

17-Immune responses to Helicobacter pylori infection

Infection with *H. pylori* reveals an increased infiltration of various types of leukocytes compared to biopsies from uninfected humans. Lymphocytes (T and B cells), monocytes, eosinophils, macrophages, neutrophils, mast cells and dendritic cells are usually present. B cells and CD4⁺ T cells together with dendritic cells (DC) sometimes organize into lymphoid follicles reflecting ongoing antigen presentation and chronic immune responses. *H. pylori*-specific CD4⁺ T cells are detectable in the gastric mucosa and peripheral blood of infected-individuals but not uninfected humans. Levels of cytokines [interferon- γ (IFN- γ), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), IL-1, IL-6, IL-7, IL-8, IL-10, and IL-18] are increased in the stomach of *H. pylori*-infected humans compared to uninfected humans (*Moyat & Velin,2014*).

Materials & Methods

Materials and Method

1) Materials:

The present study carried on 20 healthy individuals and 100 patients infected with H.pylori suffer from gastritis (upper stomach pain). Came to Gamal Abdelnaser general hospital in medicine and endemic medicine departments for treatment from continuous (pyloric burning) heart burning and upon analysis them blood samples for the present of H.pylori Antibodies they are positive, then they are classified according to age into 6 groups.

Control normal group: Control healthy individuals consist of 20- persons with ages ranged from 20 to over 65 years.

Group I: Consisted from 20 diseased patients with age less that 20 years.

Group II: Consisted from 20 diseased patients with age ranged from 20 to 35 years.

Group III: Consisted from 20 diseased patients with age ranged from 35- 50 years.

Group IV: Consisted from 20 diseased patients with age ranged from 50- 65 years.

Group V: Consisted from 20 diseased patients with age ranged more than 65 years.

2) Sample collections:

From each subject five cubic centimeter of venous blood were taken through a vein puncture using a dry plastic disposable syringe poured into clean dry sterile centrifuge tube and allow to coagulate at room temperature then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 r.p.m clean and clear non haemolyzed sera were aspirated carefully by Pasteur pipette and transferred into dry and sterile labeled glass vials. The sera were subjected to estimation of the following parameters: albumin, Total Protein, lactate, pyruvate, Interleukin-2, Interleukin-6, CRP, and

Cortisol, Immunoglobulins (IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE), Complement system (C3 and C4), Autoantibodies (Anti-DNA double-strand and anti-nuclear antibody pattern).

1) Dertemination Stool Helicobacter pylori antigen :

Helicobacter pylori antigen was determined according to the method described by *Cutler et al., (1996)*.

Intended to use:

The ELISA, Helicobacter pylori Antigen is a quantitative assay for the detection of H. pylori antigens in human stool specimen. The test results are intended to aid in the diagnosis of H. pylori infection, to monitor the effectiveness of therapng/mltic treatment and to confirm the eradication of H. pylori in peptic ulcer patients.

Principle

Purified H. pylori antibody is coated on the surface of microwells. An aliquot of diluted stool sample is added to wells, and the H. pylori antigens, if present, bind to the antibody. All unbound materials are washed away. After adding enzyme conjugate, it binds to the antibody-antigen complex. Excess enzyme conjugate is washed off and TMB Chromogenic substrate is added. The enzyme conjugate catalytic reaction is stopped at a specific time. The intensity of the color generated is proportional to the amount of antigen in the sample. The results are read by a microwell reader compared in parallel manner with calibrator and controls.

Preparation for assay:

1. Prepare 1x washing buffer. Prepare washing buffer by adding distilled or deionized water to 20x wash concentrate to a final volume of 1 liter
2. Bring all specimens and kit reagents to room temperature (20-25 °C) and gently mix.

Assay procedure

1. Place the desired number of coated strips into the holder.
2. Dispense 100µl of treated sample, calibrators, and controls into the appropriate wells. Tap the holder to remove air bubbles from the liquid and mix well. Incubate for 30minutes at room temperature.
3. Remove liquid from all wells and repeat washing three times with washing buffer.
4. Dispense 100 µl of enzyme conjugate to each well and incubate for 30 minutes at room temperature.
5. Remove enzyme conjugate from all wells. Repeat washing three times with washing buffer.
6. Dispense 100 µl of TMB Chromogenic Substrate to each well and incubate for 15 minutes at room temperature.
7. Add 100 µl of stop solution to stop reaction.
8. Read O.D at 450 nm with a microwell reader.

Calculation of results

1. Construct a standard curve by plotting O.D. 450 nm on the y-axis against the concentration of calibrator ng/ml values on the X-axis with an order 2 Polynomial trendlines.
2. Using the O.D. value of each specimen, determine the concentration from the standard curve. If sample results are greater than 100 ng/ml (over the range of standard curve), they can be reported as "high positive and greater than 100 ng/ml". To assess accurate results, samples can be further diluted and retested again.

2) Dertemination of Total protein:

Total protein was determined according to the method described by *Weichselbaum et al.,(1946)*.

Test principle (Calorimetric assay)

Divalent copper reacts in alkaline solution with protein peptide bonds to form the characteristic purple-colored biuret complex. Sodium potassium Tartrate prevents the precipitation of copper hydroxide and potassium iodide prevents auto reduction of copper.

The color intensity is directly proportional to the protein concentration which can be determined photometrically.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

$$\text{Conversion factor: } \text{g/L} \times 0.1 = \text{g/dL}$$

3) Dertemination of serum Albumin:

Serum Albumin concentration was determined according to the method described by *Doumas et al.,(1997)*.

Intended use

In vitro test for the quantitative determination of albumin in human serum and plasma on Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems.

Principle (Colorimetric assay)

At a pH value of 4.1, albumin displays a sufficiently cationic character to be able to bind with bromcresol green (BCG), an anionic dye, to form a blue-green complex.

The color intensity of the blue-green color is directly proportional to the Albumin concentration in sample and is measured photometrically.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: g/L x 15.2 μmol/L

4) Determination of lactic acid:

Serum lactate concentration was determined according to the method of *Noll, (1988)*.

Principle:

The quantification of L-lactate requires two enzyme reactions. In the first reaction catalyzed by L-lactate dehydrogenase(L-LDH) ,lactate is oxidized to pyruvate by nicotinamideadenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺)

However, since the equilibrium of reaction(1)lies firmly in the favor of L-lactate and NAD⁺, a further reaction is required to trap the pyruvate product.This is achieved by the conversion of pyruvate to D-alanine and 2-oxoglutarate, with the enzyme, D-glutamate-pyruvate transaminase (D-ALT)in the presence of a large excess of D-glutamate(2).

The amount of NADH formed in the above coupled reaction is stoichiometric with the amount of L-lactate. It is the NADH which is measured by the increase in absorbance at 340nm.

Calculation:

Determine the absorbance difference (A₂-A₁) for both blank and sample. Subtract the absorbance difference of the blank from the absorbance difference of the sample, there by obtaining ΔA_L-lactic acid. The value of ΔA_L -lactic acid should be at least 0.100 absorbance units to achieve sufficiently accurate results.

The concentration of L-lactic acid can be calculated as follows:

$$C = \frac{V \times MW \times \Delta A_{L\text{-lactic acid}}}{\epsilon \times d \times v} \quad [\text{g/L}]$$

Where:

V = final volume [ml]

MW = molecular weight of L-lactic acid [g/mol]

ε = extinction coefficient of NADH at 340 nm

$$= 6300 \text{ [l} \times \text{mol}^{-1} \times \text{cm}^{-1}\text{]}$$

d = light path [ml]

v = sample volume [ml]

It follows for L-lactic acid:

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \frac{2.24 \times 90.1 \times \Delta A_{L\text{-lactic acid}}}{6300 \times 1.0 \times 0.1} \\ &= 0.3204 \times \Delta A_{L\text{-lactic acid}} \quad [\text{g/L}] \end{aligned}$$

If the sample has been diluted during preparation, the result must be multiplied by the dilution factor, F.

5) Determination of serum pyruvic acid:

Serum pyruvate concentration was determined using the method of *Sutherland et al., (1994)*.

Principle:

Pyruvate is a key intermediate in cellular metabolic pathways. Pyruvate can be converted to carbohydrates via gluconeogenesis, to fatty acids or energy through acetyl-CoA, to the amino acid alanine. And to ethanol. Abnormal levels of pyruvate have been linked to liver diseases and metabolic disorders. Simple, direct and automation-ready procedures for measuring pyruvate concentrations find wide applications in research and drug discovery. Pyruvate assay uses a single Working Reagent that combines pyruvate oxidase and hydrogen peroxide determination in one step. The color intensity of the reaction product at 570nm is directly proportional to pyruvate concentration in the sample.

Calculation:

Subtract blank OD (water) from the standard OD values and plot the OD against standard concentrations. Determine the slope using linear regression fitting. The pyruvate concentration of Sample is calculated as

$$\text{OD Sample} - \text{OD H}_2\text{O}$$

$$[\text{Pyruvate}] = \frac{\text{OD Sample} - \text{OD H}_2\text{O}}{\text{Slope}} \quad (\mu\text{M})$$

Where: OD sample and OD H₂O are density values of the sample and water.

Conversions: 1 μM pyruvate equals 8.7 mg/dL or 87 ppm.

6) Determination of interleukin-2

Serum Interleukin -2 level was determined ELIZA according to the manufacturer's instruction.

Intended use

The kit is a sandwich enzyme immunoassay for in vitro quantitative measurement of IL2 in porcine serum, plasma, tissue homogenates, cell lysates, cell culture supernatants and other biological fluids.

Principle

The microplate provided in this kit has been pre-coated with an antibody specific to IL2. Standards or samples are then added to the appropriate microplate wells with a biotin-conjugated antibody specific to IL2. Next, Avidin conjugated to Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) is added to each microplate well and incubated. After TMB substrate solution is added, only those wells that contain IL2, biotin-conjugated antibody and enzyme-conjugated Avidin will exhibit a change in color. The enzyme-substrate reaction is terminated by the addition of sulphuric acid solution and the color change is measured spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of $450\text{nm} \pm 10\text{nm}$. The concentration of IL2 in the samples is then determined by comparing the O.D. of the samples to the standard curve.

Assay procedure summary

1. Prepare all reagents, samples and standards.
2. Add 100 μ L standard or sample to each well. Incubate 1 hour at 37oC;
3. Aspirate and add 100 μ L prepared Detection Reagent A. Incubate 1 hour at 37oC.
4. Aspirate and wash 3 times.
5. Add 100 μ L prepared Detection Reagent B. Incubate 30 minutes at 37oC.
6. Aspirate and wash 5 times.
7. Add 90 μ L Substrate Solution. Incubate 10-20 minutes at 37oC.
8. Add 50 μ L Stop Solution. Read at 450nm immediately.

Calculation of results

Average the duplicate readings for each standard, control, and samples and subtract the average zero standard optical density. Construct a standard curve by plotting the mean O.D. and concentration for each standard and draw a best fit curve through the points on the graph or create a standard curve on log-log graph paper with IL2 concentration on the y-axis and absorbance on the x-axis. Using some plot software, for instance, curve expert 1.30, is also recommended. If samples have been diluted, the concentration read from the standard curve must be multiplied by the dilution factor

Typical Standard Curve for IL2, Porcine ELISA.

7) Determination of interleukin-6

Serum Interleukin -6 level was determined ELIZA according to the manufacturer's instruction.

Intended use

The kit is a sandwich enzyme immunoassay for in vitro quantitative measurement of IL6 in human serum, plasma, tissue homogenates, cell lysates, cell culture supernates and other biological fluids.

Principle

The microplate provided in this kit has been pre-coated with an antibody specific to IL6. Standards or samples are then added to the appropriate microplate wells with a biotin-conjugated antibody specific to IL6. Next, Avidin conjugated to Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) is added to each microplate well and incubated. After TMB substrate solution is added, only those wells that contain IL6, biotin-conjugated antibody and enzyme-conjugated Avidin will exhibit a change in color. The enzyme-substrate reaction is terminated by the addition of sulphuric acid solution and the color change is measured spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of $450\text{nm} \pm 10\text{nm}$. The concentration of IL6 in the samples is then

determined by comparing the O.D. of the samples to the standard curve.

Assay procedure summary

1. Prepare all reagents, samples and standards.
2. Add 100 μ L standard or sample to each well. Incubate 1 hour at 37oC;
3. Aspirate and add 100 μ L prepared Detection Reagent A. Incubate 1 hour at 37oC.
4. Aspirate and wash 3 times.
5. Add 100 μ L prepared Detection Reagent B. Incubate 30 minutes at 37oC.
6. Aspirate and wash 5 times.
7. Add 90 μ L Substrate Solution. Incubate 10-20 minutes at 37oC.
8. Add 50 μ L Stop Solution. Read at 450nm immediately.

Calculation of results

Average the duplicate readings for each standard, control, and samples and subtract the average zero standard optical density. Construct a standard curve by plotting the mean O.D. and concentration for each standard and draw a best fit curve through the points on the graph or create a standard curve on log-log graph paper with IL6 concentration on the y-axis and absorbance on the x-axis. Using some plot software, for instance, curve expert 1.30, is also recommended. If samples have been diluted, the concentration read from the standard curve must be multiplied by the dilution factor.

In order to make the calculation easier, we plot the O.D. value of the standard (X-axis) against the known concentration of the standard (Y-axis), although concentration is the independent variable and O.D. value is the dependent variable. However, the O.D. values of the standard curve may vary according to the conditions of assay performance (e.g. operator, pipetting technique, washing technique or temperature effects), plotting

log of the data to establish standard curve for each test is recommended. Typical standard curve below is provided for reference only.

8) Determination of Complement C3:

Complement C3 was determined according to the method described by **Jacobs (1996)**.

Intended use

The Complement C3 (C3) assay is used for the quantitation of C3 in human serum or plasma.

Test principle (Immunoturbidimetric assay)

Human C3 forms a precipitate with a specific antiserum which is determined turbidimetrically.

Procedure

The C3 assay is an immunoturbidimetric procedure that measures increasing sample turbidity caused by the formation of insoluble immune complexes when antibody to C3 is added to the sample. Sample containing C3 is incubated with a buffer R1 and a sample blank determination is performed prior to the addition of C3 antibody R2. In the presence of an appropriate antibody in excess, the C3 concentration is measured as a function of turbidity.

Reagents -working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer: 100 mmol/L, pH 8.0; polyethylene glycol: 3.0% preservative

R2 Anti-human C3 antibody (goat): dependent on titer; TRIS buffer 33 mmol/L; preservative

R1 is in position B and R2 is in position C.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL}$

$\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L}$

9) Determination of Complement C4 :

Complement C4 was determined according to the method described by **Jacobs (1996)**.

Intended use

The Complement C4 (C4) assay is used for the quantitation of C4 in human serum or plasma.

Principle (Immunoturbidimetric assay)

Human C4 forms a precipitate with a specific antiserum which is determined turbidimetrically.

Reagents -working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer: 100 mmol/L, pH 8.0; polyethylene glycol: 3.0% preservative

R2 Anti-human C4c antibody (goat): dependent on titer; TRIS buffer 33 mmol/L; preservative

R1 is in position B and R2 is in position C.

Procedure

The C4 assay is an immunoturbidimetric procedure that measures increasing sample turbidity caused by the formation of insoluble immune complexes when antibody to C4 is added to the sample. Sample

containing C4 is incubated with a buffer and a sample blank determination is performed prior to the addition of C4 antibody . In the presence of an appropriate antibody in excess, the C4 concentration is measured as a function of turbidity. Methodology: Immunoturbidimetric

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte Concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L}$ $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.050 = \mu\text{mol/L}$
 $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL}$ $\text{g/L} \times 5.00 = \mu\text{mol/L}$

10) Dertemination of IgG :

IgG was determined according to the method described by *Tietz (1995)*.

Intended use:

The Immunoglobulin G (IgG) assay is used for the quantitation of IgG in human serum or plasma.

Principle: (Immunoturbidimetric assay)

Anti-igG antibodies react with antigen in the sample to form an antigen/antibody complex. Following agglutination, this is measured turbidimetrically. Addition of PEG allows the reaction to progress rapidly to the end point, increases sensitivity, and reduces the risk of samples containing excess antigen producing false negative results.

Reagents-working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 200 mmol/L; polyethylene glycol: 3.6 %; preservative; stabilizers

R2 Anti-human IgG antibody (goat): dependent on titer; TRIS buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 150 mmol/L; preservative

R1 is in position B and R2 is in position C.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L}$ $\text{g/L} \times 6.67 = \mu\text{mol/L}$
 $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL}$ $\mu\text{mol} \times 0.15 = \text{g/L}$
 $\text{mg/dL} \times 6.67 = \text{g/L}$ $\text{nmol/L} \times 0.15 = \text{mg/L}$
 $\text{mg/L} \times 0.001 = \text{g/L}$

11) Determination of IgA:

IgA was determined according to the method described by *Tietz (1995)*.

Intended use:

In vitro test for the quantitative determination of IgA in human serum and plasma on Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems.

Principle Immunoturbidimetric assay.

Anti-IgA antibodies react with antigen in the sample to form an antigen/antibody complex. Following agglutination, this is measured turbidimetrically. Addition of PEG allows the reaction to progress rapidly to the end point, increases sensitivity, and reduces the risk of samples containing excess antigen producing false negative results.

Reagents-working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 200 mmol/L;
polyethylene glycol: 3.6 %; preservative; stabilizers

R2 Anti-human IgA antibody (goat): dependent on titer; TRIS

buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 150 mmol/L; preservative

R1 is in position B and R2 is in position C.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L} \times 6.25 = \mu\text{mol/L}$
 $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL} \quad \mu\text{mol} \times 0.16 = \text{g/L}$

12) Determination of IgM :

IgM was determined according to the method described by *Tietz (1995)*.

Intended use:

In vitro test for the quantitative determination of IgG in human serum, plasma, cerebrospinal fluid and urine on Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems.

Principle

Immunoturbidimetric assay.

Anti-IgM antibodies react with antigen in the sample to form an antigen/antibody complex. Following agglutination, this is measured turbidimetrically. Addition of PEG allows the reaction to progress rapidly to the end point, increases sensitivity, and reduces the risk of samples containing excess antigen producing false negative results.

Reagents-working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 200 mmol/L;
 polyethylene glycol: 3.6 %; preservative; stabilizers

R2 Anti-human IgM antibody (goat): dependent on titer; TRIS
 buffer: 20 mmol/L, pH 8.0; NaCl: 150 mmol/L; preservative

R1 is in position B and R2 is in position C.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L} \times 1.03 = \mu\text{mol/L}$
 $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL} \quad \mu\text{mol} \times 0.971 = \text{g/L}$

13) Determination of IgE:

IgE was determined according to the method described by *Homburger et al., (1991)*.

Intended use

Immunoassay for the in vitro quantitative determination of immunoglobulin E in human serum and plasma.

Determination of total IgE is useful as an aid in the diagnosis of allergic diseases.

The electrochemiluminescence immunoassay "ECLIA" is intended for use on Elecsys and cobas e immunoassay analyzers.

Test principle

Sandwich principle. Total duration of assay: 18 minutes.

- 1st incubation: IgE in the sample (10 pL), a biotinylated monoclonal IgE-specific antibody, and a monoclonal IgE-specific antibody labeled with a ruthenium complex form a sandwich complex.
- 2nd incubation: After addition of streptavidin-coated microparticles, the complex becomes bound to the solid phase via interaction of biotin and streptavidin.
- The reaction mixture is aspirated into the measuring cell where the microparticles are magnetically captured onto the surface of the electrode. Unbound substances are then removed with ProCell/ProCell M. Application of a voltage to the electrode then induces chemiluminescent emission which is measured by a photomultiplier.

Anti dsDNA IgG kit is an indirect solid phase enzyme immunometric assay (ELISA) designed for the quantitative measurement of IgG class antibodies directed against dsDNA in human serum or plasma. Anti dsDNA IgG is intended for laboratory use only.

Principle

Anti DSDNA IgG test is based on the binding of serum or plasma IgG antibodies on dsDNA coated on the microplates. In the first step the antibodies in calibrators, controls or prediluted patient samples bind into the inner surface of the wells. After an incubation the microplate is washed with a wash buffer for removing non-reactive serum components. In the second step an anti human IgG horseradish peroxidase conjugated solution recognizes the IgG class antibodies bound to the immobilized dsDNA antigens. After an incubation any excess of enzyme conjugate, which is not specifically bound, is washed away with the wash buffer. Then a chromogenic substrate solution containing TMB is dispensed into the wells. After 15 minutes of incubation the color development is stopped by adding the stop solution. The solution color changes into yellow. The amount of color is directly proportional to the concentration of the Anti dsDNA IgG antibodies present in the original sample.

The concentration of the anti dsDNA IgG antibodies in the sample are calculated through a calibration curve.

Procedure

- Preparation of the Calibrators (C₀-C₄)
- Calibration curve is ready to use and is calibrated against International Standard WHO Wo/80. The Calibrators have approximately the following concentration:

	C ₀	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
IU/ml	0	12.5	25	50	200

Preparation of the Sample

For determination of anti dsDNA antibodies, human serum or plasma are the preferred sample matrixes.

All serum and plasma samples have to be prediluted with sample diluent 1:100; for example 10 uL of sample may be diluted with 990 uL of sample diluent.

The patients need not to be fasting, and no special preparations are venipuncture into vacutainers and separate serum (after clot formation) or plasma from the cells by centrifugation.

Neither Bilirubin nor Hemolysis have significant effect on the procedure.

-Procedure

.Allow all reagents to reach room temperature (22-28°C) for at least 30 minutes. At the end of the assay, store immediately the reagents at 2-8°C: avoid long exposure to room temperature.

.Unused coated microwell strips should be released securely in the foil pouch containing desiccant and stored at 2-8°C.

.To avoid potential microbial and/or chemical contamination, unused reagents should never be transferred into the original vials .

.As it is necessary to perform the determination in duplicate in order to improve accuracy of the test results, prepare two wells for each point of thecalibration curve (Co-C4), two for each Control, two for each sample, one for Blank.

Result

- Calibration curve

For the test Anti dsDNA IgG a 4-Parameter-Fit with lin-log coordinates for optical density and concentration is the data reduction method of choice. Smoothed-Spline approximation and log-log coordinates are also suitable. However we reccomen using a Lin-Log curve.

First calculate the averaged optical densities for each calibrator well. Use lin-log graph paper and plot the averaged optical density of each calibrator versus the concentration. Draw the best fitting curve approximating the path of all calibrator points. The calibrator points may also be connected with straight line segments. The concentration of unknowns may then be estimated from the calibration curve by interpolation.

15) Determination ANA :

Serum ANA was determined by using immunoturbidimetric assay according to the method described by *Homburger et al. (1998)*

Intended use

ANA Screen kit is an indirect solid phase enzyme immunometric assay (ELISA) designed for semi-quantitative measurement of IgG antibodies directed against Sm (Smith), RNP/Sm, Scl-70, SS-A (Ro) (52kDa e 60kDa), SS-B (La), Jo1, U1-Sm RNP, CENP-B, dsDNA, and Histones in human serum or plasma.

Principle

ANA Screen test is based on the binding of present antibodies with Sm, RNP/Sm, SS-A (Ro), SS-B (La), Scl-70, Jo 1, U1-SmRNP, CENP-B, dsDNA and Histones antigens coated on the microplates. Any present antibodies in calibrators, controls or prediluted patient samples bind to the inner surface of the wells. After a 30 minutes incubation the microplate is washed with wash buffer for removing non-reactive serum components.

An anti-human-IgG horseradish peroxidase conjugate solution recognizes IgG class antibodies bound to the immobilized antigens. After a 30 minutes incubation any excess enzyme conjugate, which is not specifically bound is washed away with wash buffer.

A chromogenic substrate solution containing TMB is dispensed into the wells. After 15 minutes of incubation the color development is stopped by adding the stop solution. The solution turns yellow at this point. The level of colour is directly proportional to the concentration of IgG antibodies present in the original sample.

Calculation

First of all determine the average of the absorbances for every duplicate. To obtain sample value, divide the absorbance of the sample by the absorbance of the Calibrator, then multiply for the concentration of the Calibrator, as shown below:

$$\text{Sample .Conc} = \frac{\text{O.D.sam}}{\text{O.D.Cl}} \times \text{Conc.Cl}$$

Reactivity is not connected in a linear way to the amount of antibodies present. Although an increase or a decrease in the concentration of antibodies results in increased or decreased responsiveness, the change is not in proportion (eg doubling the concentration of antibodies does not lead to a doubling of responsiveness).

16) Determination C-reactive protein :

Serum C-reactive protein level was determined by using immunoturbidimetric assay according to the method described by *Senju et al. (1983)*

Principle

Particle enhanced immunoturbidimetric assay.

Human CRP agglutinates with latex particles coated with monoclonal anti-CRP antibodies. The precipitate is determined turbidimetrically.

Reagents-working solutions

R1 TRIS buffer with bovine serum albumin and immunoglobulins (mouse) preservative.

R2 Latex particles coated with anti-CRP (mouse) in glycine buffer Preservative.

R1 is in position B, and R2 is in position C.

Calculation

Roche/Hitachi cobas c systems automatically calculate the analyte concentration of each sample.

Conversion factors: $\text{mg/L} \times 9.52 = \text{nmol/L}$ $\text{mg/dL} \times 95.2 = \text{nmol/L}$
 $\text{mg/L} \times 0.1 = \text{mg/dL}$ $\text{mg/dL} \times 10 = \text{mg/L}$
 $\text{mg/dL} \times 0.01 = \text{g/L}$ $\text{g/L} \times 100 = \text{mg/dL}$

17) Determination of Serum Cortisol:

Serum cortisol level was determined by using immune-radiometric according to the method described by *Siekman, (1982)*

Intended use

Immunoassay for the in vitro quantitative determination of cortisol in human serum, plasma, urine, and saliva. The determination of cortisol is used for the recognition and treatment of functional disorders of the adrenal gland.

The electrochemiluminescence immunoassay "ECLIA" is intended for use on Elecsys and cobas e immunoassay analyzers.

principle

Competition principle. Total duration of assay: 18 minutes.

- 1st incubation: 20 μL of sample is incubated with a cortisol-specific biotinylated antibody and a ruthenium complex labeled

cortisol derivative. Depending on the concentration of the analyte in the sample and the formation of the respective immune complex, the labeled antibody binding site is occupied in part with sample analyte and in part with ruthenylated hapten.

- 2nd incubation: After addition of streptavidin-coated microparticles, the complex becomes bound to the solid phase via interaction of biotin and streptavidin.
- The reaction mixture is aspirated into the measuring cell where the microparticles are magnetically captured onto the surface of the electrode. Unbound substances are then removed with ProCell/ProCell M. Application of a voltage to the electrode then induces chemiluminescent emission which is measured by a photomultiplier.
- Results are determined via a calibration curve which is instrument-specifically generated by 2-point calibration and a master curve provided via the reagent barcode.

Reagents

The reagent rackpack is labeled as CORT.

- M Streptavidin-coated microparticles (transparent cap), 1 bottle, 6.5 mL: Streptavidin-coated microparticles 0.72 mg/mL; preservative.
- R1 Anti-cortisol-Ab-biotin (gray cap), 1 bottle, 9 mL: Biotinylated polyclonal anti-cortisol antibody (ovine) 90 ng/mL; MESb) buffer 100 mmol/L, pH 6.0; preservative.
- R2 Cortisol-peptide-Ru(bpy)₂+₃ (black cap), 1 bottle, 9 mL: Cortisol derivative (synthetic), labeled with ruthenium complex 25 ng/mL; danazol 20 µg/mL; MES buffer 100 mmol/L, pH 6.0; preservative

b) MES = 2-morpholino-ethane sulfonic acid

Calculation

The analyzer automatically calculates the analyte concentration of each sample (either in nmol/L, µg/dL or µg/L).

Conversion factors: nmol/L x 0.03625 = µg/dL
 nmol/L x 0.3625 =µg/L
 µg/dL x 27.586 = nmol/L
 µg/L x 2.7586 = nmol/L

Manual calculation for urinary free cortisol: cortisol excretion over 24-hours (cortisol concentration/24 h):

Multiply the analyzer results by the volume of the 24-hour urine (L/24 h) (when the analyzer result is given in pg/dL, multiply again by 10 = µg/24 h).The average yield of extraction (n = 25) was determined to be 94 %.

Statistical Analysis

The results were expressed as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM). Data were statistically analyzed by One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.0 for Windows, GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA. Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

RESULTS

The biochemical effects of helicobacter pylori infection on immuno-stress biomarkers of patients at different ages in comparison with control normal group were assessed by measuring the next biochemical parameters:

1. Stool H. Pylori antigen.
2. Serum albumin and total protein concentrations.
3. Serum lactate and pyruvate concentrations.
4. Serum IL-2 and IL-6 concentrations.
5. Serum C3 and C4 concentrations.
6. Serum IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE concentrations.
7. Anti-DNA double strand concentration.
8. Anti-nuclear antibody pattern.
9. CRP concentration.
10. Cortisol concentration.

The results were statistically analyzed and represented in (17) tables and (17) figures, as following:

1) Stool H. Pylori Antigenconcentration:

The concentration of stool H. Pylori antigen in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table I) and graphically illustrated in (Figure I).

The obtained data in table (I) and figure (I) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of stool H. Pylori antigen concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at age less than 20 years old.

Table (I):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on stool H. Pylori antigen concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Stool H. Pylori antigen
	Values (ng/ml)
Control normal group	33.68 ± 2.85 ^c
Patients less than 20 years old.	60.95 ± 2.83 ^b
Patients at 20-35 years old.	70.55 ± 3.61 ^{ab}
Patients at 35-50 years old.	71.37 ± 4.28 ^{ab}
Patients at 50-65 years old.	74.90 ± 5.24 ^a
Patients more than 65 years old.	76.42 ± 3.75 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (I):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on stool H. Pylori antigen concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

2) Serum total protein concentration:

The concentration of serum total protein in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table II) and graphically illustrated in (Figure II).

The obtained data in table (II) and figure (II) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum total protein concentration in the infected human groups showed a non significant decrease at age less than 20 years old, while showed a significant decrease at the elder ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant decrease was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant decrease was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (II):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum total protein concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum Total protein
	Values (g/dl)
Control normal group	7.73 ± 0.26 ^a
Patients less than 20 years old.	7.06 ± 0.38 ^a
Patients at 20-35 years old.	7.12 ± 0.34 ^a
Patients at 35-50 years old.	6.98 ± 0.43 ^{ab}
Patients at 50-65 years old.	6.37 ± 0.32 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	5.85 ± 0.32 ^c

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (II):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum total protein concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

3) Serum albumin concentration:

The concentration of serum albumin in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table III) and graphically illustrated in (Figure III).

The obtained data in table (III) and figure (III) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum albumin concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant decrease at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant decrease was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant decrease was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (III):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum albumin concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum albumin
	Values (g/dl)
Control normal group	4.61 ± 0.29 ^a
Patients less than 20 years old.	4.29 ± 0.21 ^b
Patients at 20-35 years old.	3.77 ± 0.27 ^c
Patients at 35-50 years old.	3.85 ± 0.22 ^c
Patients at 50-65 years old.	3.91 ± 0.16 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	3.33 ± 0.20 ^d

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (III):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum albumin concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

4) Serum lactate concentration:

The concentration of serum lactate in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table IV) and graphically illustrated in (Figure IV).

The obtained data in table (IV) and figure (IV) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum lactate concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (IV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum lactate concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum lactate
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	12.46 ± 0.39 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	16.35 ± 1.07 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	19.46 ± 0.69 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	19.98 ± 1.06 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	21.41 ± 1.33 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	29.02 ± 0.56 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (IV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum lactate concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

5) Serum pyruvate concentration:

The concentration of serum pyruvate in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table V) and graphically illustrated in (Figure V).

The obtained data in table (V) and figure (V) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum pyruvate concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at 20-35 years old.

Table (V):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum pyruvate concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum pyruvate
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	40.68 ± 1.28 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	44.80 ± 1.69 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	42.97 ± 2.70 ^c
Patients at 35-50 years old.	49.42 ± 2.24 ^c
Patients at 50-65 years old.	54.94 ± 3.82 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	65.18 ± 2.35 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (V):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum pyruvate concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

6) Serum IL-2 concentration:

The concentration of serum IL-2 in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table VI) and graphically illustrated in (Figure VI).

The obtained data in table (VI) and figure (VI) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum IL-2 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (VI):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum IL-2 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum IL-2
	Values (pg/ml)
Control normal group	0.53 ± 0.22 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	0.96 ± 0.18 ^d
Patients at 20-35 years old.	3.83 ± 0.26 ^a
Patients at 35-50 years old.	2.61 ± 0.19 ^c
Patients at 50-65 years old.	3.22 ± 0.28 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	4.19 ± 0.25 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (VI):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum IL-2 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

7) Serum IL-6 concentration:

The concentration of serum IL-6 in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table VII) and graphically illustrated in (Figure VII).

The obtained data in table (VII) and figure (VII) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum IL-6 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (VII):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum IL-6 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum IL-6
	Values (pg/ml)
Control normal group	7.83 ± 0.49 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	10.72 ± 0.93 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	16.73 ± 1.18 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	14.37 ± 1.19 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	22.07 ± 1.44 ^a
Patients more than 65 years old.	23.72 ± 1.79 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (VII):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum IL-6 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

8) Serum C3 concentration:

The concentration of serum C3 in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table VIII) and graphically illustrated in (Figure VIII).

The obtained data in table (VIII) and figure (VIII) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum C3 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age of 35-50 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at 50-65 years old.

Table (VIII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum C3 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum C3
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	140.16 ± 6.98 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	191.70 ± 13.74 ^b
Patients at 20-35 years old.	196.55 ± 10.69 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	228.21 ± 11.75 ^a
Patients at 50-65 years old.	164.30 ± 8.45 ^c
Patients more than 65 years old.	178.35 ± 10.24 ^c

☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).

☞ S.E = Standard error.

☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (VIII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum C3 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

9) Serum C4 concentration:

The concentration of serum C4 in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table IX) and graphically illustrated in (Figure IX).

The obtained data in table (IX) and figure (IX) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum C4 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age of 35-50 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

Table (IX):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum C4 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum C4
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	24.68 ± 4.03 ^e
Patients less than 20 years old.	43.71 ± 5.87 ^{cd}
Patients at 20-35 years old.	66.54 ± 5.46 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	77.97 ± 6.19 ^a
Patients at 50-65 years old.	52.44 ± 4.63 ^c
Patients more than 65 years old.	34.61 ± 3.14 ^d

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (IX):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum C4 concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

10) Serum *Ig-G* concentration:

The concentration of serum *Ig-G* in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table X) and graphically illustrated in (Figure X).

The obtained data in table (X) and figure (X) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum *Ig-G* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

Table (X):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-G* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum <i>Ig-G</i>
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	821.25 ± 36.96 ^f
Patients less than 20 years old.	1813.23 ± 78.56 ^a
Patients at 20-35 years old.	1209.16 ± 56.90 ^d
Patients at 35-50 years old.	1616.64 ± 55.97 ^c
Patients at 50-65 years old.	1771.20 ± 50.39 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	988.86 ± 41.70 ^e

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (X):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-G* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

11) Serum *Ig-A* concentration:

The concentration of serum *Ig-A* in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XI) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XI).

The obtained data in table (XI) and figure (XI) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum *Ig-A* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at 20-35 years old.

Table (XI):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-A* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum <i>Ig-A</i>
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	330.22 ± 16.91 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	585.99 ± 24.45 ^a
Patients at 20-35 years old.	369.60 ± 18.17 ^c
Patients at 35-50 years old.	456.24 ± 20.12 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	431.75 ± 21.25 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	406.60 ± 16.55 ^b

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XI):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-A* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

12) Serum *Ig-E* concentration:

The concentration of serum *Ig-E* in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XII) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XII).

The obtained data in table (XII) and figure (XII) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum *Ig-E* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at age less than 20 years old.

Table (XII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-E* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum <i>IgE</i>
	Values (U/ml)
Control normal group	55.68 ± 3.85 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	117.02 ± 3.57 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	131.41 ± 4.31 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	139.20 ± 4.09 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	130.00 ± 3.95 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	154.34 ± 4.20 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-E* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

13) Serum *Ig-M* concentration:

The concentration of serum *Ig-M* in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XIII) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XIII).

The obtained data in table (XIII) and figure (XIII) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum *Ig-M* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

Table (XIII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-M* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum <i>IgM</i>
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	117.26 ± 3.83 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	159.25 ± 4.15 ^a
Patients at 20-35 years old.	137.61 ± 3.18 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	140.49 ± 3.65 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	145.99 ± 3.24 ^{ab}
Patients more than 65 years old.	129.80 ± 2.91 ^{cd}

☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).

☞ S.E = Standard error.

☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XIII):

The effect of *H. Pylori* infection on serum *Ig-E* concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

14) Serum Anti-DNA double stranded:

The concentration of serum Anti-DNA double stranded in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XIV) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XIV).

The obtained data in table (XIV) and figure (XIV) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum Anti-DNA double stranded concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (XIV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum Anti-DNA double stranded concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum Anti-DNA (ds)
	Values (U/ml)
Control normal group	20.18 ± 1.89 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	31.03 ± 1.53 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	38.15 ± 0.90 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	37.69 ± 0.88 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	37.12 ± 1.16 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	43.25 ± 2.45 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XIV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum Anti-DNA double stranded concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

15) Serum ANA pattern:

Serum ANA pattern in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XV) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XV).

The obtained data in table (XV) and figure (XV) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum ANA pattern in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (XV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum ANA pattern in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum ANA pattern
	Values
Control normal group	1.14 ± 0.15 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	2.56 ± 0.22 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	2.70 ± 0.26 ^c
Patients at 35-50 years old.	3.48 ± 0.23 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	3.86 ± 0.21 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	4.71 ± 0.16 ^a

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XV):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum ANA pattern in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

16) Serum cortisol concentration:

The concentration of serum cortisol in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table 16) and graphically illustrated in (Figure 16).

The obtained data in table (XVI) and figure (XVI) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum cortisol concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at age more than 65 years old.

Table (XVI):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum cortisol concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum Cortisol
	Values (µg/dl)
Control normal group	13.70 ± 1.33 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	44.78 ± 2.54 ^a
Patients at 20-35 years old.	29.75 ± 3.02 ^b
Patients at 35-50 years old.	33.19 ± 3.14 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	43.24 ± 1.75 ^a
Patients more than 65 years old.	20.70 ± 1.49 ^c

- ☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).
- ☞ S.E = Standard error.
- ☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XVI):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum cortisol concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

17) Serum CRP concentration:

The concentration of serum CRP in control normal and the infected human groups, at different ages is presented in (Table XVII) and graphically illustrated in (Figure XVII).

The obtained data in table (XVII) and figure (XVII) showed that:

- 1) The mean values of serum CRP concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.
- 2) The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients between 20-35 years old.

Table (XVII):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum CRP concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Groups	Serum CRP
	Values (mg/dl)
Control normal group	2.13 ± 0.29 ^d
Patients less than 20 years old.	3.85 ± 0.31 ^c
Patients at 20-35 years old.	3.54 ± 0.37 ^c
Patients at 35-50 years old.	4.29 ± 0.40 ^b
Patients at 50-65 years old.	4.68 ± 0.33 ^b
Patients more than 65 years old.	6.14 ± 0.42 ^a

☞ Data are presented as (Mean ± S.E).

☞ S.E = Standard error.

☞ Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different at (P<0.05).

Figure (XVII):

The effect of H. Pylori infection on serum CRP concentration in infected human groups at different ages in comparison with control normal group.

Discussion

Discussion

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) prevalence rates in adult populations vary from 35 to 90%, depending on the detection method used (serology, urea breath test, stool antigen detection test or invasive methods) and socioeconomic development status of the evaluated population. *H. pylori* is epidemiologically relevant due to its causative role in peptic ulcer disease, gastric lymphoma and adenocarcinoma in adults. Annually, nearly one million new cases of gastric cancer (GC) and 738,000 cancer-associated deaths occur worldwide and *H. pylori* is estimated to cause 89% of all GC cases. *H. pylori* associated carcinogenesis occurs by both indirect and direct mechanisms. The former are mediated by chronic inflammation, leading to increased cell turnover resulting in an accumulation of mitotic errors and by regulatory T cell induction leading to immune response evasion. Direct mechanisms are mediated by bacterial factors which affect specific molecular targets on the gastric epithelial cells, resulting in DNA damage (*George et al., 2020*).

Inflammation is the body's innate response to injury or insult, including infection, trauma, surgery, burns, and cancer. Certain proteins are released into the bloodstream during inflammation; if their concentrations increase or decrease by at least 25%, they can be used as systemic inflammatory markers. Although there are many inflammatory markers, also known as acute phase reactants (*Schuetz et al., 2019*).

Those most commonly measured in clinical practice (and discussed in this study) are Total Protein, Albumin, Interleukin-2 (IL-2), Interleukin-6 (IL-6) and, C-reactive protein (CRP), cortisol, Complement C3, and C4,

Immunoglobulins (IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE), Antinuclear antibody pattern and Anti-DNA double strand concentration.

1-Inflammation marker

1-1-Total protein and albumin

The presented data in tables (2 and 3) Fig.(2,3) show a significant decrease in serum total protein and serum albumin at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant decrease was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant decrease in serum total protein was seen in patients at 35-50 years old and the The lowest significant decrease in serum total protein was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Mean values of serum total protein concentration in the infected human groups showed a non-significant increase at age less than 20 years old, while showed a significant decrease at the elder ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group while the mean values of serum albumin concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant decrease at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

Our results showed a significant decrease in serum albumin and serum total protein these results are nearly similar to those reported by *Jalalzadeh et al.(2010)* who revealed markedly decreased total serum protein and decreased serum albumin. *Furuta et al.(2002)* also found that the incidence of hypoproteinaemia was significantly higher in H. Pylori positive subjects than in H. Pylori negative subjects and was significantly decreased after the eradication of H. pylori assumed that impaired acid secretion by H. pylori infection might be involved, because the median

gastric juice pH of patients with hypoproteinaemia was much higher (4.80) than that of the group with normal protein levels.

While *Madisch et al., (2004)* concluded that *H. pylori* associated hyper-trophic lymphocytic gastritis has to be considered as a rare cause of protein-losing gastropathy. In these cases, gastrointestinal protein loss may completely resolve solely by *H. pylori* eradication. The significant decrease in serum albumin may be due to impaired liver function by helicobacter pylori endotoxin also The Evidence has shown an association of Helicobacter pylori infection with liver dysfunction (*Salehi, et al 2014*)

Also, *Yoshioka et al., 2019* found that hypoproteinemia and clinical symptoms promptly resolved after *H. pylori* eradication, thus confirming that protein-losing gastroenteropathy (PLGE) was caused by *H. pylori* infection. This study speculates the following mechanism by which *H. pylori* infection causes PLGE. Normally, albumin that leaks from plasma into the interstitial space of the intestinal mucosa is removed by lymphatics and returned to the venous blood. Further, the epithelial cells serve as a diffusion barrier between the interstitial space and the lumen. Thus, the mechanism responsible for PLGE can be divided into three categories. First, in case of increased capillary endothelial permeability, such as with autoimmune diseases, the amount of protein in the interstitial space exceeds the drainage ability of the lymphatic system, allowing protein loss into the lumen. Second, in patients with increased lymphatic pressure, the lymphatics rupture into the intestinal lumen, allowing decompression and retrograde drainage of systemic lymph. Third, in patients with mucosal erosion or ulcers, there is a breakdown of the mucosal barrier, allowing free passage of interstitial protein into the intestine. Even if the mucosa grossly

appears intact and there is no obvious break in the diffusion barrier, proteins can leak despite the absence of increased capillary endothelial permeability or increased lymphatic pressure. In such cases, defects in the tight junction of gastric epithelium are assumed to be the responsible etiological mechanism (*Yoshioka, et al., 2019*)

The highest significant decrease in serum total protein and serum albumin was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old may be due to effect of helicobacter pylori on gastro-duodenal inflammation, ulcerative lesions .

The same results were obtained by *Maruyama et al., 2017* demonstrates that elderly patients gained weight after *H. pylori* eradication. This result was inconsistent with the general tendency towards bodyweight loss in the elderly population and suggested that the effect of *H. pylori* eradication on preventing body weight loss or increase. The mechanisms might include, improvement of gastro-duodenal inflammation, ulcerative lesions, *etc.*, as well as decrease of serum level of leptin which plays a crucial role to regulate food intake and energy expenditure. Thus, we infer that *H. pylori* eradication therapy for elderly patients with *H. pylori*-infected chronic gastritis may be an effective therapy for the prevention of weight loss in elderly individuals.

1-2- Interleukin-2 (IL-2)

There are 2 groups of immune response, Th1 and Th2, and they can be distinguished from one another by cytokine profiles. Th1 proinflammatory cytokines are interleukin (**IL**)-2, IL-12, interferon (IFN)- γ , and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α ; Th2 anti-inflammatory cytokines are IL-4, **IL**-6, IL-10, and transforming growth factor (TGF)- β . Th1 immunity

is important in antitumor activity and Th2 immunity is dominant in advanced carcinomas because the Th1/Th2 ratio is important for an antitumor effect. Th1 immunity is more favorable in anti-tumor immunity than Th2 immunity (*Salim et al., 2016*). In this study, we investigated the cytokines representing Th1 (IL-2) and Th2 (IL-6) immunity, which interact with each other.

The data presented in table (VI) Fig (VI). revealed that the mean values of serum (IL-2) concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum (IL-2) was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum (IL-2) was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

A cellular inflammatory infiltrate of the lamina propria, comprising polymorphonuclear leukocytes and mononuclear cells, is present in the gastric mucosa after Hp colonization, and an increased cytokine synthesis is thought to play a crucial role in the pathogenesis of this type of gastritis (*Basso et al., 1996*).

We found that Hp-infected patients had significantly higher level of serum interleukin-2 (IL-2) than uninfected patients. Our findings for IL-2 are in agreement with those reported by *Hussey and Jones , 2011* showing that H. pylori infection enhanced levels of serum IL-2.

Also, *Melchhiades et al., (2017)* reported that (H. pylori) is a gram-negative bacterium that colonizes the gastric mucosa and induces the production of IL-2. This process increases the magnitude of inflammation and may influence the development of gastric pathologies

While there were other studies disagree with our results such as *Sundrud et al., (2004)* showing that CD4 T cells are critical for protection against *H. pylori* infection. Thus, it seems possible that immune evasion strategies of *H. pylori* may involve the inhibition or modulation of T cell immunity. Indeed, two reports have recently demonstrated that VacA inhibits activation of Jurkat T cells (a human T cell lymphomaleukemia cell line) as well as human peripheral blood lymphocytes, indicates that the secreted *Helicobacter pylori* vacuolating toxin (VacA) inhibits the activation of T cells. VacA blocks IL-2 secretion in transformed T cell lines by suppressing the activation of nuclear factor of activated T cells (NFAT).

1-3- Interleukin-6 (IL-6) and C-Reactive protein (CRP)

The presented data in tables (VII , XVII) Figures (VII , XVII) illustrate that The mean values of serum CRP and IL-6 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in them was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

In the present study we examined the association between *H.pylori* infection and serum CRP levels. This significant was came in accordance with the results of *Al-Fawaeir and Zaid 2013* The results of this study showed that mean serum concentrations of CRP in *H. pylori*-infected were higher than in a healthy control group.

IL-6 is a multifunctional cytokine produced by many types of cells. Inflammation plays a key role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis that is an underlying cause of coronary heart disease (CHD). CRP is the major

acute-phase reactant in humans, which is derived mainly from hepatocytes in response to IL-6. In addition, some epidemiological investigations have shown a direct association between circulating IL-6 levels and risk or severity of CHD. Our findings suggest that a strong immune response to *H. pylori* enhanced the systemic inflammation, which was reflected in an increased level of serum IL-6 and serum CRP. With regard to the biological mechanisms for this finding, previous studies have shown that a chronic low grade inflammatory process leading to atherosclerosis could be one possible mechanism involved in the onset of *H. pylori*-induced ischemic heart disease (*Nakagawa et al .,2013*).

CRP levels are known to increase dramatically in response to injury, infection, and inflammation. CRP is mainly classed as an acute marker of inflammation, but research is starting to indicate important roles that CRP plays in inflammation. CRP is the principal downstream mediator of the acute-phase response following an inflammatory event and is primarily synthesized by IL-6 dependent hepatic biosynthesis (*Sproston and Ashworth 2018*).

While *Andreolla et al. 2016* found no association between CRP serum levels in *H.pylori* infected patients with functional dyspepsia, independently of CagA status; For example, a strong study conducted by *Brenner et al., 1999* involving more than 1.800 healthy subjects did not prove the relation between *H. pylori*, bacterial virulence and inflammation markers. Although it was observed an inverse relation between *H. pylori* infection and serum albumin (In our result we also found this inverse relationship between helicobacter pylori and albumin but we found association between CRP level and helicobacter pylori infection),

Andreolla et al. 2016 found that the bacteria presence was unrelated to C-reactive protein and the leukocyte count, regardless of CagA status. Such result was also reported in several studies that showed no impact of *H. pylori*'s infection in systemic markers of inflammation.

Our results came in agreement with *Waluga et al., 2015* they illustrated that *Helicobacter Pylori* infection increase IL-6 level because the Inflammation marker is synthesized in the liver, and as we will see here that *h.pylori* affect liver and consequently it will affect all inflammation marker produced by the liver. *H. pylori* may lead to liver injury via specific toxins. Also, invasion of *H. pylori* in the small bowel mucosa might increase gut permeability and facilitate the passage of bacterial endotoxins via the portal vein to the liver. *H. pylori* infection causes chronic gastritis and induces a permanent inflammatory response that may increase both the gastric and the systemic indexes of inflammation, such as TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6.

CRP is produced by the hepatocytes in the liver, and as such could potentially be affected by chronic liver disease. Chronic inflammation is thought to be a key mediator of liver cancer, leading to fibrosis and cirrhosis and eventually liver cancer. Consistent with this mechanism, recent data from the NIH-AARP cohort suggest the regular use of aspirin may reduce liver cancer risk. C-reactive protein (CRP) is an acute-phase protein that is mainly produced by hepatocytes as part of an inflammatory response. In addition to serving as a marker of systemic inflammation, CRP plays an important role in the inflammatory process where it is involved in opsonization and activation of the complement system in response to IL-6 secretion. High serum levels of CRP have been associated with the

incidence of colorectal and other cancers. Among patients with cancer, CRP has also been implicated as a prognostic marker in cancers of the ovary, esophagus, stomach, and colorectum (*Chen et al., 2015*).

Both *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection and liver diseases, including nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), viral hepatitis, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), have high prevalences worldwide, and the relationship between *H. pylori* infection and liver disease has been discussed for many years. Although positive correlations between *H. pylori* and NAFLD have been identified in some clinical and experimental studies, negative correlations have also been obtained in high-quality clinical studies. Associations between *H. pylori* and the pathogenesis of chronic viral hepatitis, mainly disease progression with fibrosis, have also been suggested in some clinical studies. Concerning HCC, a possible role for *H. pylori* in hepatocarcinogenesis has been identified since *H. pylori* genes have frequently been detected in resected HCC specimens. However, no study has revealed the direct involvement of *H. pylori* in promoting the development of HCC (*Okushin et al., 2018*).

2-Immune stress biomarker

H. pylori induce IL-6 secretion which in response leads to increase CRP level which involves in opsonization and activation the complement system .As well as *H. pylori* infection associated with an increased in immune stress marker as the complement system, Anti-ds DNA, ANA and immunoglobulin IgM, IgG ,IgA and IgE, which are associated with autoimmune diseases. Also, this infection associated with increased serum Cortisol level. *H. pylori* is probably responsible for immune system disturbance and autoimmune disorder.

2-1- Complement system

The host immune response is an important determinant of the outcome of the infection, but the mechanisms by which the immune response can eradicate gastric *Helicobacter* infection are unknown. Emerging data have indicated that *H. pylori* has multiple mechanisms to both evade and manipulate the immune response. The complement system (C) plays an important defensive role within human body. The role of C is involved in both innate (natural, non-specific) and acquired (specific) immunity. While Complement component C4 plays a central role in classical and lectin pathways of complement. C3 is a key protein of the complement system, activation of C3 results in a variety of immunologic reactions such as immune adherence, phagocytosis, antibody response, cytolysis, inflammation, and killing of pathogenic microorganisms. Several lines of evidence suggest that the complement system may have a role in *H. pylori*-induced gastritis, *H. pylori* can activate complement in vitro (*Shaldoum & Gobaara, 2018*).

The presented data in tables (VIII and IX) figures (VIII and IX) shown that the mean values of serum C3 and C4 concentration in the infected human groups is significantly increased at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum C3 and C4 was noticed in patients at the age of 35-50 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum C3 was seen in patients at 50-65 years old. And the lowest significant increase in serum C4 was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

These results following the results of *Shaldoum et al (2012)* showing that Activation of C4 is frequently found to be a more sensitive

measure of the classical pathway of activation due to bacteria activate complement system through the delayed inducement of antibody to the immune system. Also, this variation in results may be because of Age and Sex-Associated Changes of Complement Activity and Complement Levels.

The complement system has important roles in the initiation and control of inflammation, but the extent to which complement activation contributes to the immunopathogenesis of *Helicobacter pylori* gastritis has received little attention. The complement system includes several proenzymes and other components that exist in a non-active state in blood plasma (and serum). Opsonization with products of activated complement makes internalization and destruction of *H. pylori* by phagocytes more efficient in vitro. *H. pylori* is complement sensitive and activates the classic pathway even in the absence of specific antibodies. Released cell wall constituents such as lipopolysaccharide (LPSs) can activate complement and may explain why this bacterium induces gastric pathology without invading the mucosa (*Berstad et al.,2001*).

Several lines of evidence have suggested a role for complement in the immune-inflammatory response to gastric *Helicobacter* infection. The complement system is a key mediator of the immune response to multiple extracellular organisms. Moreover, evidence of complement activation has been demonstrated in gastric biopsies from individuals infected with *H. pylori* (*Ismail et al., 2003*). The complement products were present only in those areas associated with *Helicobacter*, suggesting that *H. pylori* induced local activation of complement.

The mechanisms by which the immune response can eradicate gastric *Helicobacter* infection are unknown. *Ismail et al.(2003)*

hypothesized that Helicobacter-induced activation of the complement system could promote both inflammation and eradication of Helicobacter from the stomach. The complement system is one of the natural defense mechanisms that protect the human body from infections and perhaps tumors (*Warner, 1998*). That is why H.pylori infection activate complement system leads to increase levels of serum C3 and C4 as we record it in our study.

The (classic pathway) CP and AP (alternative pathway) activity was significantly higher in the elderly.*Gaya et al .,2018* revealed that In the early phase of life, innate immunity plays a fundamental role since adaptive immunity is still under development, whereas during adolescence this is reversed . Immunity undergoes severe deterioration with age. Previous studies showed that both for innate and adaptive immunity, the function reduces with age that why in our study lowest significant increase in serum C3 was seen in patients at 50-65 years old

Also This variable results agreement with *Shaldoum, F. M., & Gobaara (et al.,2018)* who found that . Activation of C4 is frequently found to be a more sensitive measure of classical pathway of activation due to bacteria activate complement system through delayed inducement of antibody to immune system. *Desar et al. (2009)* agreed with this point of view and observed that H. pylori is complement sensitive and activates the classical pathway. Bacteria immediately activate C3 by Antigen through alternative pathway. However, *Hussain et al, (2008)* suggested that low C4 levels may falsely be regarded as classical pathway activation (reduced levels of total C4, reduced synthesis or increased catabolism of C4 without corresponding complement activation) and that several other factors may

explain low C4 level. In the current work, the low level of C4 was associated with the development and exacerbation of H. pylori.

Bacteria immediately activate C3 by Antigen through alternative pathway and delayed activation of C4 through classical pathway occurs by secreted specific antibodies. This correlation suggests possible use of changed levels of C3 and C4 as biomarker for infection with H. pylori .The detection of H. pylori infection using antigens or antibodies test can be supported with test for C3 and C4. Bacteria immediately activate complement system by Antigen through alternative pathway and delayed activation of complement system through classical pathway occurs by secreted specific antibodies. The association between low levels of C3 and C4 with the development and exacerbation of H. pylori suggests possible use of changed levels of C3 and C4 as a biomarker for H.pylori infections. (*Shaldoum & Gobaara, 2018*).

In contrast *Dore et al.(2005)* found Lower levels of C3 and/or C4 complement fractions were observed in infected patients with H.pylori with respect to controls .

While On the other hand *Jia et al.,(2016)* found that complement component (C)3 and C4 levels remained unchanged. This may be because complement proteins are not directly affected by antigens; they auto regulate and are the most constant mediators in the immune response.

In conclusion, there are important sex- and age-related differences in the complement system. These changes should be taken into account when studying complement-related diseases.

2-2-Anti-ds DNA and ANA

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is one of the most commonly studied infectious agents proposed as agents triggering autoimmune response. This is due to the unique attributes of *H. pylori* such as long-term survival in the host environment, worldwide prevalence, and its complex interactions with the host immune system. Because of its ability to elicit a chronic immune response in the host, studies have suggested a possible role for *H. pylori* in the development of autoimmune diseases. The main pathophysiological event in *H. pylori* infection is initiation and continuation of an inflammatory response. Bacteria or their products induce this inflammatory process and the main mediators of which are cytokines. This response is linked to the expression of proinflammatory cytokines, both on the surface epithelium and in macrophages/monocytes (Radić, 2014)

Anti -dsDNA and serum ANA concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

The results showed higher serum levels of ANA and Anti -dsDNA in *H. pylori*-infected patients which represent the *H. pylori*-related immune disturbance in these patients. The mean value of serum ANA was significantly higher in comparison to the control group this result was came in accordance with the results of *Jafarzadeh et al.(2013)* found higher serum levels of ANA in *H. pylori*-infected patients with peptic ulcer disease. *H. pylori* infection causes not only a variety of gastroduodenal diseases, but is also involved in the pathogenesis of various autoimmune

disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA), idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, Sjogren's syndrome, autoimmune gastric atrophy, anti-phospholipid antibody syndrome, autoimmune thyroiditis and Henoch-Schoenlein purpura (*Hasni et al.,2011*).

The significant increase of serum Anti-dsDNA came in agreement with those recorded by *Surawut et al.,(2018)* their study finding that Helicobacter pylori infection increased anti dsDNA.HP infection has been shown to enhance auto-antibodies (*Yamanishi et al., 2006; Hasni et al., 2011*), thus this study specifically looked at anti-dsDNA levels, a specific auto-antibody of lupus, which also helps determine disease severity. Indeed, HP induced anti-dsDNA in wildtypes, the localized HP gastritis may induce the systemic inflammatory responses and enhance lupus progression in some patients with lupus. IL-2 is a pro-inflammatory cytokine that is mainly synthesized by immunoregulatory T helper cells and which plays an important role in antitumor immunity. Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) is a gram-negative bacterium that colonizes the gastric mucosa and induces the production of IL-2. This process increases the magnitude of inflammation and may influence the development of gastric pathologies (*Melchiades et al.,2017*).

The possible mechanisms responsible for the elevation of ANA levels in H. pylori-infected patients still remain to be determined. Some H. pylori components may be responsible for this phenomenon. It has been demonstrated that both cell surface-bound urease and purified urease isolated from H. pylori activate murine B cells to produce various autoantibodies, such as immunoglobulin M (IgM)-type RF, anti-single stranded DNA and anti-phosphatidylcholine antibodies (*Yamanishi et*

al.,2006). Also, Previous studies conducted on mice have shown that exposure to *H. pylori* urease can lead to production of anti ss-DNA antibodies (*Radić .,2014*).

Moreover, it has also been reported that the direct interaction of extracellular toll like receptors (TLR2) on B-1 type cells with *H. pylori* urease induces the production of various autoantibodies in a T-cell-independent manner. This may account for the association of various autoimmune diseases with *H. pylori* infection. Accordingly, it has been suggested that *H. pylori* components such as urease may be among the environmental inducers that initiate several autoimmune diseases by inducing the production of autoantibodies via the activation of B-1 cells (*Jafarzadeh et al.,2013*).

Lupus characteristics as determined by serum anti-dsDNA Helicobacter pylori Infection Enhanced Anti-dsDNA Levels and Clinical Characteristics of Lupus in 24-Week-Old FcγRIIb Deficient-mice HP infection enhanced systemic inflammation, induced antibody-producing immune cells in the spleen and enhanced lupus disease severity. Thus, the localized HP gastritis may induce the systemic inflammatory responses and enhance lupus progression in some patients with lupus. Thus patients with dyspepsia or increased systemic cytokine of unknown causes should be further investigated for HP-induced chronic gastritis. Clinical studies to confirm these findings in humans are necessary, which may change our current approach to clinical management of lupus (*Surawut et al.,2018*).

On the other hand there is conflicting and controversial data regarding association of *H. pylori* infection with other autoimmune diseases. *Hasni et al.,(2011)* found that There was no significant

association between *H. pylori* positivity and presence of autoantibodies in primary or secondary Sjögren's syndrome patients (*Radić, 2014*).

Also in contrast to our results an early study reported a negative association between *H. pylori* seropositivity and the development of SLE in African-American women. These data suggest that either the presence of the pathogen confers protection from SLE or that the same mechanisms that make individuals prone to *H. pylori* infection also promote the immune dysregulation which is necessary for SLE's induction in African-American females (*Smyk et al., 2014*).

2-3-Immunoglobulins

Our data revealed that the mean values of serum Ig-G, IgA, IgM and IgE concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum IgG, IgA, IgM and IgE was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum IgG, IgM and IgE was seen in patients more than 65 years old. And the lowest significant increase in serum Ig-A was seen in patients at 20-35 years old.

Our results came in accordance with *Jafarzadeh et al., 2013* revealed that it has been suggested that *H. pylori* components such as urease may be among the environmental inducers that initiate several autoimmune diseases by inducing the production of autoantibodies via the activation of B-1 cells. Also *Al-Mossawei, et al., (2016)* assumed that this high percent may be due to the infection associated with low socioeconomic status, poor hygiene and overcrowding.

The lowest significant increase in patients more than 65 years may be due to aging because The immune activity, as most of physiological functions, decline with age, which also has been used as a theoretical basis for explaining the process of aging (*Castellão et al., 2015*).

2-3-1-Immunoglobulin class M and class G

The illustrated data in table (X) Fig (X) show The highest significant increase in serum IgG concentration increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients at 20-35 years old. While the provided data in table (XIII) Fig.(XIII) showed that The highest significant increase in seru IgM concentration was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

The mean values of serum *Ig-G* and Serum IgM concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

Similarly, *Alem et al.,(2002)* found that the prevalence of IgM antibodies to *H. pylori* in tested sera was significantly higher in symptomatic patients than in asymptomatic individuals .

On the other hand *Salim et al 2018* state that IgM and IgG antibodies average value in the blood of multiple sclerosis (MS) patients against helicobacter pylori shown a statistically significant decrease .Therefore it may be considered that probably helicobacter pylori presence in the individuals especially in female can alleviate MS signs. CMV infection can intensify the symptoms in multiple sclerosis patients.

2-3-2-Immunoglobulin class A and class G

The noticed data in table (XI) Fig.(XI) revealed that the highest significant increase in IgA concentration was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients more than 65 years old. And The mean values of serum *Ig-A* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group

Chronic *H. pylori* infection elicits local and systemic immunological responses, leading to the production of IgA and IgG antibodies. Host B cells are activated by both Th1 and Th2 cells via specific cytokines and responses involving immunoglobulins (*Fakhre-Yaseri et al.,2017*).

In our study or results revealed that The mean values of serum Ig-A and serum Ig-G concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group .This results agreement with *Li et al 2003* who found that both serum anti-*H. pylori* IgG and IgA are remarkably higher in *H. pylori* positive patients than those negative for *H. pylori* .This is may be because of most pathological mechanism of *H. pylori* infection is the immunopathological response of host. When chronic gastritis occurs, a detectable specific humoral immunological response will be established. The appearance of serum antibodies such as IgG and IgA may indicate an extensive immunoreaction causing by *H. pylori* infection. The serum anti-*H. pylori*-IgG antibody, therefore, acts as a highly accurate, simple and noninvasive method in monitoring the status of *H. pylori* infection (*Li et al., 2003*).

Knekt et al., (2006) found an elevated risk of noncardia gastric cancer among individuals with *H. pylori* infection. He reported a stronger

association for cancer cases diagnosed more than 10 years after baseline. He found an increased risk associated with elevated IgA antibodies in diffuse, intestinal and unspecified adenocarcinoma, suggesting that *H. pylori* infection is involved in all types of noncardia gastric cancers. Interestingly, the relative odds found in this study are rather similar for the intestinal type carcinoma and undefined adenocarcinoma. The lack of significance in some subtypes is apparently due to the small number of cancer cases. The clinical interest toward the IgA response is emphasized when considered in connection with earlier findings showing the association of *H. pylori* antibodies of the IgA class with a CagA positive infection, as well as with other reports showing an increased risk of peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer in cagA positive infection. Furthermore, a CagA-positive infection has been shown to be associated with a more intensive inflammation than a CagA-negative infection (*Knekt et al., 2006*).

Laboratory – based serologic testing using ELISA technology to detect IgM antibodies and ICT to detect IgG antibodies against *H. pylori* is inexpensive, noninvasive, and well –suited to primary care practice. Thus a positive IgG antibody test for *H. pylori* indicates a marker for infection rather than an indicator for active infection. While a positive IgM antibody test for *H. pylori* indicates a marker for an active infection (*Al-Mossawei et al., 2016*)

2-3-3-Immunoglobulin class E

The present data in table (XII) Fig.(XII) showed that the highest significant increase in IgE concentration was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients

more than 65 years old. And the mean values of serum *Ig-E* concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

H. pylori infection is related to allergic disease and/or immunoglobulin E (IgE) hypersensitivity. *Rasmi et.,al (2015)* Revealed that IgE levels are increased in patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection which is agreement with our result. Furthermore, inflammation caused by *H. pylori* (especially, CagA+ strains) may damage the integrity of gastric barrier and, therefore, increase the transmission of food antigens and incidence of allergic reactions.

Gastric mucosa responds with inflammation to *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection. While numerous reports have shown that the immune system produces specific IgG, IgA, and IgM isotype anti *H. pylori* antibodies, IgE-mediated pathways of *H. pylori*-associated gastritis are mostly unknown. In chronic gastritis, the number of IgE-positive cells increased significantly as compared to normal mucosa. In gastritic patients, *H. pylori* positivity was accompanied by a significant accumulation of IgE-positive cells, mainly plasma cells. These data suggest that IgE-mediated immune response probably plays an important role in the development of *H. pylori*-associated gastritis (*Berczi et al.,2000*).

Our results demonstrated significantly positive correlation between *H. pylori* infection and the production of IgE antibody as an indicator for the susceptibility to allergy, which can be used for optimizing the strategies for the treatment of allergic patients.

Gastric mucosa which acts as a barrier against antigens is destroyed by *H. pylori*. Thus, increase in the flow of food antigens passing through

increases the possibility of allergic reaction. Because of the increased epithelial secretion of CagA+ strains, a special path is established for allergens which stimulate the IgE response in atopic people. Bacteria colonization in gastro defers its defecation and provides more bacterial penetration into the digestive system. Another mechanism relevant to the second theory is the stimulation of systemic sympathetic nervous system and increase in its tone due to H. pylori infection. The increased sympathetic tone may shift the immunological responses toward Th2 that in turn increases the ability of the immune system to induce allergic reaction (*Rasmi,et al., 2015*).

2-4-Cortisol

Cortisol plays an important role in the defense of a host infected with bacteria, is secreted through the stress-mediated activation of the hypothalamic-pituitaryadrenal (HPA) axis. High levels of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and cortisol are generally considered to be outcomes of an HPA-axis disorder. Moreover, the levels of the ACTH immunoreactive substance (IS) are regulated by negative feedback from neurogenic stimulation and plasma cortisol. On the other hand, leptin suppresses HPA-axis activity, whereas ghrelin stimulates neuropeptide Y and food intake, which induces high concentrations of plasma ACTH and cortisol. HPA-axis alterations are related to gut motor functions . Moreover, serum-free cortisol fluctuations are associated with various symptoms of functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs), including FD. Some studies showed that an increased serum cortisol level promoted H. pylori colonization.

Figure (19):hypothalamic-pituitaryadrenal (HPA) axis

Our data illustrated in table (XVI) Fig. (XVI) showed that the mean values of serum cortisol concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase was noticed in patients at age less than 20 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

Our results showed a significant increase in serum cortisol at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group this results came in accordance with *Koşan et al.,2008* who found that the serum cortisol level was increased in *H. pylori*-positive patients compared with those of the healthy control group. *H. pylori* may have direct neurotoxic effects that lead to alteration of the brain-gut axis through the activation of neurogenic inflammatory processes, or microelement deficiency secondary to functional and morphological changes in the digestive tract. In digestive tissue, *H. pylori* can alter signaling in the brain-gut axis by mast cells, thereby indirectly influencing the brain-gut axis.

These immune-mediators may stimulate mast cells (MC) in the gastric mucosa, as well as the hypothalamus and brain stem (via neuroendocrine-immuno crosstalk), thereby activating the sympathetic ANS and pituitary suprarenal axis, resulting in increased cortisol and adrenalin secretion (*Budzyński and Kłopocka., 2014*).

Furthermore, *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*, Hp) infection is considered the major cause of the chronic gastric inflammation of FD (Functional dyspepsia) patients. Gastric inflammation has been shown to affect motor function and visceral sensitivity in experimental models. *H. pylori* strains that express CagA may be responsible for the FD associated with the more severe forms of gastritis. It was reported that CagA-positive *H. pylori* strains induced more dyspeptic symptoms than CagA-negative or *H. pylori*-negative strains in patients with FD. Some of these functional symptoms can be explained by a gut-driven brain disorder, and in vivo hormonal changes have also been implicated. However, no definite clinical manifestation is linked to CagA-positive *H. pylori* strains infection or fluctuating levels of hormones in FD patients (*Meng et al.,2016*).

In contrast *Katagiri et al.,2006* reported that *H. pylori*-infected patients had significantly decreased cortisol levels than *H. pylori*-negative patients. They also demonstrated that cortisol prevents *H. pylori* colonization through strengthening the host defense mechanisms. Recently, studies have shown that drugs, such as cimetidine, reduce basal and stimulated cortisol synthesis through inhibiting enzymes. However, proton pump inhibitors, such as lansoprazole and rabeprazole, are thought to cause increased cortisol levels in a starvation condition due to their possible

effects of stimulating the HPA axis and increasing the plasma ACTH-IS level (*Katagiri et al.,2006*)

Figure (20): Effects of gastrointestinal hormones level to mental disorder after *H.pylori* colonization CagA-Positive *H.pylori* strains could induce fluctuations in the levels of serotonin , gherlin, dopamine ,and cortisol ,and might be the cause of some dyspepsia symptoms and mental disorder through blood circulation and brain-gut axis (*Meng et al.,2016*).

In our previous study *Abdulamaqsoud et al .,2015* showed that both serum ghrelin and leptin concentrations were significantly reduced in *H. pylori*-infected people when compared with those in *H. pylori*-negative people which play an active role in increasing cortisol level in people infected with *H.pylori*.

4-Pyruvate and Lactate

The data illustrated in tables (IV and V) Figures (IV and V) showed that the mean values of serum lactate and serum pyruvate concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum pyruvate and serum lactate was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old. The lowest significant increase in serum lactate was seen in patients at 20-35 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum lactate was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

The result is showing a significant increase in serum pyruvate and lactate at different ages in comparison with the control group. We can explain this point by the fact that *H. pylori* is a true microaerophile that exhibits oxygen dependent growth at oxygen levels below 21% and fails to grow or grows only poorly at the oxygen levels present in air. Thus, the existence of a mixed-acid fermentation pathway in wild-type strains of *H. pylori* may be a manifestation of the metabolic adaptation of the bacterium to its particular ecological niche. During conditions of high pyruvate accumulation, besides transforming this metabolite via a mixed-acid fermentation pathway, *H. pylori* may convert pyruvate to lactate using the fermentative lactate dehydrogenase (*Mendz et al., 1994*).

Furthermore, Previous metabolic studies of *H. pylori* have revealed that this bacterium is capable of producing lactate as one of the end products of glucose and pyruvate metabolism (*Iwatani et al., 2014*).

Metabolically, lactate can be generated by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) from pyruvic acid as the end product of glycolysis. However, LDH

can also catalyse the reverse reaction, converting lactate into pyruvate. Thus, if exogenous lactate was imported into *H. pylori*, it could be oxidised into pyruvate, which would then enter the tricarboxylic acid cycle. Alternatively, lactate can donate electrons to NADH and, in turn, to the electron transport chain to enhance proton motive force and bacterial energy levels (*Machuca et al., 2017*).

Figure (21): Glucose metabolism in *Helicobacter Pylori*.

The gastric pathogen *H. pylori* uses glucose as the primary energy substrate, although the overall metabolism of *H. pylori* yet remains inadequately understood. Some early evidences, however, suggest that *H. pylori* has the ability to utilize glucose for metabolism through a glucokinase activity and enzymes of the pentose phosphate and glycolysis pathways. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is usually produced as a by-product of glucose catabolism which is then transported to the lungs through the blood stream and finally it is excreted in human breath. However, the precise role of glucose metabolism, especially in the pathogenesis of the *H. pylori* infection is not currently known. A new insight into the role of glucose metabolism is essential to elucidate the pathophysiology of *H. pylori* for its

successful colonization of the gastrointestinal tract. However, to our knowledge, so far there have been no studies focused on glucose uptake for individuals harboring *H. pylori* infections, exhibiting the time-dependent excretion dynamics of the metabolite CO₂ in exhaled breath (*Mendz et al., 1993*).

The purpose of this study was therefore, primarily to explore the potential links between pyruvate, lactate and *H. pylori* infections in response to inflammation biomarker

4-1- Pyruvate and lactate and immune cell metabolism

Accumulation of lactate in the tissue microenvironment is a feature of both inflammatory disease and cancer. Here, we assess the response of immune cells to lactate in the context of chronic inflammation. Lactate is one of the most enriched by-products of cellular metabolism in inflamed tissues. Its accumulation leads to the exacerbation of the inflammatory response in chronic inflammatory disorders like rheumatoid arthritis (*Pucino et al., 2019*).

Lactate, the end product of anaerobic glycolysis, is produced in high amounts by innate immune cells during inflammatory activation, so increase in serum lactate in infected people with *helicobacter pylori* may be due to immune response to the *H.pylori* infection. Activation of macrophages and dendritic cells (DCs) by pro-inflammatory stimuli causes them to undergo a metabolic switch towards glycolysis and away from oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), similar to the Warburg effect in tumors.

The Warburg effect is an important concept for understanding metabolic changes occurring in innate immune cells upon activation. Otto

Warburg described a metabolic profile of tumors in normoxic conditions, in which glycolysis predominates even though there is oxygen available for oxidative metabolism to proceed. Pyruvate that is produced by the glycolytic pathway, instead of feeding into the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and subsequent oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), is metabolized to lactate. The Warburg Effect is depicted in. This concept reappeared, but in the innate immune world, in the 1950s, with the discovery that neutrophils depend on aerobic glycolysis for ATP production, and have few mitochondria. Glucose consumption in these cells was high, while oxygen consumption was low. *Newsholme et al.(1987)* investigated macrophage metabolism and showed that most of the glucose consumed by resting macrophages was converted to lactate, with little being used for OXPHOS. Activated macrophages were shown to have increased expression of the glycolytic enzymes hexokinase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, indicating an increase in glycolytic activity in these cells (*Kelly and O'neill 2015*). *That leads to an increase in the production of pyruvate and lactate which support pour results.*

Figure (22): Warburg Effect .

4-2- Pyruvate and lactate with hyperinsulinemia

Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) infection will induce chronic inflammation and immune responses in the stomach. Some inflammatory cytokines and adipokines, such as tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) and leptin may be involved in this inflammation or immune response. Patients with H. pylori infection have a lower serum fasting leptin level but a higher TNF- α value. Past studies have revealed that a leptin deficiency and a high TNF- α level will induce insulin resistance (IR). IR and central obesity are the key mechanisms for developing metabolic syndrome (MS). The relationships between H. pylori infection and IR or MS have been reported by several investigations, including two large Japanese population studies and one meta-analysis study (*Polyzos et al., 2011*). However, other investigations have found conflicting results (*Chen et al., 2015*)

We can say also that significant increase in pyruvate and lactate in patient infected with helicobacter pylori may be due to hyperinsulinemia or insulin resistance caused by helicobacter pylori as explained by *Berhane et al., 2015* who revealed that helicobacter pylori cause insulin resistance lead to increase insulin which stimulate glycolysis produce excessive pyruvate that is further converted to lactate .When the body becomes resistant to insulin, it tries to cope by producing more insulin. People with insulin resistance are often producing too more insulin than healthy people. Producing too much insulin is known as hyperinsulinemia.

The high levels of circulating insulin stimulate glycolysis, anaerobic glucose metabolism, producing excessive pyruvate that is further converted to lactate leading to high circulating lactate levels. Studies have shown that glycolysis increases in patients with (*Berhane et al., 2015*)

Also *Cherkas et al .,2016* stated that H.pylori contamination is linked to a significantly higher heart rate, sympathetic activation, and increased insulin resistance,The high levels of circulating insulin stimulate glycolysis, anaerobic glucose metabolism, producing excessive pyruvate that is further converted to lactate leading to high circulating lactate levels .During the stage of hyperinsulinemia, the additional stimuli for the body to convert pyruvate to lactate, instead of converting it to acetyl CoA and sending it to the Krebs cycle (*Chen al.,2015*)

Also *Berhane et al., 2015* found that hyperisulinemia leads to increase Plasma Lactate Levels which agree with our results that show a high level of pyruvate and lactate in patient infected with helicobacter pylori.

5- Helicobacter pylori with metabolic syndrome

As we obtained in our study that helicobacter pylori infection lead to insulin resistance ,insulin resistance lead to hyperinsulinemia which stimulate glycolysis lead to increase pyruvate and lactate level as we recorded it in our study,also our result showed that the albumin level will increase in infected people with helicobacter pylori this is maybe due to insulin resistance where *Bae et al. 2013* explained that the positive association between serum albumin level and insulin resistance might be a consequence of increased albumin production in the liver under insulin-resistant conditions. Insulin resistance goes hand-in-hand with increased insulin levels and insulin is known to stimulate albumin production in hepatocytes. On the other hand, some reports have shown that albumin has a cardioprotective effect that may be due to albumin acting as an antioxidant and a protective protein against chronic inflammation.

There are three possible mechanisms that might explain our findings. First, *H. pylori* infection impairs secretion balance of proinflammatory cytokines and CRP, angiotensinogen, free fatty acids, and leptin hormone, and thus, reactive oxygen species begin to accumulate. Subclinical chronic inflammation induced by *H. pylori* infection occurs via impaired cytokine balance and stimulated macrophages. There are explanations that this leads to unresponsiveness to insulin in the peripheral tissue and subsequently to metabolic syndrome . Second, Ghrelin, as a multifunctional polypeptide secreted from gastric mucosa, is involved in ingestion, appetite, and nutrition, especially lipid absorption and lipogenesis. The Ghrelin can also modulate insulin sensitivity and stimulate insulin-induced glucose uptake , and the *H. pylori* infection can impair Ghrelin synthesis . Third, the previous studies showed that infection with *H. pylori* had a positive association with high LDL, low HDL, and cardiovascular disease and successful *H. pylori* eradication decreased the risk of high LDL and low HDL (*Yang et al.,2016*)

H.pylori infection associated with increased in immune stress marker as Anti-ds DNA and ANA and immunoglobulin IgM, IgG ,IgA and IgE, wick are associated with autoimmune diseases. Also this infection associated with increased serum IL-2 in response to this increase also Cortisol level will increase. *H.pylori* is probably responsible of immunesystem disturbance and autoimmune disorder.

Summary

&

Conclusion

SUMMARY

The aim of the present work was to find a relationship between Serum albumin, total protein, lactate, pyruvate, IL-2, IL-6, C3, C4, Immunoglobulin antibodies (IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE), Anti-DNA double strand, Anti-nuclear antibody pattern, CRP and Cortisol concentration with helicobacter pylori.

In order to achieve this aim 120 subjects

Control normal group: Consist of 20 healthy individuals with ages ranged from 20 to over 65 years

Group I: Consists of 20-diseased patients with age less than 20 years.

Group II: Consists of 20-diseased patients with age ranged from 20 to 35 years.

Group III: Consists of 20-diseased patients with age ranged from 35-50 years.

Group IV: Consists of 20-diseased patients with age ranged from 50-65 years.

Group V: Consists of 20-diseased patients with age more than 65 years.

Blood samples:

Peripheral blood samples of all infected peoples and healthy peoples were collected. The collected samples were transferred to 5ml vacutainer tubes, left to stand about 30minutes in room temperature, then centrifuged (at 3000 r.p.m for 5 minutes) and all available sera were stored at -20°C, vials, until being analysis.

Following proper selection of patients and control subjects, the following laboratory tests were performed for all of them:

1. Determination of Stool H. Pylori antigen.
2. Determination of Serum albumin and total protein concentrations.

3. Determination of Serum lactate and pyruvate concentrations.
4. Determination of Serum IL-2 and IL-6 concentrations.
5. Determination of Serum C3 and C4 concentrations.
6. Determination of Serum IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE concentrations.
7. Determination of Anti-DNA double strand concentration.
8. Determination of Anti-nuclear antibody pattern.
9. Determination of CRP concentration.
10. Determination of Cortisol concentration.

The result of the present study can be summarized as follows:

The mean values of stool H. Pylori antigen concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

The mean values of serum total protein concentration in the infected human groups showed a non significant increase at age less than 20 years old, while showed a significant decrease at the elder ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

The mean values of serum albumin concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant decrease at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

The mean values of serum lactate, pyruvate, IL-2, IL-6 and Complement (C3 and C4) concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

The mean values of serum Immunoglobulin IgM, IgA, IgG and IgE concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

The mean values of serum Anti-DNA double strand , Anti-nuclear antibody pattern, CRP and Cortisol concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group.

After the discussing the results can conclude the following:

1. *H. pylori* infection will induce chronic inflammation and immune responses in the stomach.
2. *H. pylori* components such as urease may be among the environmental inducers that initiate several autoimmune diseases by inducing the production of autoantibodies via the activation of B-1 cells.
3. *H. pylori* infection was found to be associated with an increased risk of metabolic syndrome, indicating that *H. pylori* infection could be used as a risk factor of metabolic syndrome.
4. *H. pylori* is complementing sensitive and activates the classic pathway even in the absence of specific antibodies.
5. The detection of *H. pylori* infection using Antigen tests or Antibody test can be supported with test for C3 and C4. Bacteria immediately activate C3 by Antigen through alternative pathway and delayed activation of C4 through classical pathway occurs by secreted specific antibodies. This correlation suggests possible use of changed levels of C3 and C4 as biomarker for infection with *H. pylori*.
6. *H. pylori* infection is related to allergic disease and/or immunoglobulin E (IgE) hypersensitivity Furthermore, inflammation caused by *H. pylori* (especially, CagA+ strains) may damage the integrity of gastric barrier and, therefore, increase the transmission of food antigens and incidence of allergic reactions.

7. Gastric mucosa which acts as a barrier against antigens is destroyed by *H. pylori*. Thus, increase in the flow of food antigens passing through increases the possibility of allergic reaction.
8. Our results has shown an association of *Helicobacter pylori* infection with liver dysfunction wich lead to hyporproteinemia thus confirming that protein-losing gastroenteropathy (PLGE) was caused by *H. pylori* infection.
9. Impaired liver function by helicobacter pylori endotoxin also The Evidence has shown an association of *Helicobacter pylori* infection with liver dysfunction.
10. The highest significant decrease in serum total protein and serum albumin was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old may be due to effect of helicobacter pylori on gastro-duodenal inflammation, ulcerative lesions Thus, we infer that *H. pylori* eradication therapy for elderly patients with *H. pylori*-infected chronic gastritis may be an effective therapy for the prevention of weight loss in elderly individuals.
11. Strong immune response to *H. pylori* enhanced the systemic inflammation, which was reflected in an increased level of serum IL-2, IL-6 and serum CRP. IL-6 plays a key role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis that is an underlying cause of coronary heart disease.
12. Also increase in IL-6,IL-2 and CRP level caused by *H.pylori* infection affect liver and consequently at will affect all inflammation marker produced by the liver.
13. *H.pylori* induce IL-6 secretion which in response leads to increase CRP level which involves in opsonization and activation the complement system of the Immune system Leeds to increase in C3 ,C4 and Immunoglobulins.

- 14.** H.pylori infection associated with an increased in immune stress marker as the complement system, Anti-ds DNA, ANA and immunoglobulin IgM, IgG ,IgA and IgE, which are associated with autoimmune diseases. Also, this infection associated with increased serum Cortisol level. That is why H.pylori is probably responsible for immune system disturbance and autoimmune disorder.
- 15.** Helicobacter pylorus (H. pylori) is one of the most commonly studied infectious agents proposed as agents triggering autoimmune response lead to increase Anti-ds DNA and ANA that explain the role for H. pylori in the development of autoimmune diseases.
- 16.** H. pylori infection causes not only a variety of gastroduodenal diseases, but is also involved in the pathogenesis of various autoimmune disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA), idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, Sjogren's syndrome, autoimmune gastric atrophy, anti-phospholipid antibody syndrome, autoimmune thyroiditis and Henoch-Schoenlein purpura.
- 17.** Lupus characteristics as determined by serum anti-dsDNA .Helicobacter pylori Infection Enhanced Anti-dsDNA Levels and Clinical Characteristics of Lupus Thus, the localized HP gastritis may induce the systemic inflammatory responses and enhance lupus progression in some patients with lupus.
- 18.** H. pylori may have direct neurotoxic effects that lead to alteration of the brain-gut axis through the activation of neurogenic inflammatory processes increase cortisol and adrenalin.
- 19.** Significant increase in pyruvate and lactate in a patient infected with helicobacter pylori may be due to hyperinsulinemia or insulin resistance caused by helicobacter pylori infection which cause insulin resistance leads to increase insulin that stimulate glycolysis

and produce excessive pyruvate that is further converted to lactate. Lactate is one of the most enriched by-products of cellular metabolism in inflamed tissues. Its accumulation leads to the exacerbation of the inflammatory response in chronic inflammatory disorders like rheumatoid arthritis.

20. Helicobacter pylori leads to decrease leptin level as postulated in our previous study *Abd El-Maksoud et al., 2015* which cause insulin resistance, insulin resistance leads to hyperinsulinemia which stimulate glycolysis leads to increase pyruvate and lactate level.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Our results demonstrated significantly positive correlation between *H. pylori* infection and the production of IgE antibody as an indicator for the susceptibility to allergy, which can be used for optimizing the strategies for the treatment of allergic patients.

Helicobacter pylori infection induce cytokine production This continued cytokine production can have a deleterious effect on the host, with the development of hypotension, intravascular thrombosis, pulmonary edema, and hemorrhage.

Patients with dyspepsia or increased systemic cytokine of unknown causes should be further investigated for HP-induced chronic gastritis. Clinical studies to confirm these findings in humans are necessary, which may change our current approach to clinical management of lupus.

The detection of *H. pylori* infection using antigens or antibodies test can be supported with test for C3 and C4.

H. pylori eradication therapy for elderly patients with *H. pylori*-infected chronic gastritis may be an effective therapy for the prevention of weight loss in elderly individuals.

Further prospective & interventional studies are recommended to clarify the causal relationship between *H.pylori* infection and ischaemic heart disease and to assess the effect of therapeutic eradication of *H.pylori* on cardiovascular risk factors.

H. pylori infection is a major risk factor for the process from atrophy, IM to DYS of gastric mucosa. Serum IgG and IgA are good indicators to evaluate this progress with a certain arrearage. Investigation on the effective assemblages of clinical presentations may provide a better

understanding in the pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment for *H. pylori* infection.

Because *H. pylori* infection can be easily eradicated by specific treatment, the accurate definition of this new risk factor may lead to new strategies for the prevention of ischaemic heart disease, Autoimmune disease, anemia, peptic ulcer, gastritis and gastric cancer.

Although findings regarding the correlations between *H. pylori* and autoimmune disease pathogenesis have been accumulating, the existing data do not completely lead to an unequivocal conclusion. Further high-quality clinical and experimental analyses are necessary to evaluate the efficacy of *H. pylori* eradication in immunostress biomarker changes observed in autoimmune disease.

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Arabic

Summary

الملخص العربي

إن الميكروب الحلزوني، ينمو في الجهاز الهضمي وهو بكتيريا حلزونية الشكل، تعيش وتتكاثر في الجدران المبطنة للمعدة ولديها القدرة على مهاجمة بطانة المعدة، عادةً ما تكون غير ضارة، ولكنها مسؤولة عن غالبية حالات القرحة والأمعاء الدقيقة، كما يبقى الشخص مصاب بالعدوى ما لم يخضع للعلاج، وهو تنتقل للإنسان عن طريق الأطعمة، أو المياه والأواني غير النظيفة، أو الاتصال بلعاب الشخص المصاب أو مشاركة الأواني معه، و يتميز بقدرته على الحياة في المعدة البشرية ومعدات الحيوانات وتأقلمه بصورة تمكنه من العيش لسنوات طويلة داخل الجسم الذي يهاجمه، حيث يؤدي الميكروب الحلزوني إلى حدوث التهاب للمعدة كما يعمل على تدمير الخلايا التي توجد في غشاء المعدة المخاطي، وهذا الميكروب قادر على حماية نفسه من العصائر الحمضية الهاضمة في المعدة عن طريق تكوين وسط قلوي يحيط به من خلال تكوين مادة النشادر، كما يتميز هذا الميكروب بقدرته العالية وتحصنه بوسائل دفاعية تحميه من الحمضيات التي تفرزها المعدة أثناء هضم الطعام ، وهذا بخلاف الاعتقاد السائد عند العلماء في السابق، الذين ظنوا لسنوات طويلة أن البكتيريا لا يمكن أن تعيش في المعدة البشرية التي تمتلئ بالأحماض القاتلة للميكروبات، لكن أثبتت الدراسات والتجارب بعد ذلك أن البكتيريا الحلزونية تستطيع العيش والتأقلم في البيئة الحمضية للمعدة.

حيث أن ثلثي سكان العالم يعانون من الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني، ويتسبب في الإصابة بأكثر من ٩٠٪ من قرح الاثنى عشر، و ٨٠٪ من قرح المعدة، ويصبح الأشخاص المصابون بهذا النوع من البكتيريا أكثر عرضة للإصابة بسرطان المعدة، مقارنة بنظرائهم غير المصابين، كما أن تقديرات بعض الأطباء في مصر تشير إلى أن نسبة إصابة المصريين بهذه الجرثومة تفوق النسب العالمية حيث تقترب من 90 % للأشخاص الذين تجاوزوا سن الـ 50 سنة، أما في الأعمار ما بين 20 إلى 40 سنة فإن النسبة تصل ما بين 50 إلى 70 % .

إن الميكروب الحلزوني يتسبب في الإصابة ببعض الأمراض، ومنها الحساسية في الجلد، والذبحة الصدرية، وكذلك يتسبب في التهابات البنكرياس والإصابة بالسكري، وحدثت تقرحات في المعدة، وعلى الأمد البعيد من الممكن أن تؤدي إلى ضعف الغشاء المبطن الذي يتسبب في حدوث تقرحات تحرم المصاب بها من الاستقرار والراحة.

وقد أوضحت في دراستي السابقة في درجة الماجستير (التغيرات الكيميائية المصاحبة للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني) ان الميكروب الحلزوني يؤدي الى الاصابة بالانيميا وزيادة خطر التعرض لأمراض القلب ومرضى القصور الشريان التاجي بالقلب عن طريق خفض مستوى الكوليسترول عالي الكثافة في الدم

خاصة لدى كبار السن , كما أن الميكروب الحلزوني يزيد من إفراز هرمون الجاسترين والذي بدوره يحفز إنتاج حمض المعدة مما يؤدي الى التهاب الغشاء المبطن للمعدة وحصول قرحة ايضا كما ان الاصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني يصاحبها انخفاض في مستوى الليبتين والتي بدورها تؤثر على توازن طاقة الجسم وحدث خلل في عملية أيض الدهون في الجسم.

وبناء على دراساتي السابقة التي وضحت انه هناك علاقة بين الاصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وحدث تغيرات كيميائية حيوية في الجسم كان الهدف من العمل الحالي هو دراسة تأثير الميكروب الحلزوني على مناعة الجسم من خلال دراسة التأثير الكيميائي الحيوي للميكروب الحلزوني على الدلالات الحيوية للإجهاد المناعي وإيجاد علاقة بين مصل الألبومين ، البروتين الكلي ، اللاكتات ، البيروفات ، انترليوكين(1)، انترليوكين (2)، المكون الثالث للمتمم المناعي سي(3) والمكون الرابع للمتمم المناعي (سي 4)، والأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي (إي، جي، إم وآي)، وتركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف ، و الأجسام المضادة للنواة و البروتين التفاعلي سي و مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم.

لذلك أجريت هذه الدراسة على 100 شخص مصاب بالميكروب الحلزوني تم تقسيمهم على حسب أعمارهم إلى 5 مجموعات بالإضافة الى المجموعة الضابطة التي تحتوي على 20 شخص سليم تتراوح أعمارهم بين 25 وأكثر من 65 عام وكانت المجموعات كالاتي :

➤ المجموعة الأولى (المجموعة الضابطة) : تشمل على 20 شخص أصحاء لا يعانون من التهاب الميكروب الحلزوني تتراوح أعمارهم ما بين 25- وأكثر من 65 عام .

➤ المجموعة الثانية: تحتوي على 20 مريض يعانون من التهاب بالميكروب الحلزوني أعمارهم اقل من 20 عام.

➤ المجموعة الثالثة : تحتوي على 20 مريض يعانون من التهاب بالميكروب الحلزوني تتراوح أعمارهم ما بين (20- 35 عام).

➤ المجموعة الرابعة : تحتوي على 20 مريض يعانون من التهاب بالميكروب الحلزوني تتراوح أعمارهم ما بين (35- 50 عام).

➤ المجموعة الخامسة : تحتوي على 20 مريض يعانون من التهاب بالميكروب الحلزوني تتراوح أعمارهم ما بين (50- 65 عام).

➤ المجموعة السادسة : تحتوي على 20 مريض يعانون من التهاب بالميكروب الحلزوني وأعمارهم أكثر من 65 عام .

تم جمع عينات الدم المحيطية لجميع الأشخاص المصابين والأصحاء، وتم نقل العينات التي تم جمعها إلى أنابيب مفرغة سعة 5 مل معقمة ومحكمة الأغلاق، وتم ترك العينة لمدة 30 دقيقة في درجة حرارة الغرفة حتى يتجلط الدم ويبدأ انفصال المصل (السيرم) وتم فصل السيرم تماما بواسطة جهاز الطرد المركزي وحفظه في المجمد عند درجة حرارة 20 مئوية تحت الصفر لحين إجراء التحاليل البيوكيميائية. وقد تم إجراء تحليل الأجسام المضادة للميكروب الحلزوني بالبراز للتأكد من الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني.

➤ ومن خلال التحليل الإحصائي للنتائج وجد الآتي:

(1) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للميكروب الحلزوني في البراز:

- ❑ حدث ازدياد معنوي في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني.
- ❑ كما حدث ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة في البراز في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني والذين تتجاوز أعمارهم ال 65 عام بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام .

(2) مستوى مصل البروتين في الدم:

- ❑ حدث ازدياد غير معنوي في تركيز البروتين في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني و اعمارهم تقل عن ال 20 عام ، بينما حدث انخفاض معنوي في اعمار اكبر مقارنة بالأشخاص الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني .حيث كان هناك ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين و الذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام ، وازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني وتتراوح أعمارهم بين 30 و 35 عام.

(3) مستوى الألبومين في الدم:

- ❑ حدث انخفاض معنوي في تركيز الألبومين في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الغير مصابين ، حيث لوحظ إنخفاض معنوي بنسبة عالية في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني والذين تزيد أعمارهم عن 65 عام ، بينما لوحظ انخفاض معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام.

(4) مستوى اللاكتات في الدم:

□ حدث ازدياد معنوي في مستوى تركيز اللاكتات في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني ، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني والذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام ، بينما وجد ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين والذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام .

(5) مستوى البيروفات في الدم :

□ حدث ازدياد معنوي في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني. حيث كان هناك ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين والذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام وازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني والذين تتراوح أعمارهم بي ال 20 وال 35 عام .

(6) مستوى تركيز انترليوكين (2) وانترليوكين (6) في الدم :

□ حدث ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في مستوى تركيز الانترليوكين 2 في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني ، حيث لوحظ ازدياد معنوي كبير في الأشخاص المصابين والذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام ،بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام.

(7) مستوى تركيز المتمم المناعي سي (3) في الدم :

□ حدث ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في مستوى تركيز المتمم المناعي سي (3) في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني ، حيث لوحظ ازدياد معنوي كبير في الأشخاص المصابين والذين تتراوح أعمارهم بين 35 و 50 عام ،بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تتراوح أعمارهم بين ال 50 و 65 عام.

(8) مستوى تركيز المتمم المناعي سي (4) في الدم :

□ حدث ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في مستوى تركيز المتمم المناعي سي (4) في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني ، حيث لوحظ ازدياد معنوي كبير في الأشخاص

المصابين والذين تتراوح أعمارهم بين 35 و 50 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام.

(9) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي جي :

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي جي في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة ، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم عن ال 65 عام .

(10) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي آي:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي آي في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي بنسبة كبيرة في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تتراوح أعمارهم بين 20 و 35 عام .

(11) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي إي:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي إي في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق ال 65 عام .

(12) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي إم:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي إم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن ال 20 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق ال 65 عام .

(13) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للحمض النووي المضاعف:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام للحمض النووي المضاعف في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق الـ 65 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن 20 عام .

(14) مستوى الأجسام المضادة للنواة:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الأجسام المضادة للنواة في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق الـ 65 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن 20 عام .

(15) مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز الكورتيزول في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن الـ 20 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق 65 عام .

(16) مستوى البروتين التفاعلي سي في الدم:

□ حدث ازدياد ملحوظ في تركيز البروتين التفاعلي سي في الدم في الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني في أعمار مختلفة مقارنة بالأشخاص الأصحاء الغير مصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني، حيث وجد ازدياد معنوي ملحوظ في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تزيد أعمارهم فوق الـ 65 عام، بينما كان هناك ازدياد معنوي بنسبة أقل في الأشخاص المصابين الذين تقل أعمارهم عن الـ 20 عام.

(الخلاصة)

➤ تسبب الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني التهاباً مزمناً المعدة وتحفيز الاستجابة المناعية للجسم و قد يكون هذا بسبب المكونات التي يفرزها هذا الميكروب مثل إنزيم اليورياز وهو من ضمن العديد من

- المحفزات البيئية التي تسبب العديد من أمراض المناعة الذاتية عن طريق تحفيز إنتاج الأجسام المضادة الذاتية من خلال تنشيط خلايا المناعة.
- وجد أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني مرتبط بزيادة خطر الإصابة بمتلازمة التمثيل الغذائي، مما يشير إلى أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني يمكن استخدامها كعامل خطر يزيد من فرصة التعرض للإصابة بمتلازمة التمثيل الغذائي.
- الكشف عن الميكروب الحلزوني باستخدام اختبارات الأجسام المضادة أو المستضدات يمكن دعمها عن طريق إجراء اختبار المتمم المناعي الثالث والمتمم المناعي الرابع أيضاً، حيث يقوم هذا الميكروب بتنشيط المتمم المناعي الثالث بواسطة المستضد من خلال مسار بديل ويؤخر تفعيل المتمم المناعي الرابع في المسار الكلاسيكي عن طريق إفراز أجسام مناعية معينة، حيث يشير هذا الارتباط إلى إمكانية استخدام التغيير في مستويات المتممات المناعية الثالث والرابع كعلامة حيوية على الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني .
- ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بأمراض الحساسية و فرط حساسية الغلوبولين المناعي إي ، حيث أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤدي إلى التهابات في المعدة تؤدي إلى إتلاف سلامة الحاجز المعدي ، وبالتالي زيادة انتقال المستضدات الغذائية للدم حيث أن الغشاء المخاطي الذي يعمل كحاجز ضد المستضدات يتم تدميره بواسطة الميكروب الحلزوني ، وبالتالي فإن زيادة تدفق مستضدات الطعام التي تمر يزيد من احتمال حدوث رد فعل تحسسي .
- كما أظهرت نتائجنا ارتباطاً بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني واختلال وظائف الكبد مما يؤدي إلى نقص بروتينات الدم، مما يؤكد على أن اعتلال الجهاز الهضمي الناتج عن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني هو أحد أسباب نقص البروتين في الدم.
- تؤدي الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني إلى انخفاض مستوى الليبتين في الدم كما أثبتنا في دراستنا السابقة (التغييرات الكيميائية الحيوية المصاحبة للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني) والتي تؤثر على مؤشر كتلة الجسم وتؤدي في النهاية إلى انخفاض مستوى مصل البروتين في الدم ، وبالتالي نستنتج أن علاج استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني علاجاً فعالاً للوقاية من فقدان الوزن لدى كبار السن.
- الإستجابة المناعية القوية للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تحفز الالتهابات في الجسم حيث يمكننا أن نرى إنعكاس هذه الالتهابات في زيادة مستوى انترليوكين 2 وانثليوكين 6 والبوتين التفاعلي سي حيث يلعب انثليوكين6 دوراً رئيسياً في التسبب في تصلب الشرايين الذي يعد سبباً رئيسياً لمرض القلب التاجي، كما أن الزيادة في مستوى انثليوكين 2 وانثليوكين 6 والروتين التفاعلي سي الناتجة عن

الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤثر على الكبد وبالتالي تؤثر على جميع علامات الالتهابات التي ينتجها الكبد.

➤ يعتبر الميكروب الحلزوني أحد أكثر العوامل المعدية التي تمت دراستها بشكل شائع والتي تقترح كعوامل محفزة لإستجابة المناعة الذاتية التي تؤدي إلى زيادة تركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة مما يفسر دور الميكروب الحلزوني في تطور أمراض المناعة الذاتية .

➤ لا تسبب عدوى الملوية البوابية مجموعة متنوعة من أمراض المعدة والأمعاء فحسب ، بل تشارك أيضاً في التسبب في العديد من اضطرابات المناعة الذاتية مثل التهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي ، مرض نقص الصفائح مجهول السبب ، متلازمة سجوجرن ، ضمور المعدة المناعي الذاتي ،متلازمة التهاب الغدة الدرقية المضاد للفسفوليبيد،التهاب الغدة الدرقية المناعي و الالتهاب الوعائي بالغلوبولين المناعي أي.

➤ قد يكون للميكروب الحلزوني تأثيرات سمية عصبية مباشرة تؤدي إلى تغيير المحور العصبي القناة الهضمية المتصل بالدماغ من خلال تنشيط العمليات الالتهابية العصبية التي تزيد من الكورتيزول والأدرينالين.

➤ كما توصلنا في دراستنا إلى أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤدي إلى مقاومة الأنسولين ، ومقاومة الأنسولين تؤدي إلى فرط أنسولين الدم الذي يحفز تحلل السكر و يؤدي إلى زيادة مستوى البيروفات واللاكتات في الدم ، ومن المعروف أيضاً أن الأنسولين يحفز إنتاج الألبومين في خلايا الكبد مما يؤدي إلى زيادة مستوى الألبومين لدى الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني.

➤ ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بزيادة في علامات الإجهاد المناعي مثل النظام المتمم المناعي و الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي (إي وجي وإم وآي)، وتركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة والتي ترتبط بأمراض المناعة الذاتية ،كما ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني أيضاً بزيادة مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم لهذا السبب ربما يكون الميكروب الحلزوني مسؤول عن اضطراب الجهاز المناعي واضطراب المناعة الذاتية.

➤ قد تكون الزيادة الكبيرة في البيروفات واللاكتات في المريض المصاب بالميكروب الحلزوني بسبب فرط أنسولين الدم أو مقاومة الأنسولين الناتجة عن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني ، التي تسبب مقاومة الأنسولين مما يؤدي إلى زيادة الأنسولين في الدم الذي يحفز تحلل السكر وينتج كميات كبيرة من البيروفات التي تتحول إلى لاکتات حيث ان اللاكتات هي أحد أكثر المنتجات الثانوية المخصبة

لعملية التمثيل الغذائي الخلوي في الأنسجة الملتهبة. يؤدي تراكمه إلى تفاقم الاستجابة الالتهابية في الاضطرابات الالتهابية المزمنة مثل التهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي.

➤ ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بزيادة في علامات الإجهاد المناعي مثل النظام المتمم المناعي و الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي (إي وجي وإم وأي)، وتركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة والتي ترتبط بأمراض المناعة الذاتية، كما ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني أيضاً بزيادة مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم لهذا السبب ربما يكون الميكروب الحلزوني مسؤول عن اضطراب الجهاز المناعي واضطراب المناعة الذاتية.

(التوصيات)

➤ أظهرت نتائجنا ارتباطاً إيجابياً كبيراً بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وإنتاج الأجسام المضادة إي كمؤشر على القابلية للإصابة بالحساسية ، والتي يمكن استخدامها لتحسين استراتيجيات علاج مرضى الحساسية.

➤ المرضى الذين يعانون من عسر الهضم أو زيادة السيتوكينات الجهازية لأسباب غير معروفة يجب أن يخضعوا لمزيد من الفحوصات والدراسات السريرية الكاشفة للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني والالتهابات الناجمة عن هذه الإصابة، حيث أثبتنا في هذه الدراسة مدى ارتباط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وزيادة فرص التعرض للإصابة بمرض الذئبة أو زيادة أعراضه المرضية، مما قد يغير نهجنا الحالي في الإدارة السريرية لمرض الذئبة.

➤ قد يكون علاج استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني للمرضى المسنين المصابين بالتهاب المعدة المزمن نتيجة الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني علاجاً فعالاً للوقاية من فقدان الوزن لدى كبار السن وتجنب الإصابة بأمراض القلب وبعض أمراض المناعة الذاتية كالذئبة والتهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي.

➤ يوصى بإجراء دراسات مستقبلية وتدخلية إضافية لتوضيح العلاقة السببية بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وأمراض القلب الإقفارية، ولتقييم تأثير الاستئصال العلاجي للميكروب الحلزوني على عوامل الخطر القلبية الوعائية.

➤ الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني عامل خطر رئيسي للإصابة بضمور الغشاء المخاطي في المعدة لذا يعتبر مستوى الأجسام المضادة أي و جي مؤشرات جيدة لتقييم هذا التقدم مع نسبة معينة وقد توفر الدراسات السريرية فهماً أفضل لأسباب المرض وسهولة تشخيصه والوصول الى علاج جذري لهذا الميكروب.

- نظرًا لأنه يمكن علاج الميكروب الحلزوني بسهولة وعن طريق علاجات محددة ،لذا قد يؤدي التعريف الدقيق لخطر الإصابة بهذا الميكروب إلى استراتيجيات جديدة للوقاية من أمراض القلب الإقفارية وأمراض المناعة الذاتية وفقر الدم والقرحة الهضمية والتهاب المعدة وسرطان المعدة.
- على الرغم من أن هناك العديد من الدراسات المتعلقة بالارتباطات بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني والتسبب في أمراض المناعة الذاتية ، إلا أن البيانات الحالية لا تؤدي تمامًا إلى استنتاجات حتمية بصدد هذا الموضوع ،لذا من الضروري إجراء المزيد من التحليلات السريرية والتجريبية عالية الجودة لتقييم فعالية استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني في تغييرات العلامات الحيوية المناعية التي لوحظت في أمراض المناعة الذاتية.

(الخلاصة)

- تسبب الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني التهاباً مزمناً المعدة وتحفيز الاستجابة المناعية للجسم و قد يكون هذا بسبب المكونات التي يفرزها هذا الميكروب مثل إنزيم اليورياز وهو من ضمن العديد من المحفزات البيئية التي تسبب العديد من أمراض المناعة الذاتية عن طريق تحفيز إنتاج الأجسام المضادة الذاتية من خلال تنشيط خلايا المناعة.
- وجد أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني مرتبط بزيادة خطر الإصابة بمتلازمة التمثيل الغذائي، مما يشير إلى أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني يمكن استخدامها كعامل خطر يزيد من فرصة التعرض للإصابة بمتلازمة التمثيل الغذائي.
- الكشف عن الميكروب الحلزوني باستخدام اختبارات الأجسام المضادة أو المستضدات يمكن دعمها عن طريق إجراء اختبار المتمم المناعي الثالث والمتمم المناعي الرابع أيضاً، حيث يقوم هذا الميكروب بتنشيط المتمم المناعي الثالث بواسطة المستضد من خلال مسار بديل ويؤخر تفعيل المتمم المناعي الرابع في المسار الكلاسيكي عن طريق إفراز أجسام مناعية معينة ،حيث يشير هذا الارتباط إلى إمكانية استخدام التغيير في مستويات المتممات المناعية الثالث والرابع كعلامة حيوية على الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني .

- ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بأمراض الحساسية و فرط حساسية الغلوبولين المناعي إي ، حيث أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤدي إلى التهابات في المعدة تؤدي إلى إتلاف سلامة الحاجز المعدي ، وبالتالي زيادة انتقال المستضدات الغذائية للدم حيث أن الغشاء المخاطي الذي يعمل كحاجز ضد المستضدات يتم تدميره بواسطة الميكروب الحلزوني ، وبالتالي فإن زيادة تدفق مستضدات الطعام التي تمر يزيد من احتمال حدوث رد فعل تحسسي .
- كما أظهرت نتائجنا ارتباطاً بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني واختلال وظائف الكبد مما يؤدي إلى نقص بروتينات الدم، مما يؤكد على أن اعتلال الجهاز الهضمي الناتج عن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني هو أحد أسباب نقص البروتين في الدم.
- تؤدي الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني إلى انخفاض مستوى مصل البروتين في الدم ، وبالتالي نستنتج أن علاج استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني علاجاً فعالاً للوقاية من فقدان الوزن لدى كبار السن.
- الإستجابة المناعية القوية للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تحفز الالتهابات في الجسم حيث يمكننا أن نرى إنعكاس هذه الالتهابات في زيادة مستوى انترليوكين 2 و انتليوكين 6 والبروتين التفاعلي سي حيث يلعب انتليوكين6 دوراً رئيسياً في التسبب في تصلب الشرايين الذي يعد سبباً رئيسياً لمرض القلب التاجي، كما أن الزيادة في مستوى انتليوكين 2 و انتليوكين 6 والبروتين التفاعلي سي الناتجة عن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤثر على الكبد وبالتالي تؤثر على جميع علامات الالتهابات التي ينتجها الكبد.
- يعتبر الميكروب الحلزوني أحد أكثر العوامل المعدية التي تمت دراستها بشكل شائع والتي تقترح كعوامل محفزة لإستجابة المناعة الذاتية التي تؤدي إلى زيادة تركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة مما يفسر دور الميكروب الحلزوني في تطور أمراض المناعة الذاتية .
- لا تسبب عدوى الملوية البوابية مجموعة متنوعة من أمراض المعدة والأمعاء فحسب ، بل تشارك أيضاً في التسبب في العديد من اضطرابات المناعة الذاتية مثل التهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي ، مرض نقص الصفائح مجهول السبب ، متلازمة سجوجرن ، ضمور المعدة المناعي الذاتي ،متلازمة التهاب الغدة الدرقية المضاد للفسفوليبيد،التهاب الغدة الدرقية المناعي و الالتهاب الوعائي بالغلوبولين المناعي أي.

- قد يكون للميكروب الحلزوني تأثيرات سمية عصبية مباشرة تؤدي إلى تغيير المحور العصبي القناة الهضمية المتصل بالدماغ من خلال تنشيط العمليات الالتهابية العصبية التي تزيد من الكورتيزول والأدرينالين.
- كما توصلنا في دراستنا إلى أن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني تؤدي إلى مقاومة الأنسولين ، ومقاومة الأنسولين تؤدي إلى فرط أنسولين الدم الذي يحفز تحلل السكر ويؤدي إلى زيادة مستوى البيروفات واللاكتات في الدم ، ومن المعروف أيضاً أن الأنسولين يحفز إنتاج الألبومين في خلايا الكبد مما يؤدي إلى زيادة مستوى الألبومين لدى الأشخاص المصابين بالميكروب الحلزوني.
- ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بزيادة في علامات الإجهاد المناعي مثل النظام المتمم المناعي و الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي (إي وجي وإم وأي)، وتركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة والتي ترتبط بأمراض المناعة الذاتية ، كما ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني أيضاً بزيادة مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم لهذا السبب ربما يكون الميكروب الحلزوني مسؤول عن اضطراب الجهاز المناعي واضطراب المناعة الذاتية والاضطراب العقلي .
- قد تكون الزيادة الكبيرة في البيروفات واللاكتات في المريض المصاب بالميكروب الحلزوني بسبب فرط أنسولين الدم أو مقاومة الأنسولين الناتجة عن الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني ، التي تسبب مقاومة الأنسولين مما يؤدي إلى زيادة الأنسولين في الدم الذي يحفز تحلل السكر وينتج كميات كبيرة من البيروفات التي تتحول إلى لاكتات حيث إن اللاكتات هي أحد أكثر المنتجات الثانوية المخصصة لعملية التمثيل الغذائي الخلوي في الأنسجة الملتهبة. يؤدي تراكمه إلى تفاقم الاستجابة الالتهابية في الاضطرابات الالتهابية المزمنة مثل التهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي.
- ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني بزيادة في علامات الإجهاد المناعي مثل النظام المتمم المناعي و الأجسام المضادة للغلوبولين المناعي (إي وجي وإم وأي)، وتركيز الأجسام المضادة تجاه الحمض النووي المضاعف و الأجسام المضادة للنواة والتي ترتبط بأمراض المناعة الذاتية ، كما ترتبط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني أيضاً بزيادة مستوى الكورتيزول في الدم لهذا السبب ربما يكون الميكروب الحلزوني مسؤول عن اضطراب الجهاز المناعي واضطراب المناعة الذاتية.

(التوصيات)

- أظهرت نتائجنا ارتباطاً إيجابياً كبيراً بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وإنتاج الأجسام المضادة إي كمؤشر على القابلية للإصابة بالحساسية ، والتي يمكن استخدامها لتحسين استراتيجيات علاج مرضى الحساسية.
- المرضى الذين يعانون من عسر الهضم أو زيادة السيتوكينات الجهازية لأسباب غير معروفة يجب أن يخضعوا لمزيد من الفحوصات والدراسات السريرية الكاشفة للإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني والالتهابات الناجمة عن هذه الإصابة، حيث أثبتنا في هذه الدراسة مدى ارتباط الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وزيادة فرص التعرض للإصابة بمرض الذئبة أو زيادة أعراضه المرضية ، مما قد يغير نهجنا الحالي في الإدارة السريرية لمرض الذئبة.
- قد يكون علاج استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني للمرضى المسنين المصابين بالتهاب المعدة المزمن نتيجة الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني علاجاً فعالاً للوقاية من فقدان الوزن لدى كبار السن وتجنب الإصابة بأمراض القلب وبعض أمراض المناعة الذاتية كالذئبة والتهاب المفاصل الروماتويدي.
- يوصى بإجراء دراسات مستقبلية وتدخلية إضافية لتوضيح العلاقة السببية بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني وأمراض القلب الإقفارية، ولتقييم تأثير الاستئصال العلاجي للميكروب الحلزوني على عوامل الخطر القلبية الوعائية.
- الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني عامل خطر رئيسي للإصابة بضمور الغشاء المخاطي في المعدة لذا يعتبر مستوى الأجسام المضادة أي و جي مؤشرات جيدة لتقييم هذا التقدم مع نسبة معينة وقد توفر الدراسات السريرية فهماً أفضل لأسباب المرض وسهولة تشخيصه والوصول إلى علاج جذري لهذا الميكروب.
- نظراً لأنه يمكن علاج الميكروب الحلزوني بسهولة وعن طريق علاجات محددة ،لذا قد يؤدي التعريف الدقيق لخطر الإصابة بهذا الميكروب إلى استراتيجيات جديدة للوقاية من أمراض القلب الإقفارية وأمراض المناعة الذاتية وفقر الدم والقرحة الهضمية والتهاب المعدة وسرطان المعدة.

➤ على الرغم من أن هناك العديد من الدراسات المتعلقة بالارتباطات بين الإصابة بالميكروب الحلزوني والتسبب في أمراض المناعة الذاتية ، إلا أن البيانات الحالية لا تؤدي تمامًا إلى استنتاجات حتمية بصدد هذا الموضوع ،لذا من الضروري إجراء المزيد من التحليلات السريرية والتجريبية عالية الجودة لتقييم فعالية استئصال الميكروب الحلزوني في تغييرات العلامات الحيوية المناعية التي لوحظت في أمراض المناعة الذاتية.

السيرة الذاتية

- الاسم: مروة محمد عادل سلامة متولي
- تاريخ الميلاد: 1984/11/25
- حصلت على الشهادة الابتدائية من مدرسة المنار الابتدائية للبنات- دولة الإمارات العربية المتحدة عام 1997م.
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- حصلت الباحثة على دبلوم الكيمياء الحيوية الاكلينيكية- كلية العلوم جامعة الاسكندرية عام 2008م.
- حصلت الباحثة على درجة الدكتوراة في (الكيمياء الحيوية والكيمياء الإكلينيكية) بكلية الطب البيطري بنها ديسمبر 2015.
- سجلت الباحثة للحصول على درجة الدكتوراة في (الكيمياء الحيوية والكيمياء الإكلينيكية) بكلية الطب البيطري بنها بنوفمبر 2016.

إهداء

إلى والداى الحبيبان ..
اللذان زرعاً في الرغبة أن أكون أفضل ..
وأن أتخطى صعاب الحياة .. تعثراً فهوض ..
إلى زوجى الحبيب ..
سندى وداعمى وأمانى ..
الذى دفعنى قُدماً إلى الأمام .. وأعاننى على الاستمرار ..
إلى أولادى ..
ثمرة حياتى .. وعبيرها الدائم
إلى كل من مد يداً .. لتذلل عوائقى ..
أو نوراً ليضىء دربى ..
إليهم جميعاً .. أهدى ثمرة جهدى ,,,,,,

جامعة بنها
كلية الطب البيطري
قسم الكيمياء الحيوية

التأثير الكيميائي الحيوي للميكروب الحلزوني على الدلالات الحيوية للإجهاد المناعي

رسالة مقدمة إلى

كلية الطب البيطري - جامعة بنها

للحصول على

درجة الدكتوراة في العلوم الطبية البيطرية
(تخصص الكيمياء الحيوية والكيمياء الإكلينيكية)

مقدمة من

كيمائية/ مروة محمد عادل سلامة متولى

بكالوريوس العلوم - شعبة الكيمياء الحيوية - كلية العلوم - جامعة الأسكندرية 2007م.
دبلوم الكيمياء الحيوية الإكلينيكية - كلية العلوم - جامعة الأسكندرية 2008م.
ماجستير الكيمياء الحيوية - كلية الطب البيطري - جامعة بنها 2015م.

تحت إشراف

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د/ الشيماء محمد سعيد عبد الصادق

أستاذ مساعد الكيمياء الحيوية
كلية الطب البيطري - جامعة بنها